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D4.1: Report on identifying research needs for climate change mitigation technology options

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PREFACE

The **CARISMA** project (“**C**oordination and **A**ssessment of **R**esearch and **I**nnovation in **S**upport of climate **M**itigation **O**ptions”) intends, through effective stakeholder consultation and communication leading to improved coordination and assessment of climate change mitigation options, to benefit research and innovation efficiency, as well as international cooperation on research and innovation and technology transfer.

Additionally, it aims to assess policy and governance questions that shape the prospects of climate change mitigation options and discuss the results with representatives from the target audiences to incorporate what can be learned for the benefit of climate change mitigation.

Knowledge gaps will be identified for a range priority issues related to climate change mitigation options and climate policy making in consultation with stakeholders.

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CB5	University of Graz	UNI Graz	AT
CB6	Stockholm Environment Institute	SEI	SE
CB7	Centre for European Economic Research	ZEW	DE
CB8	Center for European Policy Studies	CEPS	BE
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1. Summary

This section summarizes the main findings of the work presented in this report regarding needs and priority areas for further research, for the cases of Bio-Energy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) and Solar Photovoltaic (Solar PV). BECCS technology is highly controversial. On the one hand, it demonstrates a growing number of supporters and is considered by many climate scientists, as one of the most promising negative emissions technologies, with considerable potential to achieve climate goals (e.g. the 1.5°C goal), especially in light of the recent “neutral emissions” debate. At the same time, a potential sizeable reliance on BECCS has raised concerns amongst researchers and policy makers, mainly with regard to sustainability issues (e.g. vast areas of land for the cultivation of biomass, land competing uses, food security, etc.). In contrast, Solar PV is a competitive technology, which has been proven capable to create value and provide services to many stakeholders. However, to continue its exponential growth and remain at the centre of the energy transition, it has to provide solutions to different challenges that have emerged due to its increased deployment.

Our work aims to provide insights on research gaps and areas in priority that can be taken up by academic institutions and researchers, as well as associated insights, for policy decision makers to enhance the development and deployment of these two-key climate change mitigation options. To do so, our approach is focused on combining stakeholders’ perspectives and concerns with regard to future research needs and priorities, with scientific literature to conclude with specific directions for further research and applications. In particular, we used association representatives’ knowledge and position papers as a starting point for the identification of key research challenges and needs and complemented the latter by relevant and updated scientific literature in the field. Interesting findings, summarized below, arose from both stakeholder feedback and literature review.

1.1. Synthesis of findings from stakeholder dialogue

The first interesting finding which arose from the feedback from representatives of the respective technology associations is their perception on the different aspects that merit further research. Reportedly, for the case of BECCS, the aspect with the greatest urgency for further research is the environmental one, addressing the assessment of GHG emissions reduction in the value chain of BECCS, as well as, the BECCS impact in the food-water-energy-climate nexus (e.g. impacts in land, land requirements, impact in human health, climate mitigation benefits, etc.). Economic (e.g. microeconomic and avoidance costs (mitigation/welfare) costs in the whole value chain of BECCS, issues of affordability, profitability and contribution to sectoral and regional growth, etc.), social

(e.g. social acceptance, public awareness, issues of public perceptions, etc.) and technological (e.g. technical features and challenges of the different biomass conversion technology routes in terms of increasing efficiency, uncertainty of future performance, areas for further innovations and technological breakthroughs, etc.) aspects are right after in terms of urgency for further research. Finally, the Sintef¹ association considered the market readiness aspect in terms of maturity and demand for BECCS the less urgent for further research.

On the other hand, EPIA (SolarPower Europe) representatives stated that for the case of Solar PV the aspects with the greatest urgency for further research are both the economic and the technological ones. More specifically, the economic dimension is a key priority, as it, also, includes the political/regulatory dimension. All the current changes and developments regarding valorising the PV technology in a market framework that tries to adapt in new conditions are linked with the economic and business dimension for all stakeholders and consumers. The technological dimension is also of importance, as there are many technologies to work on and further improve.

For market exploitation, current technologies are fully bankable. PV should also follow the learning curve of technological evolution when it comes to synergies with other sectors (storage, IT, etc.). Furthermore, according to EPIA social aspect comes right after in terms of urgency for further research. However, especially for the case of Solar PV that is a proven clean renewable option which offers the distributed dimension and directly links with the customer (prosumer), the urgency is less, as the social benefits, acceptance by customer (for the residential systems—creating a feeling of ownership and control of power source) and value of the technology (e.g. employment) are in many cases evident.

Finally, the environmental and market readiness aspects come as the least urgent for further research according to EPIA, with the environmental aspect having a slight edge of urgency. More specifically, from an environmental perspective, many studies have already shown great reductions in the energy and material use for PV, as they have been developed a lot from that aspect and still are. The main focus should be on the recycling and reuse discussion of PV modules. From a market readiness perspective PV has already proven to be a mature technology, with many, already, using the word commodity.

1.2. Synthesis of findings from literature

To synthesize literature findings regarding identified needs and priority areas for further research, in a comprehensive and meaningful way for potential end-users, the authors used key themes of the Technology Framework under Article 10, paragraph 4, of the

¹SINTEF is the largest independent research organization in Scandinavia and member of the ZEP.

Paris Agreement (UNFCCC, 2016b). The selected overarching themes were namely (i) Innovation, (ii) Implementation, (iii) Enabling Environment/Capacity Building and (iv) Collaboration/Stakeholder Engagement. These served to categorize and map, according to the authors' expert judgement, the research priorities identified through the review and compare them across the mitigation options under study.

1.2.1. Innovation

In terms of Innovation for the case of BECCS, the main research priorities focus on the development, demonstration and diffusion of new technology routes and production methods across the different value chains. Analysing in parallel their economic and commercial viability, with the optimization of the existing technology routes and production methods is also considered in need of collaborative R&D approaches and support (Gough and Upham, 2010; Arasto et al., 2014; Kemper, 2015). More specifically, further research should focus on new biogas feedstocks, new biomass to biogas conversion routes and biogas upgrading techniques using CO₂ removal (Biorecro, 2011; Koornneef et al., 2013; Susmozas et al., 2015; Budzianowski, 2016). New technologies for cultivation of (micro-) algae and algal biomass production methods demand future research (Alam, Mobin, et al., 2015; Milano et al., 2016), along with the optimization of the current boilers' design to avoid the consequences of corrosion (Koornneef et al., 2012; Milne and Field, 2012)

For the case of Solar PV, the main research priorities regarding Innovation focus on the development, demonstration and diffusion of new PV technologies. The needs for further research relate to the further material development focusing on the use of less material, such as thinner wafers (e.g. epi-foil wafers) to achieve higher efficiencies and lower production costs (CHEETAH, 2016b; Nelson, et al., 2014; Neij, 2008; PIC, 2012). Additionally, technological advancements towards the better understanding and assessment of the potential and synergies of PV systems with Demand Response (DR), Energy Management Systems (EMS), Electric Vehicles (EVs) and stationary storage technologies are also required (Burger & Luke, 2016; Azzopardi & Gabriel-Buenaventura, 2014; PATHWAYS, 2015b; Parag & Sovacool, 2016; Graabak & Korpås, 2016). Finally, future research should also focus on the development of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools to support the control of power flows, along with the development of meteorological forecasting tools to obtain accurate results of the expected electricity generation (Lingfors, 2015; EDF R&D, 2015; PROSUITE, 2010).

For both cases literature agrees that research efforts should focus on how networking between key actors within developing countries and with counterpart entities in developed countries could allow actors in innovation systems to interact fruitfully strengthening the National Systems of Innovation. Effective technology transfer requires

the building of innovation capabilities in developing countries through transfer of knowledge, however especially for the case of BECCS this is still lacking in practice.

1.2.2. Implementation

In terms of Implementation, the main research priorities for the case of BECCS focus on the assessment of the appropriateness of the various BECCS technology routes. More specifically, literature mainly highlights the further improvement of data accuracy on sustainably available land (IEA, 2010; AVOID 2, 2015a; AVOID 2, 2015c) and the further impact assessment of Land-Use Change (LUC) due to the use of BECCS (IPCC, 2014; Kemper, 2015; AVOID 2, 2015c; Popp et al., 2017). Available land resources and land requirements of BECCS should thoroughly be assessed, given that large areas of land will be required if BECCS are to make a significant contribution to future mitigation strategies (Gough and Upham, 2010; IEA, 2010; Rose et al., 2013; Fiorese et al., 2014; Dowd, Rodriguez et al., 2015; Fuss, 2016).

Additionally, BECCS potential per region in terms of CO₂ transport and storage capacities should be further assessed (Gough and Upham, 2010) and future Life-Cycle Analysis (LCAs) should consider the long-term storage properties of biogenic CO₂ in terms of safety and CO₂ leakages (Dowd, Rodriguez et al., 2015; Kemper, 2015; AVOID 2, 2015c). Future research should also focus on maximizing yields for biomass supply considering the whole bioenergy life-cycle from supply and harvesting to processing and conversion (ZEP and EBTP, 2012). Furthermore, further research should assess the potential of different BECCS technology routes (e.g. bio-methane production with CCS, CO₂ capture from bio-ethanol production, combustion and gasification with CO₂ capture and storage, (co-) firing biomass with CO₂ capture, etc.) on national or local level, in terms of economic viability and infrastructure boundary conditions (Gough and Upham, 2010; Biorecro, 2011; Koornneef et al., 2013; Arasto et al., 2014; Kemper, 2015; Susmozas et al., 2015; Budzianowski, 2016). Finally, quantification of the impact that the different BECCS technology routes have on human health is necessary to achieve the efficient implementation of BECCS (Kemper, 2015).

On the other hand, needs for further research in terms of implementation for the case of Solar PV focus on how different assessments of PV modules could be enhanced to determine their appropriateness (in specific contexts) and to enhance the implementation of National Technology Action Plans and project ideas. Indicatively, further LCAs should include global scale challenges, geographical differentiations, rebound effects, renewability of resources and future scenario modelling (Ling-Chin, et al., 2016). They should, also, include the recycling of module components (cables, inverters etc.) apart from modules themselves (e.g. methodology for assessing the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) of a PV) and the assessment of solar cooling/heating systems considering

PV and heating/cooling devices as a single unit (Solar Bankability, 2016b; Carnevale, et al., 2014; Testi, et al., 2016; Hussain, et al., 2016). Furthermore, future research should concentrate on the optimization of cell manufacturing and wafer handling processes to achieve further cost reduction and increased module efficiency via defects reduction (PROSUITE, 2010; Nelson, et al., 2014; EC, 2014a; CHEETAH, 2016b). Finally, research efforts to enhance the implementation of PV projects should be placed on accelerating tests and necessary quality improvements to ensure high lifetime performances of components (including the whole value chain) (Solar Bankability, 2016b; Solar Bankability, 2016c; Munoz, et al., 2011; Sharma & Chandel, 2013; SAPC, 2015).

1.2.3. Enabling environment and capacity building

Research priorities for the case of BECCS focus on addressing factors that limit sustainable supply of biomass at a regional level and actions to increase this supply (Gough and Upham, 2010; IPCC, 2014). The need to make the most promising biomass conversion technologies commercially available beyond 2020 (Brennan and Owende, 2010; Biorecro, 2011; Saidur et al., 2011; Milne and Field, 2012) and commercialize the production costs of biofuels from (micro-) algae at large scale (Mata, Martins et al., 2010; Alam, Mobin, et al., 2015) is also highlighted. Finally, future research should focus on quantifying the key factors that influence the trade volume and price of biomass and assessing the political acceptability and application of sufficient and safe biogenic storage at large scales (Azar et al., 2010; Fuss et al., 2014).

For the case of PV, needs for future research identified to enable their further diffusion mainly concern the design/use of incentives for further PV industry establishment in the EU (Goodrich, et al., 2013). As highlighted by the representative from SolarPower Europe participating in the consultation, more grid studies with high VAR RES scenarios and the revision of energy market rules/regulations to better reflect the specificities of variable energy sources are also needed. Relevant implications have also been found in the scientific literature (IEA, 2015a; RServiceS, 2014; Brouwer, et al., 2016; Huber, et al., 2014). Finally, further data acquisition procedures and mechanisms that track the operation of PV systems to achieve less visual inspection and less O&M costs are necessary. These would also serve to provide statistically relevant results on the effects of curtailment for PV (Solar Bankability, 2016b; IEA, 2014a; INSIGHT ENERGY, 2014)

While the literature review has shown that research efforts related to enabling environments are critical for the successful development and transfer of both BECCS and Solar PV, research efforts to build capacities were not explicitly mentioned in academic literature across the different research themes. Thus, there is still much to be done in understanding how such capacity may be developed, especially in developing countries and as a result supporting capacity building in developing countries through skills training for planning and implementation is crucial.

1.2.4. Collaboration and stakeholder engagement

Research priorities for the case of BECCS focus on how to enhance the collaboration between developed and developing countries to build capacities for advanced biofuels and to ensure technology access (IEA, 2010). Bringing together different actors/components from different fields and areas with different motives to create a strong BECCS technology network, including both biomass and CCS actors, is also required (Biorecro, 2011; Gough and Upham, 2011; Vergragt, Markusson et al., 2011; Dowd, Rodriguez et al., 2015).

Future research should, also, focus on how BECCS is perceived compared to fossil fuel based CCS projects in the media, to address risks and uncertainties and to increase awareness (Biorecro, 2011; Dowd, Rodriguez et al., 2015). Finally, synergies and benefits of BECCS with current European CCS strategies should be further studied (Biorecro, 2011; Vergragt, Markusson et al., 2011; Pickard et al., 2014; Kemper, 2015; Hetland et al., 2016). Overall, building a global network of knowledgeable and skilled organizations and individuals is a core objective for the case of BECCS and future efforts and activities from stakeholders in the field should focus more on how to achieve that.

Priorities for the case of Solar PV in terms of collaboration and stakeholder engagement, focus on how to conduct consultations and open-fair discussions to determine the national cost-benefit ratios, the boundary conditions and the compensation rules for the PV owner, in case that curtailment is enforced (compared to grid reinforcement) with a goal to reduce grid expansion expenses (PV GRID, 2014). Moreover, the representative from SolarPower Europe participating in the consultation stated that open discussion on the quality standardization of PV systems including the whole value chain should also be promoted. Overall coordination and support efforts should focus on facilitating open and transparent communication among cross-country stakeholders to identify and deploy long-term sustainable solutions for the wider deployment of variable power generation technologies at a regional level (IEA, 2014a; IEA, 2015a; REserviceS, 2014).

In sum, the results of the synthesis across the 4 selected priority areas revealed a heterogeneous landscape of numerous and diverse mechanisms, activities and initiatives for both the cases of BECCS and Solar PV. An outline of the main suggested policy implications and practices is provided below (see Table 1), which seek to address the identified research needs and challenges while providing useful insights for policy- and decision-makers, as well as, the research community. For a detailed analysis of the research priorities and policy implications identified for BECCS and Solar PV you may refer to sections 4.4 and 5.4 respectively.

Table 1: Main implications for policy and practice according to the identified needs and priorities for further research for the cases of BECCS and Solar PV.

BECCS	Solar PV
<p>R&D funding/programmes to support the Improvement of the efficiency and the commercialization of the various BECCS technology routes and the establishment of the necessary CCS and biomass infrastructure.</p>	<p>R&D funding/programmes to support the development of new market-business models, synergies with storage technologies/Demand Response (DR), technical upgrades in solar cooling/heating technologies, further material development and the algorithmic development of digital systems.</p>
<p>New mechanisms and innovative financing processes-Incentives creation to enable BECCS opportunities from both the public and the private sectors and to enable the technology uptake and the necessary infrastructure establishment for advanced sustainable biofuels.</p>	<p>New mechanisms and innovative financing processes-Incentives creation to guarantee financing for small and medium-size investors.</p>
<p>Promoting collaboration: (1) between CCS, biomass and BECCS stakeholders, (2) countries that grow biomass and countries with CCS know-how, (3) countries (developed and developing) that have high advanced sustainable biofuels capacity, but limited funding capabilities.</p>	<p>Promoting collaboration between stakeholders for long-term sustainable solutions in a regional level, on the quality standardization of PV systems including the whole value chain.</p>
<p>Revision/Streamlining of policy measures (e.g. certification schemes) to promote sustainability criteria for the sustainable use of biomass and to limit competing uses of agricultural land.</p>	<p>Revision/Streamlining of policy measures to: Develop quality standards & certificates for PV systems including the whole value chain also O&M; Re-design of market rules & support schemes to accommodate and promote new business models for electricity generation.</p>

2. Introduction

2.1. Background

Climate Change Mitigation Options (CCMOs) are essential when combating climate change, while their further development and transfer needs to be accelerated in face of an urgent need to reduce global annual emissions of greenhouse gases by 2020 and beyond (Cozzi, 2011). The Paris Agreement came into force on 4 November 2016 with an ambition of limiting global warming to 1.5 °C above pre-industrial levels signalling the urgency for “a balance between anthropogenic emissions by sources and removals by sinks of greenhouse gases in the second half of this century” (UNFCCC, 2016a). Essentially the agreement serves as a catalyst for national developments by keeping the issue on dangerous climate change on the agenda and urging policymakers of nations worldwide to constantly revisit it (Oberghassel et al., 2016).

With the emergence of the Paris agreement, a new innovative system of nationally determined contributions (NDCs) by nations around the world has been established reflecting countries’ highest ambition in terms of taking climate measures beyond what has been previously implemented (UNFCCC, 2016a; Vandyck et al., 2016; Murphy and McDonnell, 2017). Nations also made notable decisions to continue a two-year work plan to guide future work especially with regard to the “Enhanced technology framework” among other issues. An Enhanced technology framework will aim to improve existing Technology mechanism² and includes five overarching themes to be further elaborated in the next negotiating session in 2017, namely: innovation, implementation, enabling environments and capacity building, collaboration and stakeholder engagement and support. These themes reflect persistent issues, which can limit the potential of key mitigation technologies necessary to implement the Paris agreement nationally and globally. To ensure the efforts of countries to meet with the Paris agreement objectives, it becomes increasingly important to identify dynamic challenges relevant to innovation, implementation and enabling environments, so as to guide future research and assessments on key mitigation technologies to enable their further deployment (UNFCCC, 2016a; de Coninck and Sagar, 2015).

Identifying the challenges and needs for further research for climate change mitigation technologies is thus important for the implementation of international climate

²Within the UNFCCC process, countries have confirmed the importance of enhancing climate technology development and transfer to developing countries. To facilitate this, in 2010 the Conference of the Parties established the Technology Mechanism.

agreements. Stakeholders from the research community, as well as, from the industry need to be fully aware and updated on emerging issues to focus their efforts on key priority areas that are essential for further and much needed rapid deployment of mitigation technologies (UNDP, 2010). In addition, information regarding mitigation technologies for reaching the 1.5°C goal is also crucial for national policymakers to make more informed decisions and propose concrete policy actions that will ensure their further deployment. Needs on further assessments and industrial applications vary to a great extent across different mitigation technologies and can assist private actors to make better investment decisions when choosing appropriate mitigation technology measures. Therefore, providing reliable and up-to-date information on the needs for further research to address eminent challenges in the implementation of key mitigation technologies is deemed not only relevant, but also essential across different national industries and governments to determine their future support and efforts.

2.2. Identifying research needs and priority areas for key Climate Change Mitigation Options

With the attention now on the implementation of the Paris Agreement, the energy sector should maintain international political momentum in order to deliver carbon neutral electricity supply by 2050. Given that energy represents the lion's share of global emissions, the energy sector is essential for driving sustainability. The European electricity sector believes that decarbonization is important for the long-term sustainability of the global economy and focuses on leading this transition (Cooper, 2016; Eurelectric, 2016; Vandyck et al., 2016).

Currently, the European power system is in the middle of transformations driven by a shared climate agenda. To meet this agenda, the following ingredients are essential: higher energy efficiency; generation largely and increasingly based on renewable energy sources (RES); an efficiently used and where necessary expanded high voltage grid respectful of nature conservation objectives; smarter transmission and distribution grids; smarter meters; empowered consumers via demand-side response; electricity storage; and a fit for purpose interface between the transmission and distribution levels of the electricity system. All these are key components to fighting global warming and creating a sustainable power system for the 21st century (Eurelectric, 2016).

In addition, many climate scientists argue that early peaking of global emissions around 2020 and rapid decline towards zero emissions are critical for achieving the Paris goal and that the term decarbonization has been replaced by a much vaguer "emissions neutrality". As a result, achieving the Agreement's mitigation and temperature goals could mean that globally negative CO₂ emissions are required by the second half of the

century to remove the gas from the atmosphere and store it on land, underground or in the oceans. Achieving negative emissions signals the deployment of uncertain and at present controversial technologies, including biomass energy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) (Lewis, 2015; Anderson and Peters, 2016; Fuss, 2016).

The purpose of this report is to support current knowledge and provide an overview of needs for further research and analysis of policy implications and technical issues related to the development and further deployment of BECCS and Solar PV. Although BECCS is still in early development stages, it is already considered to have significant potential to achieve climate goals, especially in light of the recent “neutral emissions” debate. On the other hand, Solar PV, having achieved market maturity, is one of the two technologies on track for a 2°C scenario (along with onshore wind) and thus, presents increased interest for the sustainability of the power sector and entail important insights for policy and practice. Identified analytical gaps and areas for further research and applications can be taken up by academic institutions and researchers, as well as from relevant industry associations to enhance the development and deployment of these two-key climate change mitigation options.

BECCS

Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) is considered as one of the most promising negative emissions technologies. Even though they have yet to be demonstrated at a commercial scale, negative emissions technologies (typically BECCS) are now included by climate scientists in the majority of modelled “pathways” showing how the 1.5°C goal could be achieved. BECCS is considered “carbon negative”, since bioenergy is theoretically “carbon neutral,” based on the idea that plants will regrow to fix the carbon that has been emitted. However, many critics argue that this overlooks emissions from land use change and life cycle emissions (ZEP and EBTP, 2012). Although large BECCS deployment facilitates reaching the 1.5°C target in scenarios and allows for some flexibility in other sectors that are difficult to decarbonize rapidly, such as the non-CO₂ greenhouse gases associated with the food system, the large reliance on BECCS has raised uneasiness amongst policymakers, the public, and scientists, with risks to sustainability being voiced as the prime concern.

For example, the large-scale deployment of BECCS would require vast areas of land to be set aside for the cultivation of biomass, which raises competing uses between the conservation of ecosystem services and ensuring food security in the face of a still growing population. Political implications are further enhanced by the fact that suitable area for growing biomass is not distributed evenly across the globe. To this end, further research regarding BECCS potential and regional opportunities should be routed

addressing existing risks and concerns (ZEP and EBTP, 2012; Fuss et al., 2014; Kemper, 2015; Fuss, 2016).

Solar PV

Solar PV has grown and developed beyond anyone's expectations. It has managed to become one of the key technologies of RES for the energy transition. To achieve this, it had to follow a very steep learning curve-reducing the costs and increasing efficiency (conversion and energy). Reducing the cost of the technology was the main challenge until a couple of years ago. Nowadays, this is no longer considered the first priority, as to continue the exponential growth and really be at the end centre of the energy transition, it has to provide solutions to different challenges that have emerged due to the increased shares. Those are mainly regulatory and consequently financial/business challenges (EPIA, 2012).

Solar PV can lead the way to new models of sustainable development with new investments, industries and employment generation. Thus, opportunities raised by the further development of Solar PV should be embraced. Since one-third of energy-related CO₂ emissions worldwide are from the power sector, many climate scientists and experts believe that Solar PV can make a significant contribution to reducing emissions, which in turn will contribute to limiting the temperature increase. Acknowledging that solar power is now well on the way to being a fully competitive alternative to conventional energy, participating to the transition towards a sustainable energy future, the earlier country and cross-country energy markets, begin to accelerate the pace of installations, the less capacity will be required at the end (EPIA, 2012; SolarPower Europe, 2015; Eurobat, Epha, SolarPower Europe, 2016).

3. Approach for identifying needs for further research for Climate Change Mitigation Options (CCMOs)

There is a large body of academic literature focusing on the assessment of climate change mitigation options, analysis of demonstration programmes and industry pilots, feasibility studies for different CCMOs and literature reviews amounting to hundreds of papers. In addition to scientific literature, position papers are being published regularly from relevant technology associations presenting priority areas aiming to bridge the gap between basic research and market needs. These position papers were considered in this report to provide a good basis for identifying key challenges and needs for future mitigation technology assessments. Stakeholders' knowledge and concerns were also considered as one of the main sources for identifying assessment needs.

The methodology that was adopted for the identification of needs for further research of CCMOs is described next.

The **first step** was to identify the relevant technology associations for each option under study. This was considered the starting point because technology associations express the needs and barriers faced by the respective businesses and technology providers. To this end, for each mitigation technology under assessment, we identified associated technology associations or technology platforms established at European or global level.

A first filter was applied to limit the search results based on the type of the identified position papers. Scientific reports and studies conducted from research associations not clearly expressing the positions were not included in the first part of this analysis, as they were only considered relevant for the second step of the approach (i.e. literature review). When a position paper was available, we evaluated its appropriateness with criteria related to the date of publishing, list of references used and analysis used to support the positions. In addition, we evaluated the legal status of the association, how long has it been established, its members in Europe and worldwide, as well as its activity overall to determine whether it was relevant and representative to include.

At the same time, information collected from position papers was complemented by information collected through a direct contact with the associations³. The goal was to ascertain the respective associations' views on key challenges and research needs required to enhance the development of the mitigation technologies under assessment

³For each technology association identified, representatives were contacted via email to verify on the positions of the associations, as well as to provide additional ones through the use of a semi-structured questionnaire (see Annexes II and IV). Details on the stakeholders who responded to the consultation can be found in the respective technology chapters.

(see **Figure 1**). The consultation process was undertaken through emails to the relevant technology associations supportive of the deployment of mitigations technologies, from July to December 2016. A list with details on the stakeholders who participated in the consultation and the position papers used to complement the outcomes of the consultation is provided in Annexes II and IV.

Section 1 summarizes the information on “needs”, “challenges” and “issues” identified through the most updated position papers and consultation with the relevant technology associations. In particular, from the insights that emerged from the consultations and the positions expressed by technology associations in the relevant position papers, we identified recurrent themes and distilled them into specific key-research areas and topics.

The **second step** consists of a review of the available information in the scientific literature regarding the research priority areas that were previously identified. To this end, the collected information on needs for further research and assessments for the selected CCMOs was synthesized into thematic categories and keywords to guide the literature sampling. Our goal was to ensure that literature research is done in a structured way so that we minimize the probability of leaving out important and information-rich contributions. We searched several combinations of the technology options under study or specific categories of those technologies with specific related keywords, as: “cost-benefit analysis”, “assessment”, “innovation”, “new business models”, “sustainability issues”, etc.

Since the scope of the literature review was to identify up-to-date assessment needs for each technology option, we limited the literature search to the period of 2008 until 2016. Due to a large number of relevant findings on the assessments for each mitigation option, the analysis of evidence from the literature was based on a randomized sample ($n = 60+$, *varying by technology option*). Our literature review was not exhaustive rather it served to provide evidence on whether specific up-to-date needs have already been identified from the academic community and whether additional more specific ones are raised.

Finally, in the **third step** of the methodology, we provide a synthesis of the available information gathered from both technology associations and recent literature and discuss key policy implications. Through this approach, we are able to compare the perspective of industrial and technology associations with the viewpoints from the scientific community (as reflected in recent literature).

Figure 1: Steps and approach adopted for identifying needs for further research

4. Bio-Energy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS)

4.1. Summary of key research needs and priority areas for BECCS

▲ **The need for further cost assessment of BECCS**

The main obstacles for BECCS demonstration relate to scale, location (the need to be close to biomass resources) and the lack of infrastructure. Infrastructure is very important when predicting the costs of CO₂ transport and storage. There is a lack of consistent and comprehensive assessments of current and expected costs of BECCS. Future research should focus on assessing the BECCS potential per region through specific cost supply curves for CO₂ transport, and storage and biomass availability.

▲ **BECCS from a life cycle perspective**

To date, only few studies address the life cycle assessment of BECCS. Experts point out that emissions vary with the specific application and the location of each project and thus life-cycle emissions should be assessed for each specific BECCS project. Further research is important to focus on optimization of supply, conversion and storage systems assessing life-cycle risks, investigating the best use of biomass. Further quantification of the impact different BECCS technology routes have on human health is also an important area for future research from a life-cycle perspective.

▲ **Further assessment of the land requirements of BECCS**

Few studies so far have investigated the land requirements for BECCS. Given that large areas of land will be required if BECCS is to be integrated in the future climate change mitigation strategies, future research on impact assessment of Land-Use Changes due to BECCS application should receive attention to avoid negative consequences (e.g. carbon stock loss, decrease/neutralize net positive GHG mitigation outcomes, etc.).

▲ **The potential for pitfalls**

BECCS is not without the potential for pitfalls, as there is no guarantee that the sourcing of biomass will always be from sustainable sources. Sustainability criteria should be applied when assessing the potential for BECCS technologies and additional research should verify these results with more detailed assessments of factors that limit sustainable supply of biomass at a regional level.

▲ **Promising biomass conversion routes to enable the necessary economies of scale**

Several routes to convert biomass to energy are already available and applicable, but still need to be adapted to BECCS. Several studies have already looked at a number of ways to convert biomass in a BECCS system examining which conversions are most efficient, technically feasible and can be integrated to CCS. Future research should account for optimal plant size for biomass combustion and conversion systems to enable the economies of scale needed for BECCS implementation.

▲ **Increasing public awareness and social acceptance**

One of the main issues of BECCS is the lack of a supporting community, awareness and credibility amongst its own key stakeholders and the wider public. The key supporters of BECCS so far are mainly academics and NGOs. Further research should explore how the human factor (e.g. different actors/components from different fields, positions, motives, etc.) can influence the further deployment of BECCS. Further research should also be oriented towards how BECCS is perceived compared to fossil fuel based CCS projects in the media to increase empirical knowledge.

▲ **Accelerating research into advanced sustainable biofuels**

Understanding the feasibility of CCS application to different biofuel plants is crucial for the future deployment of BECCS. Thus, further research on infrastructure and new technological breakthroughs are important for the future of BECCS.

▲ **Biogas (co-)firing with CCS**

BECCS can be integrated to biofuel production units such as biogas and hydrogen production plants making a competitive alternative compared with fossil fuel fired power plants and CCS. To enable future CCS-equipped gas processing capacity, along with large amounts of hydrogen production capacity further research should focus on: (i) assessing the opportunities for biogas co-firing in gas power plants, (ii) evaluating novel biomass to biogas conversion routes (iii) novel biogas upgrading techniques using CO₂ removal while (iv) analysing in parallel realistic commercial potential.

▲ **The case of algal biomass**

The use of micro-algal biomass for cost-effective BECCS will remain highly unlikely in the short to medium term, as their cost competitiveness still requires technological breakthroughs. Future research should focus more on studying algal (macro/micro) biomass feedstock in terms of fuel and CO₂ capture properties.

4.2. Current challenges and research needs

This chapter outlines the current challenges and research needs regarding BECCS as distilled from the viewpoints – expressed in their respective position papers – of the Joint Task Force of the European Technology Platform for Zero Emission Fossil Fuel Power Plants and the European Biofuels Technology Platform (ZEP and EBTP, 2012), the BELLONA⁴ Foundation and SINTEF⁵.

BECCS is the combination of two technology solutions: Biomass and CO₂ Capture and Storage (CCS) (BELLONA, 2015). In view of the Paris agreement and the urgent need for carbon-negative solutions, BECCS is considered as the only large-scale technology that can remove CO₂ from the atmosphere. In fact, BECCS is used in most future emission scenarios that do not exceed 2°C warming, to provide ‘negative emissions’. The extensive use of BECCS in this context is driven by the need to resolve the emissions gap between current emission trajectories and the cumulative carbon budget that equates to 2°C.

BECCS has the capacity to accelerate reductions in atmospheric concentrations of CO₂, to remove or compensate for historical emissions, as well as, to reduce the overall costs of climate change mitigation by offsetting more difficult to abate emissions, as for example those from aviation (IEAGHG, 2014; BELLONA, 2015;). However, deploying BECCS on such ambitious scale relies on a number of hypotheses, such land availability, future yields, storage capacity, capture rate, social acceptance and others, many of which could have significant implications, but are not yet fully understood (AVOID 2, 2015a).

Despite the theoretical benefits, the drop in the EUA price – from \$30 per ton in 2008 to \$8 in 2012 and to about \$5 in 2017 (EEX, 2017) - has severely impacted CCS demonstration and deployment. Less funding is available from the “New Entrance Reserve 300” under the ETS Directive and the long-term business case for CCS and subsequently BECCS has been considerably weakened (ZEP and EBTP, 2012).

Currently CO₂ emissions resulting from biomass conversion are not rewarded in the ETS (they are regarded as neutral), so there is no incentive to abate them, even where it can be done at very low additional cost (BELLONA, 2015). To make BECCS economically viable, it is argued that the ETS must go beyond zero emissions, so that negative

⁴The Bellona Foundation is an independent non-profit organization that aims to meet and fight the climate challenges, through identifying and implementing sustainable environmental solutions.

⁵For details and information on the associations identified and the consultation process undertaken please refer to Annex II.

emissions are rewarded. BELLONA notes that capturing and storing emitted CO₂, regardless of the source, should be rewarded in the same way. However, due to current and expected feedstock prices, EUA prices and the existence of RES targets and Member State incentives for energy, such rewarding is unlikely in itself to lead to any increase in, for example, biomass co-firing in coal-fired power plants or biofuel production volumes, but it could lead to CCS being deployed where biomass replaces fossil fuels, once CCS technologies are commercially proven (ZEP and EBTP, 2012).

According to EBTP, to enable cost reductions and the demonstration of BECCS on electricity and CHP installations for both co-firing and dedicated biomass units, incentives for biomass utilization are likely to remain necessary in addition to very high EUA prices, unless novel feedstock helps reduce the price of biomass (ZEP and EBTP, 2012).

In addition, EBTP believes that improving advanced biofuel technology pathways in order to achieve economic feasibility and enhancing the performance and reliability of conversion processes is of primary importance and warrants intensive RD&D activities. Regarding this, BELLONA and EBTP agree that more detailed research should be focused to ensure that advanced biofuels provide economic benefits for developing countries, while pilot and demonstration projects outside, as well as within the OECD, would be required to develop supply chain concepts, assess feedstock characteristics and analyse production costs in different parts of the world (ZEP and EBTP, 2012; BELLONA, 2015).

Another challenge for reaching a large-scale BECCS deployment is the need for a sufficient, sustainable biomass supply (BELLONA, 2015). Given the magnitude of the emission challenge, this clearly requires new pathways to increase biomass supply, including heavily investing in RD&D, development and up scaling of suitable microalgae production, growing and harvesting macro-algae (seaweed) from the seas, and novel methods for growing suitable biomass on lands not currently suited for crops (BELLONA, 2015). EBTP confirms the need to improve the biomass supply and suggests incentivizing the agriculture and forestry biomass supply chains in order to reduce feedstock uncertainty and the overall risk of advanced biofuel scale-up investments (ZEP and EBTP, 2012).

Apart from financial issues, the Taskforce also recommends that further research be undertaken on the issue of public awareness, since a recent study (Wallquist et al., 2011) indicates that there is a difference in perception and attitude of the general public towards BECCS projects compared to fossil CCS projects – notably a decrease in the so-called NIMBY effect.

Energy-intensive sectors such as the power sector and the industry sector are of major importance since BECCS would be able not only to reduce carbon emissions, but also to give carbon negative products, while biofuels production and bio-refineries present good application opportunities, since for these the cost of CO₂ capture is generally very low (BELLONA, 2015).

The following research priority areas for BECCS were identified summarizing the viewpoints of the Joint Task Force the European Technology Platform for Zero Emission Fossil Fuel Power Plants, the European Biofuels Technology Platform, the BELLONA Foundation and SINTEF:

1. Pilot and demonstration projects outside, as well as within the OECD (which focus on developing supply chain concepts, assessing feedstock characteristics and analyzing production costs).
2. Comprehensive cost assessments and life-cycle analyses (LCAs) of BECCS value chains for the various technology routes.
3. Improving public awareness and strengthening public engagement.
4. Up-scaling biomass conversion processes for improved economies of scale for CCS deployment.
5. Accelerating research into sustainable advanced biofuels (with emphasis on economic benefits for developing countries).
6. Identifying situations where experience from CCS in fossil industry is directly applicable and where the purer CO₂ emissions negate a need for expensive equipment to separate the CO₂ from the flue gas.
7. Assessments on the potentials for biogas co-firing in gas power plants (with a focus on the opportunities for hydrogen production).
8. Determining the effect of the composition of biogenic CO₂ on the CCS value chain in power plants (corrosion, effect on amine/ammonia solvents etc.).
9. Identifying any specific storage properties for biogenic CO₂, i.e. biogenic impurities in the CO₂ stream.
10. Studying algal (macro/micro) biomass feedstock in terms of fuel properties and CO₂ capture.

These research priorities (also summarized in **Table 2**) are further described and discussed below based on findings from recent scientific literature in the field. The aim is to explore whether the research focus areas in knowledge highlighted by technology associations and organizations are also raised by recent assessment and feasibility studies on BECCS options and whether additional demands for further research can be identified. The discussion for each area is followed by a set of more specific analytical needs when and where identified through the academic review.

Table 2: Subjects covered for the case of BECCS.

Research Priority	Why is the research priority required?	Section Number
Evidence of pilot and demonstration projects.	Pilot and demonstration projects to prove advanced technologies and close any knowledge gaps.	4.4.1
Comprehensive cost assessments and life-cycle analyses (LCAs) of BECCS value chains for the various technology routes.	Costs and Life Cycle impacts for the large-scale deployment of BECCS technologies have not yet been comprehensively assessed, either for Europe or globally. Given the substantial differences between the various technology routes, a generalized description would not be appropriate and more detailed work is needed.	4.4.2
Public perception and awareness.	There is a difference in perception and attitude of the general public towards BECCS projects compared to fossil CCS projects.	4.4.3
Up-scaling biomass conversion processes for improved economies of scale for CCS deployment.	To make the most promising biomass conversion technologies combined with CCS commercially available by 2020 and accelerate wide-scale deployment of BECCS.	4.4.4
Accelerating research into sustainable advanced biofuels.	Improve advanced biofuel technology pathways in order to achieve economic feasibility and enhance the performance and reliability of conversion processes.	4.4.5
Improving data accuracy on sustainably available land.	The effects of direct and indirect land use change are considered key determinants for the viability of a BECCS project, considering that large areas of land will be required if BECCS are to make a significant contribution to the future energy mix.	4.4.6
Assessments on the potentials for biogas co-firing in gas power plants - The opportunities for hydrogen production.	A wide range of biomass feedstocks is potentially available to serve as vectors to release energy through conversion to other vectors (e.g. biogas) and thus work is still needed to estimate the opportunities for BECCS technologies where biogas is combined with CCS.	4.4.7
Determining the effect of the composition of biogenic CO ₂ on the CCS value chain in power plants (corrosion, effect on amine/ammonia solvents etc.).	The composition of biomass fuels is variable and their generally high alkaline content can lead to ash deposition and corrosion when co-firing in existing boilers, which will drive up costs.	4.4.8
Identifying any specific storage properties for biogenic CO ₂ , i.e. biogenic impurities in the CO ₂ stream.	Because of (geo-)physical variations, there is a need to explore specific storage properties that will provide storage site operators with greater clarity on increasing the probability of success and/or lowering the costs of selecting suitable storage sites.	4.4.9
Studying algal (macro/micro) biomass feedstock in terms of fuel properties and CO ₂ capture	Due to the high uncertainties and limited available data, marine biomass has not been included in the BECCS potentials. Intense research is needed in many parts of the world to find ways to unleash the promising energy potential of these marine types of biomass.	4.4.10

4.3. Overview of assessment data/studies available in the literature

There is already a large body of studies on BECCS. We start our investigation by presenting an overview of the literature we reviewed. Our approach on the review was hybrid; to extract needs for further research from the academia perspective we included information from journals (articles, proceeding papers and book chapters) and we made sure to include existing knowledge and experience from grey literature (i.e. technical/scientific reports, project deliverables, etc.). The final sampling was random (n = 60+ literature sources).

For the case of peer-reviewed journals, our literature search was structured in two rounds. In the first round, we attempted to identify literature sources using initial keywords. For the purpose of broad thematic inclusion, we used filters related to the assessment of different aspects of BECCS. In the second round, we expanded our initial search using some additional key parameters, to account for more specific themes of needs for further research, as extracted from the position papers and the consultation process (e.g. themes on advanced sustainable biofuels, (micro-) algae, biogas plants, etc.). In both rounds, we limited our search to the period of 2000 till 2016 selecting studies from 2010 onwards. However, few older studies were selected as they were deemed relevant to our work.

For the case of grey literature, we made sure to include in our review state-of-the-art reports relevant to BECCS (e.g. published by IEA, IPCC, etc.) and technical reports/deliverables from previous EC funded projects, as CARISMA strongly intends to build on existing knowledge and experience and to establish synergies with previous projects. Same search and inclusion limitations with above were also applied for this case.

We start our investigation into BECCS by evaluating the availability of data/studies in the literature sources we identified. **Figure 1** below summarizes our literature findings regarding available studies and aspects of interest.

Figure 2: Summary of literature findings regarding available studies and aspects of interest.

As shown in **Figure 2**, almost 85% of the literature sources addressed the environmental aspects of BECCS in their research. This was usually conducted through LCA frameworks and included the assessment of GHG emissions reduction in the value chain of BECCS as well as the BECCS impact in the food-water-energy-climate nexus (impacts in land, global warming, acidification, soil and water eutrophication, human toxicity, eco-toxicity, radioactivity and resource depletion). Furthermore, more than 75% of literature sources assessed the costs (both microeconomic and avoidance (mitigation/welfare) costs) in the whole value chain of BECCS. Different integration scenarios were usually considered analysing mainly issues of affordability, profitability and contribution to sectoral and regional growth.

Regarding the technological aspects of BECCS, almost 75% of the literature sources identified focused on technical features and challenges of the different biomass conversion technology routes in terms of increasing efficiency, predicting uncertainty of future performance and identifying areas for further innovations and technological breakthroughs. In addition, almost 75% of the literature studies addressed the market readiness of BECCS in terms of maturity and demand for the technology, focusing on issues of diffusion and pointing out existing and necessary policy, regulations, financial instruments, incentives and GHG accounting frameworks to enable further deployment and demonstration of BECCS. Finally, our literature screening indicated that almost one third of the sources studied BECCS from a social perspective, assessing mainly issues of social acceptance and improving of public awareness, addressing also issues of public perceptions and implications for both CCS and bioenergy options.

Figure 3 summarizes our work regarding the type of information each study used to address/assess the different aspects of BECCS.

Figure 3: Summary of the studies from our literature review according to the type of information/data available per aspect.

Figure 3 indicates that although economic data is equally quantitative and qualitative, half of the studies address the assessment of BECCS using mainly qualitative information.

Overall, our literature review indicates that there is already a sufficient body of literature studies for all the aspects of BECCS, and that for the aspects under study (economic, social, environmental, market readiness, technological) further research is already routed. However, from a social perspective the research results and information available are considerably less.

4.4. Findings from literature regarding research needs

4.4.1. Evidence of pilot and demonstration projects

Development of CCS technologies provides a new suite of opportunities for BECCS (Rhodes and Keith, 2005; Biorecro, 2011; IEA, 2013b; AVOID 2, 2015a; PATHWAYS, 2015b). Although biomass energy is already widely used in power generation applications using a variety of feedstocks, CCS technology is still in its infancy and as a result BECCS is still a far-future prospect which first requires CCS demonstration at scale (Biorecro, 2011; Gough and Upham, 2011; Laude et al., 2011; Vergragt, Markusson et al., 2011; IEA, 2013b; Rose et al., 2013; AVOID 2, 2015a; PATHWAYS, 2015b). There is an ambiguity in the relationship between BECCS and CCS. BECCS is already surprisingly strong regarding available knowledge and will benefit from the further diffusion of CCS and from the fact that some CCS demonstration projects will perform BECCS (Laude et al., 2011; Vergragt, Markusson et al., 2011). However, BECCS will need to be reinforced by policy measures to overcome the risk that CCS locks out BECCS (Vergragt, Markusson, et al., 2011; Schakel et al., 2014). Over the decade 2020 to 2030, CCS could have been deployed on one out of eight gas-or biomass-fired power plants, primarily in OECD member countries and China (IEA, 2013a). The most applicable industry sector for introduction of BECCS is pulp and paper industry, but some potential exists also in cement industry, iron and steel industry and oil and gas refineries (Saidur et al., 2011; EASAC, 2013; Arasto et al., 2014).

According to literature one of the main problems for BECCS demonstration is scale (Biorecro, 2011; Laude et al., 2011; Rose et al., 2013; Sanchez and Callaway, 2016). CO₂ fluxes will typically be smaller than those applying to commercial fossil-fired power plants, which will increase capture and transportation costs. Another is location, determined by the need to be close to biomass resources (otherwise cost and energy requirements for biomass transportation may be prohibitively high) rather than to CO₂ transport networks and storage facilities (AVOID 2, 2015a; Sanchez and Callaway, 2016). The infrastructure development, consisting of specialized CO₂ pipelines routing to storage sites, will be built around existing large point sources. Unless located close to a storage hub, landing point or existing large point source equipped with CCS, lack of infrastructure is likely to present the main economic barrier to dedicated BECCS (Gough and Upham, 2011; Laude et al., 2011).

The suitability of BECCS is unlikely to be universal-some countries and regions will be much better suited to large scale biomass/BECCS applications than others (Biorecro, 2011; Gough and Upham, 2011; Laude et al., 2011; Vergragt, Markusson et al., 2011; IEA, 2013b; Rose et al., 2013). There are many potential obstacles to the realization of

BECCS large scale implementation (Gough and Upham, 2011; Laude et al., 2011; Vergragt, Markusson et al., 2011). Smaller scale BECCS, through co-location of dedicated or co-combusted biomass on fossil CCS CO₂ transport pipeline routes, is easier to envisage and would be potentially less problematic. Hence, care needs to be taken not to exaggerate the potential of BECCS, given that there are currently few studies of the cost of connecting bio-processing (combustion, gasification or other) infrastructure with CO₂ storage sites and that scenarios of global bioenergy potential remain contentious (Gough and Upham, 2011).

On the other hand, economies of scale may further improve the relative costs of transport and storage from larger fossil or co-fired plant compared with the smaller dedicated biomass plants (Gough and Upham, 2011; Laude et al., 2011; Sanchez and Callaway, 2016). Once a CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure is established, there may then be the opportunity to establish smaller scale bioenergy power plants with capture adjacent to the large CCS installations (Gough and Upham, 2011; Biorecro, 2011; Laude et al., 2011). Low and medium penetration rate (10-25% and 25-50% respectively) is the most likely scenario in the OECD and developing countries, while the high penetration rate scenario is very unlikely to happen (Fiorese et al., 2014).

There are no directed incentive programs or tailored market mechanisms to promote BECCS. Thus, various conceptual challenges have been identified within existing markets, requiring policy formulation, to explicitly incorporate delivery of negative emissions via BECCS (Carbo et al., 2011; Gough and Upham, 2011; Laude et al., 2011; Vergragt, Markusson, et al., 2011; Ricci, 2012; IEA, 2013b; Haro et al., 2015). The focus related to BECCS has so far been on the inclusion of BECCS into existing mechanisms, such as EU-ETS, but this may not be enough for rapid deployment (Vergragt, Markusson et al., 2011). Without a clear mandate for large scale emissions reductions, there is no reason for BECCS to be implemented. BECCS does not fit into existing regulatory frameworks in their current form and accommodating BECCS within amended or new frameworks presents a variety of challenges (Carbo et al., 2011; Gough and Upham, 2011; Laude et al., 2011; Vergragt, Markusson et al., 2011; Ricci, 2012; IEA, 2013b; Haro et al., 2015; Kemper, 2015). Only regions that have favourable, i.e. high, CO₂/natural gas prices and the necessary infrastructure in place will be able to implement the full potential of BECCS (Kemper, 2015).

The IEA Bioenergy roadmap suggests that the first commercial-scale BECCS project should happen between 2020 and 2025 (IEA, 2012). Although very much at the commencement stage, BECCS demonstration projects can provide opportunity to gather knowledge, achieve consensus and build support around the technology's properties (Laude et al., 2011; Vergragt, Markusson et al., 2011; Arasto et al., 2014). The use of

BECCS faces large challenges in financing and currently no such plants have been built and tested at scale (IPCC, 2014; Kemper, 2015). Investment subsidies are needed to alleviate the initial capital costs of this technology and financial incentives are a necessary part of the future success of BECCS, given that a large-scale Brazilian BECCS project has been cancelled due to lack of financial support (Moreira et al., 2016). Currently, the main countries that have focus on BECCS deployment are United States, Western Europe, Eastern Europe, Japan and Canada (Moreira and Pires, 2016). Altogether, there are around 20 interesting global BECCS projects in various stages, ranging from evaluation over operation to cancellation (Biorecro, 2011; Milne and Field, 2012; Kemper, 2015). **Table A-1** in Annex I summarizes these projects and their main characteristics.

There is an urgent need to expand the number of BECCS projects in all phases (Biorecro, 2011). However, very few actors are aware of the possibilities of BECCS. There are no governments, international bodies, multinational companies or other resource-rich institutions that have so far committed rhetorically to BECCS deployment. This implies that the legitimacy of the BECCS Technological Innovation System (BECCS TIS) is at present mainly coming from a select number of climate academics and NGOs. Interestingly, biomass actors have not yet been active in developing and implementing BECCS, even though it could be argued that BECCS could serve to strengthen and reinforce the biomass niche in the same manner as CCS could reinforce the fossil fuel regime (Vergragt, Markusson et al., 2011). The key actors in the BECCS TIS are mainly academics among which are those who work with long-term climate scenario modelling, such as in the IPCC and IIASA. However, there are a small number of NGOs, such as Norwegian Bellona and ZERO and a few companies, such as Norwegian Tel-Tek and Swedish Biorecro that are working in this field (Vergragt, Markusson et al., 2011).

Evidence from the literature shows that the main challenges and barriers for the further deployment of BECCS concern: the limits to the different currently known technological routes, the better use of existing biomass feedstocks in order to assure sustainable supply, improving land-use to assure the availability of alkaline soils for carbon storage by biochar, enabling the scalability of CCS systems (up/down), the development of optimized conversion and storage systems, the development of comprehensive maps showing potential storage capacities, identifying transport and storage infrastructure needing the establishment of financial incentives/motivation to reduce carbon emissions and achieve negative carbon emissions and the need to solve the ocean acidification problem, more pilot and demonstration projects to better understand the feasibility of applying CCS to different bioenergy and biofuel plants (Biorecro, 2011; IEA, 2012; Milne and Field, 2012; Rose et al., 2013; Pickard et al., 2014; Kemper, 2015; Hetland et al., 2016). Key actions that will strengthen the BECCS niche include developing roadmaps,

establishing research groups, centres and networks, hosting seminars and workshops for scientists, the public and potential stakeholders, directing dedicated BECCS R&D and arranging demonstration support programs, as well as dedicated incentive programmes (Vergragt, Markusson et al., 2011). Arguably, National and European Authorities have to consider the possibility to monetize stored carbon credit from biomass and assure a high enough long-term carbon price through clear political signal(s). Public authorities need to be involved into these types of early opportunities projects by providing financing support to small emitters, so enabling significant projects rates of return (Laude et al., 2011). Finally, to the greatest extent possible, all carbon impacts of BECCS should be fully reflected in carbon reporting and accounting systems under the UNFCCC and Kyoto Protocol (IEA, 2013a).

Specific research needs & priority areas

- ▲ Investigating the synergies and benefits of BECCS with current European CCS strategies;
- ▲ Further assessment of the effect of (co-) firing biomass on the performance of CO₂ capture options in pilot/demonstration plants, particularly in terms of potential effects of increasing biomass fractions;
- ▲ Further consideration of the co-utilization of biomass and coal in existing and new Fischer-Tropsch facilities planned or operating worldwide in conjunction with CO₂ capture from bio-ethanol production;
- ▲ Further assessment of biomass uses in industry combined with CCS (e.g. steel, cement production), biomethane production with CCS and CCS in the pulp and paper sector.
- ▲ Further insight into the economic and infrastructure boundary conditions for CO₂ capture from bio-ethanol production using detailed case studies;
- ▲ Build a biomass energy infrastructure that enables BECCS, including adjustment in optimal plant size for biomass combustion and conversion systems to account for the economies of scale needed for BECCS implementation.

4.4.2. Comprehensive cost assessments and life-cycle analyses (LCAs) of BECCS value chains for the various technology routes

4.4.2.1. Cost assessments of BECCS value chains for the various technology routes

Estimates of the costs of BECCS are highly uncertain as they depend on many variables and assumptions coupled with the additional uncertainty of little commercial experience of a full-scale CCS plant (Biorecro, 2011; Gough and Upham, 2011; Laude et al., 2011; IEA, 2013b; Rose et al., 2013; Hetland et al., 2016). Given that there is a lack of consistent and comprehensive assessments of current and expected cost of CCS, literature indicates that unavailability of CCS technologies is the most significant cost barrier for BECCS. According to literature, costs for BECCS are comparable to conventional CCS technologies, with costs potentially being in the range of 60-250 USD/tCO₂ (Kemper, 2015).

From the transport perspective, the greatest obstacles are the technical feasibility and cost-effectiveness based on the distance of transportation (Koornneef et al., 2012; Moreira and Pires, 2016). Transportation costs, also, depend on whether existing pipelines are being re-used or new pipeline infrastructure is required, whether transport is onshore or offshore, whether there is a network for CO₂ transport or point to point transport is required (Gough and Upham, 2010; Biorecro, 2011; Gough and Upham, 2011; Laude et al., 2011; Vergragt, Markusson et al., 2011; Koornneef et al., 2012). It is not easy to predict large-scale transportation alternatives, due to the high investment that would be required for the pilot plants.

Nevertheless, storage remains the key of the success and viability of BECCS (Moreira and Pires, 2016). The storage costs are influenced by the capacity of storage sites and the number of injections (Gough and Upham, 2010; Biorecro, 2011; Gough and Upham, 2011; Laude et al., 2011). To minimize CCS cost, the storage sites should be placed close to large CO₂ emitters from biomass operations, as already occurring in Scandinavia and Brazil (Moreira and Pires, 2016). The costs associated with CO₂ capture and transport are likely to be higher at a BECCS plant than at fossil-only CCS plant since dedicated bioenergy power or heat plants are typically smaller (Gough and Upham, 2011; Vergragt, Markusson et al., 2011; Rose et al., 2013).

Our literature review indicates that there are many potential BECCS technology routes. According to IEAGHG six of the most promising BECCS routes are: Pulverized Coal power plant with biomass co-firing (PC-CCS co-firing), Circulating fluidized bed combustion power plant, with a 100% biomass share (CFB-CCS dedicated), Integrated gasification

combined cycle with co-firing of biomass (IGCC-CCS co-firing), Biomass integrated gasification combined cycle (BIGCC-CCS dedicated), Bio ethanol advanced generation and Biodiesel based on gasification and Fischer Tropsch-synthesis. For the best performing routes, BIGCC-CCS and IGCC-CCS appear to be economically attractive (Koornneef et al., 2012; Kemper, 2015). In comparison, the economic potential of the biomethane production routes is negligible, with some niche potential for anaerobic digestion (Kemper, 2015). By conducting a techno-economic analysis, Klein et al. concluded that BIGCC with CCS could serve as the main bioenergy conversion technology in the long-term (Klein et al., 2011). Considering a biomass gasification combined cycle plant with CO₂ capture, BECCS could be competitive with coal or gas (without capture) at a carbon price of around \$100/tC and cheaper at around \$160/tC. With reference to the EU ETS (EU Emissions Trading Scheme), an ETS certificate price of €48-55/tCO₂ (€176-202/tC) could be necessary for a biomass co-fired plant with capture to become competitive with an equivalent plant without capture and €65-76/tCO₂ (€238-278/tC) for dedicated biomass plant with capture (Gough and Upham, 2010; Gough and Upham, 2011; Laude et al., 2011). For large-scale biomass-based Substitute Natural Gas(BioSNG) production plants, Carbo et al. argue that the CO₂ avoidance cost amount to 62 €/ton CO₂, under the assumption that these negative emissions are recognized in the emission trading (Carbo et al., 2011). Finally, co-firing biomass with coal in larger plants implies a rather limited incremental cost provided CCS is already included (Hetland et al., 2016). **Table A-2** in Annex I summarizes a collection of recent techno-economic assessment studies in literature, presenting key assumptions and findings, concerning various technology routes for the principal value chains of BECCS.

Literature studies acknowledge that BECCS costs can be reduced by using large-scale biomass conversion facilities, which require the development of cost-effective and low-emitting large-scale feedstock and supply logistics (IPCC, 2014). However, there are only a few studies available looking into the cost of connecting bio-processing (combustion, gasification or other) infrastructure with CO₂ storage sites (Gough and Upham, 2010).

Specific research needs& priority areas

- ▲ More studies on the cost of connecting bio-processing (combustion, gasification, etc.) infrastructure with CO₂ storage sites to accelerate BECCS demonstration;
- ▲ Assessing the economic trade-offs of various routes for capturing CO₂ from biomass electricity or poly-generation systems;
- ▲ Further research on the role of BECCS in IAM scenarios of future emissions pathways. More transparency is needed in IAM assumptions about availability of BECCS over time;

- ▲ Better understanding and quantification of the key factors that influence the trade volume and price of biomass enabling a more robust assessment of the economic potential of BECCS technologies;
- ▲ Assessing the BECCS potential per region and in greater detail through regional specific cost supply curves for CO₂ transport and storage, including source ink matching.

4.4.2.2. Life-Cycle Analyses of BECCS value chains for the various technology routes

To date, only few life cycle assessments of BECCS exist indicating that BECCS is an effective option for generating electricity with negative net CO₂ emissions, which rise with an increasing share of biomass in the fuel. A life cycle approach becomes essential once negative emissions are to be claimed (Gough and Upham, 2010; Biorecro, 2011; Laude et al., 2011; Vergragt, Markusson et al., 2011).

Quite a few studies from the literature (Obersteiner et al., 2001; Laude et al., 2011; Vergragt, Markusson et al., 2011; Arasto et al., 2014) agree with the viewpoint expressed by BECCS technology associations, that regulation regarding EU ETS is not ready yet to accept negative emissions. From the climate change point of view, captured and stored biogenic CO₂ is as valuable as stored fossil CO₂ and thus there should not be a difference between acceptable CO₂ emission reductions whether the captured CO₂ is fossil or biogenic. On other hand, the required adjustments in the existing ETS framework to account for negative emissions may not be feasible to be adopted, since it includes uncertainties due to Land Use Change (LUC) effects that could arise from deploying BECCS, particularly on a large scale that is potentially required to meet ambitious emission reductions targets in the middle to later part of this century (Zakkour, Kemper et al., 2014; AVOID 2, 2015a). Additionally, there is still uncertainty whether BECCS results in net negative emissions during the full life cycle (AVOID 2, 2015a). Regardless of the specific technology route, the ability of BECCS to generate negative emissions could fundamentally change the role of biomass in achieving deep emissions reductions by providing a mechanism to offset emissions anywhere in the economy (Rhodes and Keith, 2005; Biorecro, 2011; IEA, 2013b; Rose et al., 2013). However, caution should be applied such that BECCS is not used as an argument to enable higher overall cumulative emissions, even with an equivalent stabilization target (Keith, 2009), as BECCS does not imply that we no longer need to develop renewable energy sources or that we can relax mitigation efforts (Gough and Upham, 2011).

The most important aspect of BECCS from a life cycle perspective could be considered the use of biomass (Biorecro, 2011). Evidence from literature shows that up to 66% of

emissions from a particular bioenergy lifecycle are emitted in the biomass production chain (Scown et al., 2012) and that a change in management strategy can “swing” emissions from positive to negative or vice versa. CCS technologies can technically be applied to any biomass refining or utilizing process emitting CO₂. The CO₂ footprint of a process can also be diminished by removing carbon from the process in other forms than CO₂ (Laude et al., 2011; Arasto et al., 2014). This leads to a completely different kind of lifecycle approach for carbon cycles with aspects also related to cascading use of biomass (Biorecro, 2011; Arasto et al., 2014). Biomass co-firing seems to be the most efficient common technology route offering CO₂ avoidance cost lower than that for CO₂ capture, provided the availability of reasonably priced carbon neutral biomass (Biorecro, 2011; Laude et al., 2011; Vergragt, Markusson et al., 2011; Rose et al., 2013). Biomass combustion does not contribute to direct anthropogenic CO₂ emissions; thus, its capture leads to decreasing the CO₂ emissions during the entire lifetime. In comparison with boilers fired only with coal it is stated that the co-firing of biomass leads to a decrease of emissions of CO, SO_x, NO_x and flue dust by about 12-16%. It is clear that the application of biomass co-firing with the CCS technologies leads to a lower impact on the depletion of non-renewable natural resources, which proves that the biomass co-firing is favourable from the sustainable development point of view (Gładysz and Ziębik, 2016).

LCA results indicate that co-firing 30% biomass combined with 90% CO₂ capture results in negative net CO₂ emission in the order of 67–85 g/kWh (see **Table A-3** in Annex I). To best of our knowledge, although few studies have assessed the impact of co-firing on the power plant’s efficiency and CO₂ balance, none of them have yet conducted a detailed investigation into the effects of co-firing on the performance of the CO₂ capture unit. It is important to assess the impact of co-firing on CO₂ capture performance because the different components in biomass change the flue gas properties, which might affect the behaviour of chemicals and catalysts in the capture process. As such, differences might occur in the performance of the capture unit and in the distribution of inputs and outputs of the power plant (Schakel et al., 2014). According to AR5’s chapter on energy systems, the majority of the persistent life cycle emissions of BECCS stem from the use of fossil fuels (e.g. for planting and harvesting) and Land Use Change (LUC) (Bruckner et al., 2014; AVOID 2, 2015c). The extent of these emissions also depends on the specific type of biomass, location, scale and biomass production and land management systems.

Corsten et al. provide an overview of LCAs in the literature, indicating that integrating CCS to conventional coal/natural gas power plants decreases the Global Warming Potential (GWP) by 65–75% from the life cycle perspective. Nevertheless, adverse impacts on other environmental aspects due to the capture plant are reported, such as increased SO_x and NO_x emissions due to the efficiency penalty at the power plant when applying CO₂ capture (Corsten et al., 2013; Schakel et al., 2014). Most of the LCA

studies in literature only assess Global Warming Potential (GWP) and impacts on other environmental aspects are merely investigated in the study of Carpentieri et al., where 100% biomass fired BIGCC constitutes the considered electricity generation technology and pre-combustion chemical absorption the CO₂ capture strategy (Carpentieri, Corti et al., 2005).

It is also important to keep in mind that LCA studies suffer from limitations, uncertainties, variability and lack of comparability (Kemper, 2015). Literature studies acknowledge limitations in data availability and uncertainties that could affect the environmental performance of BECCS (Kemper, 2015; AVOID 2, 2015c). Such limitations comprise the existing experimental data on the effect of co-firing biomass on the CO₂ capture process and the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) data on the construction and dismantling of an IGCC and on the use or treatment processes of by-products and waste streams (Schakel et al., 2014). Although BECCS systems show a potential to reduce human health impacts, the net effect might vary significantly in different cases (Kemper, 2015).

Specific research needs & priority areas

- ▲ Assessing the impact of co-firing on CO₂ capture performance from a life-cycle perspective;
- ▲ Further quantification of the impact different BECCS technology routes have on human health;
- ▲ Maximizing and optimizing yields through bioengineering for biomass supply with negative emissions (thinking about the whole bioenergy life-cycle from supply and harvesting to processing and conversion);
- ▲ Follow up work on the interactions and uncertainties in the carbon cycle response to negative emissions;
- ▲ Optimization of supply, conversion and storage systems assessing life-cycle risks;
- ▲ Investigating the best use of biomass (e.g. use agricultural residues and push down into more marginal fuels, contaminated material/waste and un-harvested biomass) from a life-cycle perspective;
- ▲ Investigating the possible carbon debt that occurs from the time span between biomass production and biomass usage;
- ▲ Assessing the potential of novel carbon storage and/or utilization technologies (e.g. augmented ocean disposal) from a life-cycle perspective.

4.4.3. Public perception and awareness

There is already a wealth of studies and information on public perception of CCS in general available in the literature (see e.g. Shackley et al., 2004; Ashworth, Pisarski et al., 2009; de Coninck et al., 2009; Wallquist et al., 2010; Terwel et al., 2011; Ashworth et al., 2012; Ashworth et al., 2013; Hall, Ashworth et al., 2013; Einsiedel et al., 2013; Hobman and Ashworth, 2013; Dowd et al., 2014; L' Orange Seigo, Dohle et al., 2014). This section will not reiterate the findings from these assessments, but rather present information on future research areas. Thus, literature shows that studies focusing solely on the public perception of BECCS are limited so far (Kemper, 2015). Although research undertaken to date into public perceptions of CCS with fossil fuel has been insightful in understanding risk perceptions influencing public acceptance of the technology, the extent to which risk perceptions of BECCS may impact the technology's uptake or raise other issues of acceptability is yet to be determined (Biorecro, 2011; EASAC, 2013; Dowd, Rodriguez et al., 2015).

When CCS is presented as a standalone technology to address climate change mitigation acceptance is unlikely (Dowd, Rodriguez et al., 2015). Yet, if approached from a social perspective and presented as one of a portfolio of low carbon energy technologies with capability for addressing climate change, greater appreciation of CCS as a mitigation option is likely (Upham and Roberts, 2011). There is a belief that public perceptions will indeed impact the success of BECCS, with negative perceptions of CCS and/or biomass considered likely to stall the technology's uptake. However, biomass and CCS in combination are expected to gain greater public support than the technologies might achieve individually (Gough and Upham, 2011; Dowd, Rodriguez et al., 2015).

Carbon reduction through conventional CCS (with fossil fuels) is more widely known, while BECCS appears to have a far less public profile regardless of its optimistic GHG emissions reductions potential (Gough and Upham, 2010; Dowd, Rodriguez et al., 2015). Vergragt, Markusson et al. state that the key problem for BECCS is cultural, lacking in a 'community of support', awareness and credibility amongst its own key stakeholders and the wider public (Vergragt, Markusson et al., 2011). Although our review identified several studies focusing on bioenergy and/or biomass little is known in the literature regarding public perceptions of BECCS. To increase public awareness, identifying specific key interventions is essential to advance the technology (Dowd, Rodriguez et al., 2015), including: an EU roadmap towards 2050; establishment of research groups with a BECCS focus; BECCS specific centres and networks; the hosting of seminars and workshops for the benefit of scientists, public and potential stakeholders; the directing of dedicated BECCS research and development; the arrangement of demonstration support along with specific incentive programs (Biorecro, 2011; Dowd, Rodriguez et al., 2015). While there

are expanding communities in both CCS and bioenergy, the linkages between the two remain relatively weak. The challenge will be to bring components (key individuals, organizations, ideas) together to establish a BECCS actor networks and a BECCS technology system (Gough and Upham, 2011).

Findings from the literature also suggest that, to develop a better understanding of the industry's existing public perception on BECCS, social acceptance of bioenergy should also be taken into consideration (Dowd, Rodriguez et al., 2015). For the case of UK, coalition of big firms and policymakers has created substantial problems for bioenergy, as for example the case of NGOs criticizing the sustainability of imported biomass (PATHWAYS, 2015b). Bioenergy is a technologically heterogeneous niche and thus actor-networks are fragmented, with each sub-niche having distinctive principal actors and actor constellations. Controversies about the sustainability of certain forms of biomass could undermine socio-political legitimacy leading to anti "big-biomass" campaigns that might grow in the future (Lal, 2005; Dornburg et al., 2008; Tilman et al., 2009; PATHWAYS, 2015b). Additionally, bioenergy production in the public eye is often associated with the presence of waste plants and as a result social acceptance of bioenergy should be overcome with education and marketing (Fiorese et al., 2014). Finally, in the public eye, the key concerns cited in relation to bioenergy crops relate to competition for use of productive land between bioenergy and food crops, impact on biodiversity and deforestation, negation of greenhouse gas benefits if bioenergy crops are grown on land with existing high carbon stock and potential negative impacts on communities (e.g. land rights, poverty, workers' rights) (Gough and Upham, 2011; AVOID 2, 2015a; AVOID 2, 2015c).

To increase the awareness and profile of BECCS with the general public, the industry is encouraged to actively engage with the media (Biorecro, 2011; Dowd, Rodriguez et al., 2015). However, there is no empirical research so far investigating BECCS in the media, and thus it is uncertain how this technology in particular is perceived compared with fossil fuel based CCS projects. With risks associated with new technologies and the possibility of becoming the focus of public and political debate, it is essential for the BECCS industry to monitor and engage the media in order to provide technical information as well as address any concerns or perceived risks. This can lead to further awareness of and discussions about BECCS wider application, use and impact (Dowd, Rodriguez et al., 2015).

Specific research needs & priority areas

- ▲ Explore how the human factor (e.g. different actors/components from different fields, positions, motives etc.) can influence the further deployment of BECCS;

- ▲ Investigating how BECCS is perceived compared with fossil fuel based CCS projects in the media to increase empirical knowledge.

4.4.4. Up-scaling biomass conversion processes for improved economies of scale for CCS deployment

Several routes to convert biomass to energy have been identified so far (Fiorese et al., 2014). Our findings show that choosing a specific conversion route depends on the nature of the feedstock, the availability of a given technology and the demand for a specific energy product, namely electricity, heat or fuels (McKendry, 2002a; McKendry, 2002b; McKendry, 2002c; Bauen et al., 2009). Some biomass conversion technologies are in principle able to adapt to different feedstocks and to produce different energy products (Saidur et al., 2011; Fiorese et al., 2014). Biomass conversion technologies are diverse and characterized by different stages of development and deployment (Saidur et al., 2011; EASAC, 2013; Fiorese et al., 2014; Moreira et al., 2016; Sanchez and Callaway, 2016).

There are a number of ways to convert biomass in a BECCS system and several studies have looked at which conversions are most efficient, technically feasible and can be integrated to carbon capture and storage (Biorecro, 2011; Milne and Field, 2012; EASAC, 2013; IEA, 2013a). The four major biomass conversion routes are biochemical conversion (fermentation and hydrolysis), thermochemical conversion (e.g. gasification), power production (gasification and combustion) and industrial processes (Brennan and Owende, 2010; Saidur et al., 2011; Arasto et al., 2014; Sanchez and Callaway, 2016). In addition to ethanol fermentation the thermochemical biomass conversion processes are considered the first-phase targets for applying capture of CO₂, both from a logistic and cost point of view (Saidur et al., 2011; Arasto et al., 2014). Experts suggest that RD&D research is needed for CCS and for conversion processes in both the thermochemical and the biochemical paths highlighting in parallel the need for demonstration activities (Fiorese et al., 2014). By their estimations, thermochemical conversions paths are in line with the expected cost reductions for 2020, while cost projections for biochemical conversions seem more pessimistic than the estimates presented by IRENA, mainly due to the differentiation of technologies in the biochemical conversion pathway (IRENA, 2013; Fiorese et al., 2014). Evidence from literature also suggest that thermochemical conversion processes, as combustion and co-combustion of biomass with coal, are well-developed including mature technologies (steam turbines and gas turbines), while other thermochemical paths as pyrolysis are less-developed including emerging technologies (i.e. Biomass Integrated-Gasifier/Integrated Gasification Combined Cycle, BIG/IGCC) (EASAC, 2013; Fiorese et al., 2014). Particularly, integrated biomass gasification combined cycle (BIGCC) is a promising biomass-to-electricity conversion technology,

especially suitable for CCS with high capture rate (Koornneef et al., 2012; Fiorese et al., 2014). Our literature findings conclude that both thermochemical and biochemical conversion paths are in need of substantial advances in terms of increasing conversion efficiency (Brennan and Owende, 2010; Klein et al., 2011; Saidur et al., 2011; Milne and Field, 2012; Fiorese et al., 2014). One other option that deserves special attention is the technology applied to sugar cane-based energy, which converts part of the primary energy to ethanol via fermentation (Moreira et al., 2016).

All three technological routes for CCS could be applied to biomass energy systems (Keith, 2001; Obersteiner et al., 2001; Rhodes and Keith, 2005; Brennan and Owende, 2010; Biorecro, 2011; Gough and Upham, 2011; EASAC, 2013; IEA, 2013a; Pickard et al., 2013; Sanchez and Callaway, 2016). Post-Combustion Capture (PCC) or Oxy-fuel capture could be integrated with modern biomass boiler technologies or retrofitted to existing plants, though the small scale and low efficiency of existing biomass boilers would make this relatively inefficient (Rhodes and Keith, 2005; Saidur et al., 2011). Alternatively, coal-fired power plants could be retrofitted to co-fire biomass and incorporate CCS such that biomass carbon captured would more than offset incomplete capture of coal carbon (Robinson, Rhodes et al., 2003; Rhodes and Keith, 2005; Biorecro, 2011; Saidur et al., 2011; EASAC, 2013; Schakel et al., 2014). With sufficiently stringent emissions controls, such a plant could be retrofitted to burn only biomass. This mainly depends on emissions controls inducing a low purchase price for unmodified coal-fired power plants, financial dominance of large negative emissions over potentially high fuel costs and local access to very large biomass resources (Rhodes and Keith, 2005; Brennan and Owende, 2010; Saidur et al., 2011; EASAC, 2013). Modern biomass gasification technologies could also incorporate Pre-Combustion Separation (PCS), while less operating experience and economic data is available for Oxygen-blown biomass gasification, although it has been demonstrated and offers higher energy efficiencies and carbon capture (Rhodes and Keith, 2005; Brennan and Owende, 2010; Saidur et al., 2011; EASAC, 2013).

Our literature review identifies several changes in favour of biomass conversion in recent years, as the one made by the UK Bioenergy Strategy in 2012. This change was mainly due to the cost-effectiveness of conversion processes in comparison to new build dedicated biomass and to the fact that conversion processes will enable further biomass applications by 2020 in sectors other than electricity generation (i.e. heat, transport, etc.). Coal-to-biomass conversion fits very well with the existing electricity regime, because of the governments' preferences for working with incumbents on established large-scale technologies (such as co-firing and coal plant conversions) rather than new entrants (such as dedicated biomass) and smaller-scale solutions. Furthermore, it is also easy for operators to switch from coal to biomass and it provides a reliable and constant level of electricity generation (compared to wind and solar). In recent years, (some)

coal-fired power plants have been closed or converted to biomass, because they reached the end of their life span or because of environmental legislation such as the European Large Combustion Plants Directive (LCPD) (PATHWAYS, 2015b). However, although conversion efficiencies will most likely increase in the coming decades due to the development of enhanced steam cycles for dedicated biomass power plants, they are expected to be below that of fossil-fired power plants due to a higher energy requirement for on-site pre-treatment and operation, and due to the lower heating values of the feedstock (Koorneef et al., 2012).

The Bioenergy Technology Roadmap of the SET-Plan (EC, 2009b) stresses the importance of making the most promising biomass conversion technologies commercially available (committing to a clear RD&D program beyond 2020) to achieve further diffusion and deployment of BECCS. Significant advances are in need when it comes to large-scale biomass conversion addressing issues of transport and intermediate storage of large amounts of biomass, as well as improving pre-treatment processes to reduce moisture content and increase specific heat content of large-scale biomass supply chains (Brennan and Owende, 2010; Biorecro, 2011; Saidur et al., 2011; Milne and Field, 2012). Another challenge is to build a biomass energy infrastructure that enables BECCS, including adjustment in optimal plant size for biomass combustion and conversion systems to account for the economies of scale needed for BECCS implementation (Biorecro, 2011; EASAC, 2013). Differences between biomass and coal might affect replacing coal by biomass and also co-firing of biomass and coal boilers (Saidur et al., 2011; Koorneef et al., 2012). Strong and balanced policy efforts are needed to create a stable investment environment and allow commercialization of new bioenergy conversion technologies (IEA, 2012). Finally, while the production of electricity from biomass is evolving into a mixed system of small and large-scale conversion plants, it remains unlikely to achieve competitiveness comparable to fossil fuels, even by doubling the RD&D efforts, without further carbon policies (Saidur et al., 2011; Fiorese et al., 2014).

Specific research needs & priority areas

- ▲ Further research on improving boilers design, materials and combustion technology;
- ▲ Further research on Oxygen-blown biomass gasification as little operating experience and economic data is available;
- ▲ More research on biomass integrated gasification combined cycle (BIGCC) as a very promising biomass conversion technology;
- ▲ More research on making the most promising biomass conversion technologies commercially available to achieve further diffusion and deployment of BECCS;

- ▲ Further research on co-firing of biomass in atmospheres with application in CCS processes (oxygen-enriched and oxy-fuel atmospheres);
- ▲ Assessing the potential of technology routes that combine bio-methane production with CCS on the level of a country or local area, where conditions are favourable;
- ▲ Assessing the possibility for reuse of captured CO₂ to enhance business case for smaller systems with CO₂ capture (e.g. CO₂ use in industry and in the horticulture) for the digestion-CCS route;
- ▲ Increasing conversion efficiency in both the thermochemical and the biochemical path;
- ▲ Further research on biological processes, as bio-ethanol fermentation, as they provide additional CCS opportunities.

4.4.5. Accelerating research into sustainable advanced biofuels

One of the key issues for the future deployment of BECCS is the understanding of the feasibility of CCS applications to different biofuel plants (IEA, 2012). Accelerating research into sustainable advanced biofuels becomes imperative when it comes to BECCS. Sustainable biofuels, right now, have a rather low momentum, mainly for their high costs and little cost reduction potential (PATHWAYS, 2015a). Recent innovation trajectories appear to have very low momentum, with coal-to-biomass now dominating in terms of both deployment and support from powerful energy companies and governments. With the current demand for sustainable biofuels, there is a need to develop a range of resources as the combined mix will be a significant step towards the replacement of fossil fuels. Still, policy commitment for a further expansion of this niche is limited, also for wider sustainability concerns and competing uses of biomass for the decarbonization of other sectors (PATHWAYS, 2015b).

Although advanced biofuel development is still in an early stage and many developing countries have not yet looked into new technologies, one important question to answer is whether sufficient feedstock quantities could be provided to meet future biofuel demand, thereby making the investment in the necessary R&D and infrastructure worthwhile (intensive RD&D efforts are required over the next 10-15 years). Findings from literature acknowledge that, while in some emerging economies like Brazil, China and India sufficient financing and R&D capacities are provided, for other developing countries like Cameroon and Tanzania advanced biofuels have only limited potential to promote sustainable development in the near future. As a result, until commercial availability of new technologies is achieved, developing countries should focus on investing in rural infrastructure, agricultural production and improved energy supply. Another point of

consideration, for the case of the developing countries, is to enhance collaboration both with developed countries and other emerging economies to build capacities in the field of advanced biofuels and to ensure technology access, as is already the case, for example, in Brazil, China, India and Thailand (IEA, 2010).

Finally, the IEA notes that it is still too early to fully assess the potential social, economic and environmental impacts of advanced sustainable biofuel production in practice. However, to understand better these issues in developing countries and emerging economies, further research on specific areas of interest should be conducted (IEA, 2010).

Specific research needs & priority areas

- ▲ Continued development of technologies to optimize the micro-algae production, oil extraction and biomass processing-pre-treatment, logistics and conversion technologies for flexibility, reliability and scale. Advanced biofuels could offer a true supplement to fossil if high yielding algae species can be identified, advanced production and harvesting methods are employed and innovative drying and oil extraction processes are utilized;
- ▲ Further research on development of supply chain concepts, assessment of feedstock characteristics and analysis of production costs in different parts of the world;
- ▲ Collection of field data from commercial advanced biofuel production from residues to better understand impacts on agricultural markets and the overall economic situation;
- ▲ Improving data accuracy on sustainably available land to determine the potential for dedicated energy crops. More case studies could enable further analysis of local agricultural markets, material flows, and specific social, economic and environmental benefits and risks;
- ▲ Exploring utilization prospects in other industrial processes, such as in petro-chemistry and cement manufacturing;
- ▲ Investigating how collaboration between developed and developing countries could assist building capacities for advanced biofuels and ensuring technology access.

4.4.6. Improving data accuracy on sustainably available land

Numerous studies indicate that technical barriers related to the development of sustainable farming practices and socio-political barriers such as competing uses of agricultural land for the production of food, biofuels and bio-based materials and the development of agricultural regime are of crucial importance to the future development

of bioenergy regimes as BECCS (Kheshgi, Prince et al., 2000; IEA, 2010; Biorecro, 2011; Klein et al., 2011; IEA, 2012; Fiorese et al., 2014; Fuss et al., 2014; AVOID 2, 2015a; AVOID 2, 2015c; Fuss, 2016). Key concerns relate to: (i) the competition for use of productive land between bioenergy and food crops, (ii) the impact on biodiversity and deforestation and (iii) the negation of greenhouse gas benefits if bioenergy crops are grown on land with existing high carbon stock, as net avoided GHG emissions are strongly dependent on the manner in which feedstock is procured (Gough and Upham, 2010; Gough and Upham, 2011; IEA, 2012; Rose et al., 2013; AVOID 2, 2015a).

Another important issue associated with sustainable bioenergy production for BECCS is Land Use Change (LUC) (IPCC, 2014; Kemper, 2015; AVOID 2, 2015c; Popp et al., 2017). Direct LUC occurs when additional biomass feedstock demand leads to the cultivation of new areas for biomass production and indirect LUC, when existing production areas cover the additional feedstock demand, displacing the previous production function of the land triggering expansion of land to new areas (Kemper, 2015; AVOID 2, 2015a). However, very few reports have investigated the land requirements of BECCS (Tokimatsu, Yasuoka et al., 2017). BECCS is not without the potential for pitfalls, as there is no guarantee that the sourcing of biomass will always be from sustainable sources resulting in possible net positive CO₂ emissions outcomes instead of emissions reductions (Gough and Upham, 2010; Biorecro, 2011; IEA, 2012; Koornneef et al., 2012; IEA, 2013b; AVOID 2, 2015a; Dowd, Rodriguez et al., 2015; Moreira and Pires, 2016). Experts have already expressed concerns regarding the sustainability of land due to biomass supply and consequences of increasing use of biomass on global land use, biodiversity and water use (Gough and Upham, 2010; Biorecro, 2011; Koornneef et al., 2012; Milne and Field, 2012; Fiorese et al., 2014). Sustainability criteria should thus be applied when assessing the potential for BECCS technologies (Gough and Upham, 2010; IEAGHG, 2011; Koornneef et al., 2012; Fiorese et al., 2014; Kemper, 2015).

In addition, BECCS could potentially result in carbon stock loss and decrease or neutralize net positive GHG mitigation outcomes due to direct and indirect land-use changes (Gough and Upham, 2010; IEA, 2010; Rose et al., 2013; AVOID 2, 2015c; Dowd, Rodriguez et al., 2015). Recent research shows that land use and land cover changes driven by biomass production for energy purposes may negatively impact the life-cycle GHG emissions balance (Rose et al., 2013; Kemper, 2015). Policies (such as certification schemes) need to be implemented to promote biomass sustainable use and to avoid biomass infringing on food security and other environmental goals given that large areas of land will be required if BECCS is to make a significant contribution to the global carbon budget (Azar et al., 2010; Gough and Upham, 2010; IEA, 2010; Biorecro, 2011; Rose et al., 2013; Fiorese et al., 2014; Fuss, 2016). Accordingly, impact assessments of land-use changes should redefine the understanding of absolute CO₂

emissions avoided (Gough and Upham, 2010; IEA, 2010; Rose et al., 2013; Dowd, Rodriguez et al., 2015).

Finally, some studies (IEA, 2010; AVOID 2, 2015a; AVOID 2, 2015c) raise the same issue: that to better understand the potential and impact of bioenergy technologies as BECCS in developing countries, improved data accuracy on sustainably available land to determine the potential for dedicated energy crops needs to be further addressed. Particularly in developing regions, global estimations indicate considerable potential for the cultivation of dedicated energy crops. The highest potential is assumed to countries with good climatic conditions or with the ability to intensify their agriculture to free large areas of land. However, some of the assumptions made by previous literature studies are very ambitious, considering the high share of currently cultivated land and the steadily increasing population of some countries (e.g. India and Thailand). Therefore, the availability of land dedicated to energy crops for the production of advanced biofuels may be limited and requires careful assessment (IEA, 2010; AVOID 2, 2015a).

Specific research needs & priority areas

- ▲ Detailed assessment of factors that limit sustainable supply of biomass at a regional level and of actions to increase this supply;
- ▲ Impact assessment of Land-Use Change for food production and for the case of BECCS;
- ▲ Research on available land resources and land requirements of BECCS through detailed case studies analysing social, economic and environmental benefits and risks.

4.4.7. Assessments on the potentials for biogas co-firing in gas power plants - The opportunities for hydrogen production

The production of biomass-based Substitute Natural Gas (BioSNG) with CO₂ Capture and Storage (CCS) offers the opportunity for net CO₂ uptake from the atmosphere (Carbo et al., 2011). Literature shows that the incorporation of BECCS in the production of substitute natural gas (SNG) has been analysed (Haro et al., 2015) and that BECCS is not restricted only to production of electricity or heat, but can also be integrated to biofuel production units such as biogas and hydrogen production plants (Kemper, 2015). BECCS, through BioSNG production, can be a competitive alternative compared to fossil fuel fired power plants and CCS. BECCS technologies that involve fuel synthesis provide relatively straightforward opportunities for retrofit application of CCS, since CO₂ requires separation at all times to comply with product specifications (Carbo et al., 2011). A key

conversion technology for biogas production is the anaerobic digestion of animal wastes and other high-moisture content materials (Brennan and Owende, 2010; Fiorese et al., 2014) which is commercially proven and already used (UEMOA, 2008; Brennan and Owende, 2010; Koornneef et al., 2013). Gas from anaerobic digestion can, after appropriate treatment, be used in secondary conversion devices, such as an internal combustion engine for producing electricity or shaft work. Our review indicates Fast Internally Circulating Fluidised Bed (FICFB) and MILENA as key promising gasification technologies with both being in the demonstration phase. The expectation is that, once these two technologies are developed towards commercial-scale demonstration plant, they will enable full-scale commercial biogas power plants of 500 MW in the coming decades (Koornneef et al., 2013).

The only commercial BioSNG project that our review identified is the Göteborg Biomass Gasification Project, GoBiGas, which was initiated by Göteborg Energy and E.ON, scheduled to be operational by 2016 (80 MWth SNG plant) (Carbo et al., 2011). Additionally, Skåne area in southern Sweden is a region with multiple facilities to upgrade biogas. Since the upgrading process yields a high purity stream of CO₂ as a by-product, it has been proposed that CO₂ from multiple gas upgrading facilities in Skåne could be used in a BECCS project, storing CO₂ in geological formations below ground in the south west parts of the region (Biorecro, 2011). There is already twenty years of experience in upgrading biogas and several upgrading technologies are commercially available. The choice for an upgrading technology (and thus CO₂ removal) depends on different factors, such as the costs, the composition and characteristics (e.g. temperature, pressure) of the gas flow that has to be treated, the required purity of the CO₂ stream and the capacity (i.e. total gas flow) (Koornneef et al., 2013).

It is expected that over the decade 2020 to 2030, almost one-third of global gas processing capacity will be CCS-equipped, along with large amounts of hydrogen production capacity (in refining) (IEA, 2013a). Evidence from literature, also, indicates that converting biomass into gas has the potential to become available for a broader range of energy devices. Biomass-sourced gas can be converted to electricity or mechanical work (via a secondary conversion device such as an internal combustion engine) or used as a synthetic gas for producing higher quality fuels or chemical products such as hydrogen. Biogas can be also used in more efficient power generation systems called combined cycles, which combine gas turbines and steam turbines to produce electricity (UEMOA, 2008). In most commercially run biogas power plants internal combustion engines, such as gas engines have become the standard technology. Other state-of-the-art options include dual fuel engines in which biogas can be co-fired with usually very small proportion of e.g. bio-diesel or bio-ethanol. Efficient hydrogen production from biogas can be achieved via sorption enhanced reforming in particular if

cheap or waste sorbents are available locally (Budzianowski, 2016). However, from a life-cycle perspective, the environmental and energy performance of hydrogen from biofuel reforming is found to be highly dependent on the biogenic feedstock selected (Susmozas et al., 2015).

Over the last few years a number of potential process innovations for biogas technology have been proposed and investigated and therefore review reports that systematically compare, analyse and evaluate the suitability of these emerging methods with emphasis on realistic commercial potential are needed. Innovations are also required in biogas production, conditioning and utilization and R&D efforts should be primarily directed toward areas where disruptive innovations could be generated relatively quickly. Finally, policy options will be essential as they shape directions of innovativeness in biogas technology and need to be in place before biogas technology is selected to play a significant role in the economy of any country (Budzianowski, 2016).

Specific research needs & priority areas

- ▲ Further research on novel biogas feedstocks;
- ▲ Further research on novel biomass to biogas conversion routes;
- ▲ Further research on novel biogas upgrading techniques using CO₂ removal via more energy efficient pathways;
- ▲ Investigating new biogas utilization methods such as bio-methane;
- ▲ Systematic analysis and evaluation of emerging potential process innovations for biogas technology with emphasis on technological excellence and realistic commercial potential;
- ▲ Investigating industrial symbiosis of biogas with conventional emissions/energy intensive industries.

4.4.8. Determining the effect of the composition of biogenic CO₂ on the CCS value chain in power plants (corrosion, effect on amine/ammonia solvents etc.)

Biogenic CO₂ emissions are defined as CO₂ emissions related to the natural carbon cycle, as well as those resulting from the production, the harvest, the combustion, the digestion, the fermentation, the decomposition and the processing of biologically based materials (Biorecro, 2011; Arasto et al., 2014). They are considered as being balanced with the CO₂ uptake from air during the growth of the plants (Biorecro, 2011; Volkart, Bauer et al., 2013). Biogenic CO₂ emissions are accounted as fossil emissions (Biorecro,

2011; Arasto et al., 2014) and are captured just as them (Biorecro, 2011; Volkart, Bauer et al., 2013). No principal technical restrictions with the capture of biogenic CO₂ exist. Despite of fluidized bed technology's high flexibility regarding the fuels, in the case of biomass combustion some challenges exist with emphasis in the case of utilization of CCS. For example, with oxy-fired fluidized bed boilers, even small concentrations of chlorine in the fuel can lead to deposits of harmful alkaline and chlorine compounds on boiler heat transfer surfaces due to components enrichment in the flue gas because of lack of nitrogen in furnace and flue gas re-circulation (Arasto et al., 2014).

Literature indicates that significant issues to overcome characterize the composition of biogenic CO₂ on the CCS value chain in both dedicated and co-fired biomass installations (Milne and Field, 2012). Such issues are pollutant formation, carbon conversion, ash management and balance-of-process issues (e.g., fuel supply and storage, fuel preparation and ash utilization). Corrosion caused by the formation of potassium chloride is also a problem in boilers. Many fast-growing plant species that are good candidates for providing large quantities of sustainable biomass have high levels of potassium, which can lead to the formation of the corrosive potassium chloride. In some cases, however, a blend of biomass with coal can facilitate a reduction in corrosive species and harmful emissions. In such cases, the biomass captures sulfur from coal and forms potassium sulfate, which is less corrosive than potassium chloride. Whilst there are solutions to all of these issues, avoiding the consequences of corrosion requires further attention from the research community (Koornneef et al., 2012; Milne and Field, 2012).

Specific research needs & priority areas

- ▲ Investigating the consequences of corrosion in boilers and fast-growing plant species that provide large quantities of sustainable biomass.

4.4.9. Identifying any specific storage properties for biogenic CO₂, i.e. biogenic impurities in the CO₂ stream

The storage of biogenic CO₂ refers to the capture, compression and transport of a biogenic CO₂-rich stream to an onshore or offshore geological storage facility (sequestration) (Haro et al., 2015). There are no specific technical implications of introducing BECCS to the storage stages of the CCS processes, since the CO₂ stream produced by the capture process is independent of the plant feedstock. For the case of biomass co-firing, the infrastructure development, consisting of specialized CO₂ pipelines routing to storage sites, will be built around existing large point sources (Gough and Upham, 2010). Stored biogenic CO₂ is as valuable as stored fossil CO₂ and as a result

there should not be a difference between acceptable CO₂ emission reductions in the plant whether the stored CO₂ is fossil or biogenic (Arasto et al., 2014).

An IPCC assessment of the literature (IPCC, 2005) foresees storage capacity in geological formations of at least 550 Gt of biogenic CO₂. The report notes uncertainties with respect to storage capacities in saline formations and emphasizes that the storage capacity might be significantly larger, in the order of 1,000s of Gt CO₂. Stored biogenic CO₂ over the course of the century ranges between 350 to 500 Gt CO₂, which lies well within the global capacity of 1,000s of Gt CO₂ (Azar et al., 2010). However, much research remains before biogenic storage can be applied at such scales and it cannot be taken for granted that there are sufficient and safe geological storage options and sufficient political acceptability, for this option to work at a large scale (Azar et al., 2010; Fuss et al., 2014).

Though biogenic storage on its own may greatly reduce atmospheric CO₂, there is concern that as climate change continues, the biosphere may cease to be a net sink and instead become a net source of atmospheric carbon. The capture of CO₂ produced by bioenergy combustion for electricity generation (at the point of conversion) can potentially be addressed through advances in CCS technologies for the capture of CO₂ and storage in underground geological formations (as in CCS demonstration plants with fossil fuel combustion power stations) (Dowd, Rodriguez et al., 2015). In contrast to other types of carbon sinks, such as oceans and forests, geological storage is not affected by temperature increases, tree logging or other changes that might jeopardize these other forms of carbon sequestration. Other sinks involve the risk of negative feedback loops at increased temperatures, potentially leading to significant releases of stored CO₂. The compression and geological storage of biogenic CO₂ requires it to be separated into a pure stream. As biomass has such a high density of CO₂ in its flue gas, it is easier to capture the CO₂ in the flue stream. This fact partly offsets the smaller scale of the biomass facilities (Biorecro, 2011).

Specific research needs & priority areas

- ▲ Determining the impacts of the existing biogenic geological storage options in terms of safety;
- ▲ Exploring the political acceptability for application of sufficient and safe biogenic storage at large scales;
- ▲ Further LCA of long-term storage properties of biogenic CO₂;
- ▲ Investigating the impact of CO₂ leakage from the reservoir on the overall environmental performance of BECCS;

- ▲ Further assessment of the potential of non-traditional biomass processes (e.g. algae, biochar, etc.) as new opportunities for storing biogenic CO₂.

4.4.10. Studying algal (macro/micro) biomass feedstock in terms of fuel properties and CO₂ capture

Our literature review indicates that non-traditional biomass processes, such as algae, can open up new opportunities for capturing biogenic CO₂ (Salih, 2011; Arasto et al., 2014; Alam, Mobin et al., 2015; Milano et al., 2016). Micro-algae can typically be used to capture CO₂ from three different sources: atmospheric CO₂, CO₂ emissions from power plants and industrial processes and CO₂ from soluble carbonate (Brennan and Owende, 2010; Milano et al., 2016). The term BECCS has been used in the context of biological sequestration as a feedstock to produce algal biomass (Gough and Upham, 2011). However, literature indicates that the use of micro-algal biomass for cost-effective BECCS will remain highly unlikely in the short to medium term, as their cost competitiveness still requires technological breakthroughs such as maximization of algal lipid content and growth rate (Kemper, 2015). For micro-algae capturing CO₂ directly from air, the low atmospheric CO₂ concentration is the main limitation. Micro-algal cultures do not require high CO₂ concentrations, as they could be harmful. Land availability is, also, often pointed as a main limitation of micro-algae (Moreira and Pires, 2016).

A main technique, typically employing microalgae, for producing biomass using CO₂ and solar energy is Biofixation (IEA, 2011). The conversion of algal biomass to energy encompasses the different processes ordinarily used for terrestrial biomass and which depend, to a large extent, on the types and sources of biomass, conservation options and enduses. The conversion technologies for utilizing micro-algae biomass can be separated into two basic categories of thermochemical and biochemical conversion. Factors that influence choice of conversion process include: the type and quantity of biomass feedstock, the desired form of the energy, economic consideration, project specifics and the desired end form of the product. Both thermochemical liquefaction and pyrolysis appear to be the most technically feasible methods for conversion of algal biomass to biofuels, after the extraction of oils from algae (Brennan and Owende, 2010; Alam, Mobin, et al., 2015; Milano et al., 2016). Further efforts on micro-algae production should concentrate in reducing costs in small-scale and large-scale systems. This can be achieved for example by using cheap sources of CO₂ for culture enrichment, use of nutrient-rich wastewaters or inexpensive fertilizers, use of cheaper design culture systems with automated process control and with fewer manual labour, use of greenhouses and heated effluents to increase algal yields (Mata, Martins et al., 2010; Alam, Mobin, et al., 2015).

Our findings acknowledge that third generation biofuels specifically derived from micro-algae are considered to be a technically viable alternative energy resource that is devoid of the major drawbacks associated with first and second-generation biofuels (Brennan and Owende, 2010; Salih, 2011; Alam, Mobin, et al., 2015; Milano et al., 2016). Although micro-algae have high potential to produce biofuels and replace fossil in power generation, challenges to commercialize the production at large scale need to be addressed. The challenges are such as: (a) the demand for biofuels is not high in view of low market price of fossil fuel; (b) the cost for the biofuels production from microalgae is high; and (c) the energy ratio of above unity needs to be achieved (Milano et al., 2016). Low cost with high efficient and low contamination harvesting techniques are another obstacle faced by the current stages of microalgae cultivation (Alam, Mobin, et al., 2015; Milano et al., 2016). Finally, literature findings show that biofuels production from micro-algae biomass is considered expensive and the returns of investment are quite slow and low (Alam, Mobin, et al., 2015). However, with the improvement of advanced technologies and possible government incentives it is hoped that micro-algae biofuels will soon become economic feasible and comparable to fossil fuels in term of cost of production (Alam, Mobin, et al., 2015; Milano et al., 2016). At present research is going on to identify the most promising algae species that can be mass produced in order to make biomass production commercially viable. Current harvesting process using centrifugation (mechanical), chemical flocculation, biological or electrical methods creates challenges for recovering the suspended algae. All these processes are still relatively costly (Alam, Mobin, et al., 2015).

Specific research needs & priority areas

- ▲ Optimizing the logistical value chain of biomass while studying the negative effects (e.g. due to water availability and soil quality) of biomass production from algae;
- ▲ Further research on the heat and mass transfer phenomena to ensure the best environment for (micro-) algae growth;
- ▲ Investigating the economic and commercial viability of novel technologies for cultivation of (micro-)algae;
- ▲ Bringing down the current costs for the commercialization of the production of biofuels from (micro-)algae at large scale;
- ▲ Further research on the synthesis of the natural flocculants to reduce the time taken and cost for (micro-)algae harvesting systems;
- ▲ Further research on the economic and environmental sustainability of biomass and algal production methods;

- ⤴ Assessing the potential of phagotrophic⁶ micro-algae as sustainable solution for the near future;
- ⤴ Assessing the potential of other biomass supply options, such as aquatic biomass from algae.

4.5. Concluding remarks–Implications for policy and practice

This report has identified knowledge gaps and needs on BECCS to shape future research or to highlight existing research efforts in key areas. Both the perspectives of technology associations and academic literature were included in our approach to extract this information. The main challenge is how to enable and enhance the relationships between academia and research with those involved in policy and practice. Thus, this section focuses attention on the implications of our work for policy and practice related to BECCS. Challenges for climate change mitigation in Europe from policymakers' perspective include concerns about the embedding of climate change mitigation options in socio-economic planning in central and local governments, the fact that mitigation technologies are not often mature enough for market and thus they do not make it to diffusion phases and lack of knowledge of relevant technologies and policies in different parts of Europe. Taking into consideration these points, a number of implications for research relating to the application and translation of evidence and opportunities for knowledge exchange with those involved in the policy and practice of BECCS are:

1. BECCS is still a promising prospect, which will benefit from the further diffusion of CCS and the fact that some CCS demonstration projects will perform BECCS. There is an ambiguity in the relationship between BECCS and CCS and further research needs to investigate the synergies and the benefits of BECCS with current European CCS strategies. Strengthening the EUA price and establishing additional economic measures at Member State/EU level to enable demonstration projects to take a final investment decision, along with non-ETS measures (e.g. adequate regulatory framework to govern both short- and long-term liabilities and responsibilities) and ETS adjustments, are the most commonly suggested actions towards the further deployment of CCS. Potential antagonistic effects between CCS and BECCS have been highlighted with the need to avoid CCS locking out BECCS. Government intervention with a coordinated effort to improve R&D and market opportunities for both CCS and

⁶Phagotrophic algae, is microalgae species that can eat particles and other small bacteria (e.g. *Ochromonas danica*). There is not much research carried out yet on phagotrophic microalgae but, according to Milano et al., it could result in a sustainable biofuel feedstock in the near future (Milano et al., 2016).

BECCS, collaboration between CCS, biomass and BECCS stakeholders and legitimization of BECCS are necessary actions to avoid this lock out. Additionally, it is likely that countries that grow biomass may well not be the countries where the power generation with CCS occurs and thus, the policy framework should consider existing localized differences.

2. In policy terms, there is a need to interpret the necessary technological and innovation breakthroughs and optimizations in a way that national and European policymakers can understand the relevance to the further deployment of BECCS. For example, there is already a need to assess the limits of the different current technological routes of the several BECCS value chains, to develop optimized conversion and storage systems and comprehensive maps showing potential storage capacities. This holds policy implications in terms of national and international regulatory frameworks and standards, of whether the latter can accommodate the regional differences across the BECCS supply chain.
3. R&D funding is expected to contribute to improving the efficiency of the various BECCS technology routes and to reduce their cost during their first diffusion steps. R&D efforts should be first oriented to determine the costs of the various BECCS routes, including, for example additional costs induced by corrosion and other technology challenges when co-firing with high biomass percentages in existing boilers. In other words, a clear R&D programme should focus on making the most promising biomass conversion technologies commercially available beyond 2020.
4. Directing dedicated BECCS R&D and finance support is also crucial to establish the necessary CCS and biomass infrastructure. Literature agrees that only regions/countries with the necessary infrastructure in place will be able to implement the full potential of BECCS. Future scenarios of BECCS assume global participation in policy frameworks that incentivize and regulate the deployment of CCS infrastructure and BECCS, which calls for increased efforts for policy coordination and monitoring of BECCS potential negative emissions across countries. The use of international agreements and climate policy mechanisms, such as the Kyoto Protocol and the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) also need to be explored. To do so, all carbon impacts of BECCS should be fully reflected in carbon reporting and accounting systems under the UNFCCC and Kyoto Protocol.
5. In addition to that, the identification of appropriate transport and storage infrastructure requires the establishment of direct or indirect incentives to reduce carbon emissions and achieve negative carbon emissions. Determining how safe it is to bet on negative emissions, in terms of adapting existing mechanisms and the impact on the energy markets should be analysed in more depth. Policymakers will need a much more complete picture of negative emissions than what is currently at

hand. It is argued that to meet the 1.5-degree target suggested by the Paris Agreement, efforts should focus on negative emissions and thus BECCS needs to be rewarded by accounting for negative emissions in the EU ETS. This could be achieved through the modification of the ETS Directive (Directive 2003/87/EC) to recognize (negative) emissions from biogenic sources and the establishment of a mechanism in the ETS for the issuing of EUAs on the basis of such emissions. These EUAs would be given to operators that achieve negative emissions, to sell to the market (or surrender for any fossil emissions if relevant), thus providing a direct monetary incentive. Modifications in the ETS framework should not be made without taking into account the uncertainties of Land Use Change (LUC) deriving from BECCS implementation and without previous verification of negative emissions potential, when considering the entire life cycle of BECCS. If negative emissions are to be included in EU ETS adequate accounting and verification frameworks should be put first in place to verify at least that BECCS results in net negative emissions during the full life cycle.

6. Two major implications for policy and practice in the BECCS case are the better use of existing biomass feedstock and the improvement of land use. The first one is required to assure sustainable supply, while the latter would help to overcome technical barriers related to the development of sustainable farming practices and socio-political barriers such as competing uses of agricultural land. The formulation of policy targets needs to be aligned with sustainability criteria promoting sustainable use of biomass (e.g. Report COM(2010)11 of the European Commission) and avoiding biomass infringing on food security and other environmental goals. Furthermore, the issue of biomass sustainability should also be addressed in the context of the Kyoto Protocol. Important co-benefits (e.g. improving soil fertility, addressing ocean acidification) of sustainable biomass use should be integrated during policy impact assessments. These suggestions refer to other policy areas as well such as agricultural policy where coherence is lacking. A coherent EU Agricultural Policy framework should encourage negative emissions technologies (e.g. biochar) that result in such co-benefits, such as the improvement of soil fertility.
7. Certain biofuels production routes could provide “low-hanging fruits” for early, low-cost CCS deployment. However, policy commitment for further expansion of advanced sustainable biofuels niche is still limited and investment in R&D and infrastructure to ensure sufficient feedstock quantities to meet future biofuel demand is needed. Establishing a strong biofuels regime and infrastructure is crucial for the further deployment and commercialization of BECCS. Hence the creation of a global roadmap enabling governments and industry to implement measures to accelerate the required technology development and uptake would be the first step towards this

direction. Additionally, enhancing collaboration between developed and developing countries to build capacities and to ensure technology access, raises an important policy focus that could also promote the future of BECCS where there is high biofuels potential, but limited funding capabilities.

8. Another major implication for policy and practice is to highlight that social acceptance will not stem from just the bi-lateral relationship between a host community and a BECCS project, but a much wider set of social norms, social and political structures and actors that will need to be engaged in order for BECCS to become successful. Negative perceptions of CCS and/or biomass should not stall BECCS uptake and thus policymaking should focus on increasing public awareness by bringing components (key individuals, organizations, ideas) together to establish BECCS actor networks and technology systems both at a national, as well as, at a cross-country level. This points to the key role of both CCS and bioenergy actors (agencies, industry, academia, research community, NGOs, etc.) in shaping future conditions for social acceptance through their responsibilities for legislation, financial incentives and regulatory settings. This in turn requires an EU roadmap for BECCS deployment towards 2050, establishment of research groups, centres and networks with a BECCS focus, hosting of seminars and workshops for the benefit of scientists, public and potential stakeholders and promoting dialogue. Additionally, policy actions to promote the active engagement of BECCS actors with the media, to address concerns and perceived risks, should be envisaged.
9. Finally, demonstration support programs, as well as dedicated incentive programs that will enable BECCS opportunities need not to come solely from the public purse. Although the public sector will have to finance a portion of these investments, it may not have the capacity to meet the full investment needs. Entrepreneurial activity and private initiative are highly recommended. However, private investments take place within a framework of stability and predictability, while policymakers want flexibility in terms of adapting and modifying policy as technology changes or new information comes to light. The perception of changing policy, in terms of altering long-term policy signals (e.g. altering commitment towards biomass use as reflected in country-level biomass diffusion targets in the energy mix), may also damage BECCS investment prospects. To attract private sector investors and energy companies it is important to create an enabling and viable environment that provides security and reasonable risk mitigation. For BECCS in particular this relates mostly to streamlining high revenues (e.g. through effective long-term carbon pricing) and clear political/policy signals. For example, one of the main reasons that investors currently show no interest in supporting new carbon-free technologies, as BECCS, is the lack of proper government support to bridge the first non-profitable years of deployment. It

is obvious that it may take several decades for BECCS to become privately profitable, as was, also, the case for other RES technologies in the past (e.g. offshore wind, solar power, electric vehicles, etc.). Such a specific government effort has already been put in place in Netherlands, where BECCS is already eligible for support under the SDE+ programme. However, the support provided is still considered insufficient, as it doesn't still compensate the costs associated with CO₂ capture and storage. Finally, it is worthy to note that efficient policymaking should engage investors who demand not only a high return on investments, but also an environmental and social added value.

5. The Case of Solar Photovoltaics (Solar PV)

5.1. Summary of key research needs and priority areas for Solar PV

▲ **The cost of PV electricity and financial support schemes**

During the design of financial support schemes supporting PV and other RES-E electricity generated by renewable sources, the cost of the electricity produced is taken into account. The Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE) method is often used method to define the cost of the electricity produced by different technologies, but lacks in precision since it requires a lot of assumptions to be made. Along with the unavoidable intermittent operation of Solar PV, this tool needs amendments, to meet the desirable results. These amendments would be the inclusion of technology risks, the different financing methods among the generation technologies and the clarification of assumptions (e.g. concerning the PV's location, capacity, complexity, efficiency, operation, plant lifetime, etc.) in the LCOE's calculations. Several support schemes are starting to appear which signpost a post-support scheme era with new market and services design to support the valorisation of the fast-growing variety of PV technology applications, with the most predominant being net-metering, sales and lease back models, crowd-funding and green cooperatives. Benchmarking with other economies outside EU borders and the incentives given, such as free land use and subsidized electricity also need to be further studied and their potential transfer in EU Member State (MS) countries needs to be further explored. These studies should include both community scale PV installations and PV factory placement.

▲ **The issue of RES variability**

Although at times RES-E technologies can provide grid support services, such as frequency and voltage support, their high variability (VAR) profile inserts certain limitations concerning the system's stability and requires back-up peak plants to be deployed to maintain the safe operation of the grid. Demand-side integration, energy storage, meteorological forecast tools and smart grid technologies can help address the intermittent nature of RES technologies, as well the need for peaking thermal plants to maintain system stability, thus their use needs to be further studied and explored. The cooperation of Distribution/Transmission System Operators and generators in clearly defining the hierarchy of functions, time of bidding and the forecasting tools required is of great importance to overcome the aforementioned limitation, and also to make sure that an action, of one party (i.e. the DSO) does not have repercussive effects on other parties (i.e. TSO, generators).

▲ **The smart grid concept making use of PV**

Recently, the concept of clustering of small residential PV systems equipped with smart building technologies is gaining market interest since it may contribute to the overall energy needs. Demand response and energy management systems (smart meters, smart thermostats, smart appliances etc.) can help surpass fluctuation problems and energy demand peaks, however up to date very few demonstration projects investigate this portfolio. Emphasis should also be given to public opinion, since the acceptance of digitalization is still controversial, because of a lack of information on the potential benefits it holds.

▲ **The need for new, sustainable business models for electricity markets**

Current business models are utility-based, describing a consumer that requests energy supply from a utility and the consumer pays for this service. With the high penetration of PV in the generation regime new business models are needed so that bidirectional energy flows are taken into account, and the revenue streams for both the utilities and the prosumers are well defined. Several business models for both consumer and TSO/DSO scale have emerged and are being examined in the literature analysing their design in terms of the type of PV and storage system ownership and the way the return is received. Whichever the PV owner, the initial investment has to be supported by investment schemes, research on which is on-going but needs to accelerate to keep up with fast-growing market needs. Furthermore, several business models considering self-consumption and electric vehicles are still in pilot phase and need to be studied thoroughly.

▲ **Assessing the impacts of curtailment**

There is a need for determining the optimal trade-off between the costs of curtailment that burden the producer with the costs of grid reinforcement that burden the grid operator. Focus should be given in balancing the interests of different consumer groups. . Compensation schemes already implemented in different EU countries should draw the attention of future ex-post and ex-ante policy assessment studies. Finally, the theoretical potential of storage technologies with small capacity (batteries, flywheels etc.) to instantly balance supply and demand for short periods of time to reduce curtailment should be further explored.

▲ **The synergies of PV with the cooling/heating sector**

Solar electric energy offers significant advantages in the cooling and heating sector as well. Up to now several attempts have been made in scientific literature to evaluate the environmental and economic benefits from the substitution of conventional technologies with solar assisted ones. The R&D needs specified refer to technical upgrades in solar

cooling and heating technologies so that they become more efficient than conventional ones. Furthermore, a Life Cycle Assessment considering PV and heating/cooling components as one system will give a more complete picture of the environmental and financial benefits.

▲ **Life cycle assessments focusing on the reuse of materials**

To date very few studies include the end-of-life phase in life cycle assessments of PV systems as it was considered to be of secondary importance, since the PV systems lifetime spans for over 20 years. However, with the increasing number of systems being installed, a large waste volume is predicted in the years to come, mandating clear recycling procedures to be defined. Literature suggests that these procedures have to be well defined, on the grounds that recycling costs remain low, contributing to the safe disposal of modules. Moreover, recycling of electrical components must be considered too. The Life-Cycle Analysis must be developed in a way that takes into account regional differences, renewability of sources, rebound effects and future scenario modelling.

▲ **The subjects of material use and material efficiency in PV manufacturing**

Studies concerning PV efficiency have been going on for a long time. The main focus point has been the choice of raw material use and the pursuit of those who perform better. Given that material availability is threatened in the near future and PV manufacturing leaves an environmental footprint, recent studies suggest that R&D should be focused on less material use for module manufacturing, without compromising the system's efficiency, while driving manufacturing costs down. In addition, research on materials needs to aim at increasing the system's lifetime further contributing to a reduction for recycling needs and costs. Well-engineered material handling processes are considered to help achieving this goal, so R&D on manufacturing processes is also suggested.

▲ **The need for quality standardization in PV manufacturing along with O&M procedures**

Very few studies have focused on the quality standardization of PV systems. The stages in the lifecycle of a PV system that need to be standardized range from manufacturing processes to transport and installation. Operation and maintenance (O&M) processes are also considered to be highly influential to the efficient operation of a system. Literature suggests that the standardization of all processes should try to balance the interests of the system owner who wants maximum efficiency from its system with the interests of the manufacturer or the O&M contractor who wants minimum costs. For the benefit of

the system owner, definition of inspection periods and downtime intervals during maintenance is also suggested. Finally, information and communication technologies are considered to help reduce the O&M costs, since they send operational data without the need for visual inspection.

5.2. Introduction

PV is a competitive technology, which has been proven capable to create value and provide services to many stakeholders. However, to continue the exponential growth and really be at the end centre of the energy transition, it has to provide solutions to different challenges that have emerged due to the increased shares. Those are mainly regulatory challenges and consequently financial/business challenges.

Acknowledging that solar power is now well on the way to being a fully competitive alternative to conventional energy, participating to the transition towards a sustainable energy future, Solar Power for Europe, the new EPIA (European Photovoltaic Industry Association), points out to several issues that merit attention. This chapter presents a summary of the challenges and needs identified by reviewing recent position papers⁷ published from the association, as well as, including supplementary viewpoints expressed by the association's representative⁸ during the stakeholder consultation.

One of the first issues highlighted is the current energy market, how it is regulated and subsequently designed. It is stated that rules and regulations governing today's electricity balancing markets are still largely fit for conventional power generation and often exclude or hamper new technologies and solutions. Therefore, revised market design rules, that better reflect the specificities of variable energy sources, are needed,. In terms of market design, the highest priority must be given to adequate and liquid intra-day markets with continuous trading and harmonized gate-closure time across the EU, and the reforms should be organized on the assumption that at least 50% of our power generation on a yearly basis will come from renewables in 15 years from now (EPIA, 2012). The fair valorisation of flexible, cheap and CO₂-free energy products is important, while also the role of storage should be taken into account and enhanced. It is suggested that new market design should ensure free, fair, and open global markets and a level playing field between energy generating technologies for policies to succeed.

⁷Relevant Position papers identified include the "Position Paper on Developing a real industrial policy for PV in Europe, EPIA, 2012" as well as the association official response to the public consultation on the Renewable Energy Directive (REFIT) evaluation, "Preparation of a new Renewable Energy Directive for the period after 2020" published in 2016.

⁸ Mr. Ioannis-Thomas Theologitis, Senior Advisor for SolarPower Europe has been contacted through email and has kindly provided feedback (through a semi-structured questionnaire) on the future challenges for Solar PV, priorities and needs for further research validating and supplementing the ones identified through the review.

Characteristically representative from Solar Power Europe has remarked that: *"The whole electricity market framework needs to be revised to a post support scheme era that will enable valorisation of PV technology (within this, issues such as self-consumption schemes, flexibility, distribution/aggregation, ancillary services, priority dispatch, curtailment should be included)."*

Issues of (lack of) coherence and coordination between the renewable energy and energy efficiency directives are also raised. Relevant to the energy efficiency discussion is also the pertinent issue of Smart Buildings. Regarding the latter, and more specifically regarding Building Integrated PV (BIPV) technologies, it is suggested that *"BIPV should be seen as a stand-alone component due to multiple functionalities it provides to the building envelope (electricity is only one of them)"*. Associated areas to how BIPV technologies are considered also the automation industry and electric vehicles.

Solar Power for Europe also points out that new mechanisms and innovative financing processes should guarantee financing for small and medium-size investors. In addition, guidelines could be provided for potential support mechanisms by benchmarking with other economies. New mechanisms (such as power purchase agreements with local actors) for the valorisation of the renewable electricity would ensure adequate funding, while crowd-funding mechanisms should also be enhanced. Ultimately re-enhancing the confidence of investors by reducing the risk for PV investments, promoting good practices and business models by assessing the current bottlenecks, is considered crucial for further PV deployment. More specifically, administrative costs could be significantly reduced and with them the overall cost of renewables. In addition, redistributing the installed capacities across Europe needs to be considered. For the latter to be achieved, better implemented provisions on streamlined administrative procedures and grid connection processes would be needed to level the non-resource related national characteristics, such as capital costs and administrative costs. Moreover, further PV grid integration can be facilitated and national support schemes can open to renewable energy foreign producers, as a result of enhancing interconnections and removing bottlenecks.

Regarding industrial policy, sustainable growth of both upstream and downstream business needs to be facilitated with focus on quality infrastructure, employment and value creation. It is stated that the investment or support of solar should not been seen as sectoral approach and should be more aligned with the consumer's empowerment of the EC (EPIA, 2012). The adoption of more sustainable jobs across the EU can be promoted by integrating renewable energy into education and providing relevant skills training programmes. In addition, greater focus on education and training of those

influencing the design of new buildings and retrofits would benefit renewables in the building sector.

In the case of electrification of transport, the lack of proper recharging infrastructures presents an obvious barrier, partially addressed by the Regulation of Alternative Fuels Infrastructures, but a holistic view should be developed in order to fully grasp the synergies between the power and the transport sector.

When it comes to product related matters especially in view of the Eco-design and Eco-label Directive, there is need for proper assessments of PV based on real industry facts, avoiding low quality results that will hamper the market and create more costs and compromise the well-earned competitiveness. In addition, a lack of standardization of technical requirements has been identified and it is suggested that IEC standards (61215 and 61646) be complemented with more qualitative-based standards.

Finally, it remains crucial to resolve the issues that concern the retail market and create a suitable PV market and industrial environment for the EU. Adequate support at the EU level should account for the ways in which industrial PV production is supported in countries outside Europe. Otherwise without a competitive production hub, Europe will lose its world-renowned industrial competence in production machinery, material supply and ultimately its research, development and innovation competence in the field.

The following research focus points in the field of Solar PV are a summary of the response from the representative from Solar Power for Europe and the content included in the recently published position papers:

1. New support mechanisms and cost accounting methods;
2. The specificities of variable energy generating technologies;
3. Aggregation of PV systems (especially smaller size systems) and the use of this portfolio for providing services;
4. New market and business models promoting flexibility, synergies with storage technologies/demand response, e-mobility etc.;
5. The impacts of curtailment (PV and other RES);
6. Synergies with the heating/cooling sector (technical and economic);
7. Re-use of PV module material in the framework of a circular economy;
8. Improving energy efficiency (of a PV system) also considering PV and storage;

9. Quality criteria and standardization for product development and testing.

These focus points are further analysed in section 5.4. The purpose of this analysis is to collect evidence from the scientific literature that discuss the same needs and to record any additional needs that need to be studied. Table 3 below serves as guide through the different research priorities discussed in the sections to follow. Every section is concluded with a set of specific research needs for each priority area.

Table 3: Subjects covered for the case of Solar PV.

Research Priority	Why is the research priority required?	Section Number
1. New support mechanisms and cost accounting methods.	Need to support the phase out of the Feed-in-Tariff price regulation by balancing the costs incurred by state support schemes, while ensuring long-term return of investment maintaining PV installation attractive to producers/prosumers.	5.3.1
2. The specificities of variable energy generating technologies.	For the exploitation of the services that VAR RES technologies can offer to the grid and the reduction of the interferences they introduce.	5.3.2
3. Aggregation of PV systems (especially smaller size systems) and the use of this portfolio for providing services.	Need to reduce the transaction costs that burden stand-alone PV market-access. Also for the determination of the balancing effects that digitalization (services and devices) can offer, in view of the intermittent operation of PV technologies.	5.3.3
4. New market and business models promoting flexibility, synergies with storage technologies/demand response, e-mobility etc.	Concerns have been raised about the viability of the current business model. Policymakers and planners could be aided in effectively integrating distributed PV generators and prosumers in the electricity market, if relevant research is promoted.	5.3.4
5. The impacts of curtailment (PV and other RES).	There is a need for the determination of the optimal trade-off between the costs entailing the producer (considering also compensation schemes) and the costs for grid reinforcement.	5.3.5
6. Synergies with the heating/cooling sector (technical and economic).	To exploit the potential and benefits of solar assisted heating/cooling applications stand-alone and combined with PV systems. There is a need to benchmark these systems with electric-mechanical ones and also increase their efficiency.	5.3.6
7. Re-use of PV module material in the framework of a circular economy.	Since the amount of installed PV system is rapidly growing, the safe disposal of modules is crucial in mitigating their environmental footprint.	5.3.7
8. Improving energy efficiency (of a PV system) also considering PV and storage.	Improving the efficiency of PV will lead in shorter return of investment periods, will increase the system's lifetime, and will also reduce the need for module recycling.	5.3.8
9. Quality criteria and standardization for product development and testing.	To ensure high PV quality and operational efficiency.	5.3.9

5.3. Overview of assessment data/studies available in the literature

The literature selection method used for the case of solar PV was similar to the one described in the case of BECCS (section 4.3). The body of the studies selected (60+ literature sources), consists of scientific journals (articles, proceedings from papers and book chapters), as well as, grey literature (project deliverables, technical/scientific reports, etc.), and was searched for by using keywords relevant to the research points described above. The aspects of interest of the ensemble of studies that was gathered are shown in **Figure 4** below.

Figure 4: Summary of literature findings regarding available studies and aspects of interest.

As shown in **Figure 4**, more than 87% of the sources focus on the economic evaluation of PV systems. The economic analyses varied between studies, with the most common being the determination of PV electricity through the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) method, the prediction of the future manufacturing cost reduction of modules considering new material and manufacturing processes and using learning curves, and research on financial support schemes that encourage PV installation. The second more addressed aspect is the technological one, with about 64% of the sources including it in their scopes. Technical feasibility studies mostly focus on the potential reduction of material use or the use of new ones, along with handling process optimization and their associated impact on reducing manufacturing costs and increasing module efficiencies.

The environmental aspect was included in almost 53% of the studies, which mainly focus on life cycle assessment (LCA) to determine the environmental footprint of a PV system. Impacts that relate to human health are usually treated in terms of health risk reduction as a consequence of the CO₂ emissions mitigation. The market readiness and social aspects are the least studied with 47.22% and 37.5% attention received respectively. Market readiness mainly refers to uncertainties raised due to unknown future technological innovations, while the social aspect studies assess social impacts mainly in terms of job creation potential, the educational opportunities and the social acceptance of PV systems and their respective business models.

Figure 5 below summarizes the type of information per aspect available in the ensemble of sources we used. As we can see, only the economic aspect has equal proportions of quantitative, semi-quantitative and qualitative information, while the other aspects are mainly discussed in qualitative terms.

Figure 5: Summary of the studies from the literature review according to the type of information available per aspect.

5.4. Findings from literature

5.4.1. New support mechanisms and cost accounting methods

In scientific literature, several attempts have been made to analyse the economic-technical evaluation mechanisms for financing photovoltaics (PV). The cost of produced

solar energy is a significant factor which needs to be taken into account when proposing new funding mechanisms. The determination of the cost of PV electricity is typically conducted using the Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE) methodology (CHEETAH, 2016a). The LCOE is used as a benchmark tool for the assessment of the cost effectiveness of different power generation technologies. It is obvious though, since it is a benchmarking tool which uses assumptions about the future, there is high sensitivity to assumption definition and accuracy. In fact, many assumptions, such as for the PV location, capacity, complexity, efficiency, operation, plant lifetime and other factors, take place. Furthermore, the method typically does not consider the risks of each technology, and the impact of economic and financial systems on the price of electricity cannot be reflected. The risks and costs of technical assumptions are analysed in a recent study of the Solar Bankability project. The type of financing for different technologies during the LCOE implementation is usually kept the same, despite the fact that they are financed differently (i.e. loans, second mortgages, government incentives, third party financing and equity financing). Debt financing though, is usually preferred, since interest payments are non-taxable in some systems and the cost of the system is spread in a longer time period. Initial investment, interest payments in case of debt financing, operation and maintenance costs, and the government incentives are all included in LCOE calculations. Finally, if the LCOE method is to be used for comparing grid prices, transmission and interconnection fees must also be included in the LCOE analysis. Evidently to acquire realistic results from the LCOE method, one should make as accurate assumptions as possible with respective sensitivity analysis and justifications (Solar Bankability, 2016a; Branker, et al., 2011).

Goodrich et al investigated the incentives that lead PV manufacturers in placing their enterprises in certain countries (Goodrich, et al., 2013). They focus in comparing the Chinese and the US market. One key factor that every manufacturer takes into account is the cost of labour. Chinese factories outmatch the US factories with an advantage of 0.07\$/Watt. With increased scale of process tools (wafers per hour) and the performance of c-Si devices (watts per wafer), the production tools needed per watt of production have been decreased, reducing alongside the impacts of low-cost labour. Emerging PV markets, such as China, require a country-risk premium, given the fact that, generally, the PV industry faces technological and regulatory uncertainties, which act additively to demand-side risks. To cope with this discouraging factor, China offsets this with regional factors, like supply-chain advantages, that enhance a firm's probability of achieving expected cash flows. These advantages consist of a direct 10% discount on raw materials due to enhanced supplier leverage, an additional 5-10% product specific discount, a regional material advantage of about 0.06\$/Watt independent of the production scale, and the availability of production machines sold only from Chinese suppliers, which can

be up to 90% cheaper than those sold worldwide. Subsidy of PV factories in China is based on low-cost land-use rights, free factory space and subsidized electricity providing a significant minimum sustainable price advantage. In addition, it is believed that Chinese firms' high reliance on debt conforms to the expectation of equity premium and has played a very significant role in financing PV manufacturing growth.

Support mechanisms for PV deployment vary across countries around the globe. According to a European Commission's report, a variety of support mechanisms have been implemented in European countries. In Austria, a net-parity tariff scheme has been applied for operators of PV systems larger than 5 kWp (kilo-Watt peak). Belgium has applied a net metering scheme for PV systems up to 5 kWp (in Brussels) and 10 kWp (in Flanders and Wallonia), given that the electricity generated is lower than the consumer's electricity demand. Denmark, also applies a net metering scheme, but only within one hour of the electricity being produced. In addition, the Public Service Obligation⁹ (PSO) is solely paid by systems larger than 50 kW, with the renewable energy surcharge part being waived. The main support scheme in Netherlands has been net metering since 2011. For systems, larger than 15 kW though, a premium tariff under the SED+ scheme, for a maximum of 1000 full load hours per year, is provided. In Switzerland, the support mechanism has a scalable profile. New installed PV systems with capacity between 2 and 10 kW get an investment subsidy instead of a feed-in tariff (FiT), while owners of larger systems with capacity up to 30 kW can choose between an investment subsidy or a FiT. Finally, in France any system gets a reduced VAT rate of 10% for the first 3 kWp produced (EC, 2014a).

The International Energy Agency (IEA, 2014b) has pointed out that with sliding feed-in premiums (FiPs), the returns are more modest and the increases in risk and costs of capital are less pronounced. With FiPs, PV systems compete with each other, with those performing better than average when the electricity prices are high, getting higher returns than those that don't reach the average point. All the aforementioned support mechanisms are usually implemented in combination with fiscal incentives, such as investment tax credits or production tax credits. An overview of the support schemes applied in each member state, as well as detailed information for each support scheme can be found in (EC, 2013), as well as the well-known EU database res-legal.eu.

⁹The PSO levy is a kind of tax charged to electricity consumers in many countries of the European Union. The proceeds of the PSO are used to cover the additional costs incurred by sustainable and renewable energy generation, with goal to encourage renewable energy production by making it more affordable. The PSO is collected by energy suppliers, who in turn pass it to Transmission/Distribution System Operators. The two PSO schemes related to renewable generation are known as Alternative Energy Requirement (AER) and Renewable Energy Feed-in Tariff (REFIT) (CER, 2015).

Alternative financing schemes applied in European countries have also been the focus of the recent PV Financing project. In Austria, the most commonly used scheme is debt financing through loans, since good conditions are offered to large corporate projects by banks. More recently, sale and lease back schemes are applied in the commercial and public sector. In France loans are also the most commonly used scheme for PV, with crowd-funding mechanisms spreading quickly. Two financial methods are popular in Germany, leasing and crowd-funding. Leasing enables the producer to self-consume PV electricity while paying a reduced EEG (German: Erneuerbare-Energien-Gesetz) surcharge without investing. The crowd-funding scheme raises money from a large number of people for use in the residential, commercial, industrial and public sectors. In Italy and Spain financing is mainly based on loans, while crowd-funding is considered to be of the most promising solution to overcome the financial barriers, but it is not yet applied. Especially in Spain, where current PV installation growth is low, those financing schemes are not really popular, and thus, those who choose to install a system do it through self-funding. In the UK, self-funding and loans are the dominant funding schemes, with crowd-funding to be considered promising for the future. Turkey is also included in the study, which except for loans sets up green cooperatives as an innovative scheme for funding the residential, commercial, public and industrial sector (PV Financing, 2016).

Table 4 below summarizes support mechanisms for PV systems in different European countries.

Table 4: Support mechanisms for PV systems in different European countries.

Country	Applied support scheme
Austria	FiT, Subsidy, Loans, Leasing
Belgium	Net-metering, Quota, Subsidy
Bulgaria	FiT, Loan, Subsidy
Croatia	FiT, Loan
Cyprus	Premium, Subsidy
Czech Republic	FiT, Loan, Premium tariff, Subsidy
Denmark	Loan, Net-metering, Premium tariff, Subsidy
Estonia	Premium tariff, Subsidy
Finland	Premium tariff, Subsidy
France	FiT, Loans, Crowdfunding, Tax regulation mechanisms
Germany	FiT, Loan, Premium tariff, Leasing, Crowdfunding
Greece	FiT, Subsidy (soft loan), Tax regulation mechanism
Hungary	FiT, Subsidy
Ireland	FiT, Tax regulation mechanisms
Italy	FiT, Loans, Premium tariff, Net-Metering
Latvia	FiT
Lithuania	FiT, Loan, Subsidy, Tax regulation mechanism
Luxemburg	FiT, Subsidy, Regulation mechanism
Malta	FiT
Netherlands	Loan, Net-metering, Premium tariff, Subsidy, Tax regulation
Poland	Quota system, Tax regulation mechanism
Portugal	FiT
Romania	Quota System, Subsidy
Slovakia	FiT, Subsidy, Tax regulation mechanism

Slovenia	FiT, Loan, Premium tariff, Subsidy
Spain	Self-funding, FiT, Loans, Premium tariff, Tax regulation mechanisms
Sweden	Quota system, Subsidy, Tax regulation mechanisms
Switzerland	FiT, Subsidy
UK	Self-funding, Loans, FiT, Quota system, Tax regulation mechanism

Sources: (EC, 2014a; EC, 2013; IEA, 2014b; PV Financing, 2016).

Concluding evidence gathered from policy design and evaluation studies focus on the support schemes applied on PV deployment. Financing schemes such as loans, sales and lease back models and self-funding are mostly being applied in the European region. Other innovative financial methods include crowd-funding and green cooperatives, which are still scarcely applied or at a development stage.

Finally, the establishment and growth of PV factories in the EU region is crucial in order to expand PV establishment in the generation regime. In addition, supply-chain advantages such as discount on prime materials, manufacturing instead of purchasing production machines, better supplier leverage are significant examples of support mechanisms to consider since they reduce PV cost during the whole production chain.

Specific research needs & priority areas

- ▲ Focus on developing an LCOE method that better clarifies assumptions such as costs, financing, lifetime and loan terms, in order to acquire more realistic results;
- ▲ Analysis of the design of innovative funding mechanisms (e.g. crowd-funding) supporting investments from the private sector and their potential to provide assurance for long-term financial return;
- ▲ Analysing replication requirements & conditions for success of best-case funding schemes implemented in EU countries;
- ▲ To enable the transfer of these mechanisms in other country-contexts empirical investigation of such schemes through detailed case study analysis and ex-post performance evaluations should take place;
- ▲ Benchmarking analysis of support mechanisms with other economies are important for further deploying and diversifying the PV industry and deserve special research attention.

5.4.2. The specificities of variable energy generating technologies

Sustainability assessments for different generation technologies usually focus on economic criteria (i.e. LCOE), technological criteria (i.e. efficiency, Demand Response capability), environmental criteria (i.e. land use costs, environmental costs) and socio-political criteria (i.e. effect on human health, job creation, social acceptance). The need for assessing the high variability (VAR) of RES options, including PV, is highlighted in the REserviceS' Project report (REserviceS, 2014) and has naturally drawn the attention of feasibility studies at the EU level (EDF R&D, 2015) as well as of several scientific assessments (Lingfors, 2015; Huber, et al., 2014; Brouwer, et al., 2016). The intermittent operation of RES technologies inserts the possibility of breaching certain operational limits in the distribution grid. The term intermittency refers to the stochastic nature that electricity generation from RES, including PV, presents. Because of the fact that high electricity production does not always coincide with high demand of energy, the interconnection of a large number of PV in the electricity mix, shifts the need for base load generation plants to peaking plants which will be required in times of low solar irradiation.

Despite these limitations, it is argued that VAR RES technologies can offer Grid Support Services, as long as there are adequate market frameworks and technical requirements in place (REserviceS, 2014). The more widely identified technical requirements include storage of energy, demand side management and meteorological forecast models that can reduce the renewable electricity production uncertainty. Short term-balancing can be achieved using storage technologies (e.g. batteries) while long-term variations can be handled with the deployment of thermal plants. The determination of the optimal mix of wind and PV can help reduce the fluctuation effects of RES technologies, have stabilizing effects on the grid and reduce the need for long-term variations handling. VAR-RES' capability to provide frequency support, in particular Frequency Containment and Frequency Restoration Reserve (FCR and FRR), to the extent that it is beneficial (reliability vs. cost) to the system should be financially compensated. In addition, compulsory, non-remunerated grid support services provision should be mitigated or replaced by remuneration schemes, as it is neither cost-efficient nor necessary to request services from all connected generators in most systems (Graabak & Korpås, 2016).

IEA (IEA, 2015a; IEA, 2014a) complements that simultaneous support of all energy technologies and research on the appropriate technology mix reveals immediately available solutions for CO₂ emissions mitigation, while initiatives for more complex solutions aiming at long-term sustainability are being promoted. IEA also suggests that open and transparent communication among stakeholders can help quickly identify and deploy long-term sustainable solutions in regional level. For wider deployment of VAR

RES technologies, innovation is needed in demand-side integration, energy storage and smart grid infrastructure. Most importantly, given the complexity of VAR RES coordination, Transmission System Operators (TSOs), Distribution System Operators (DSOs) and generators must have a clearly defined hierarchy of functions concerning supervision and control actions, so that an action, for example, of the DSO does not have repercussive effects on the TSO or the generator (REserviceS, 2014). In the context of IEA's work, the "Technical and organizational rules for operators and users of transmission and distribution networks" (TOR) framework applied in Austria has been mentioned. The TOR is part of the so-called "market rules" for the liberalized electricity market. Part of this framework describes actions for the assessment of network interferences and states limits for the permissible impact, provides guidelines for the treatment of generators and covers operational issues, such as installation, protection practices, voltage control, etc.

Specific research needs & priority areas

- ⤴ Overhaul of energy market rules and regulations, to better reflect the specificities of variable energy sources, with emphasis given on free, fair, and open markets and a level playing field between energy generating technologies. More grid studies with high VAR RES scenarios should, thus, take place;
- ⤴ Research on the optimal mix of RES technologies that has minimum intermittency effects to the grid's operation should take place;
- ⤴ Storage of energy and demand side management should be studied as options for reducing the variability effects of RES technologies, as well as the degree of variability they can handle before incorporating thermal plants as stabilizing factors;
- ⤴ R&D on developing advanced meteorological forecasting tools that give accurate results of the expected RES electricity generation should be encouraged.
- ⤴ Research on operational practices and timing of bidding of services along with advanced forecasting tools is still missing;
- ⤴ New markets and services design, such as frequency restoration reserve and frequency containment reserve, should consider both the characteristics of VAR RES in the existing power system and ancillary services provided.

5.4.3. Aggregation of PV systems (especially smaller size systems) and the use of this portfolio for providing services

The aggregation of small PV systems and other RES to the generation regime is considered of high importance, because they can offer several financial, environmental

and social benefits. Financial benefits refer to reduced cost of electricity (especially when solar home systems are present) as part of a net metering scheme or other funding methods. Environmental benefits stand for CO₂ mitigation since they emit very small amount of greenhouse gases during their life-cycle (CARISMA, 2016). Social benefits refer to improved quality of life for citizens in combination with an expense reduction for people living in areas that are not cost-effectively powered by the current electricity network. However, their intermittent function makes their integration to the grid difficult. Smart Grid technologies can help surpass this problem and allow clustering of small RES systems such as PV to contribute to electrical energy needs (PROSUITE, 2010).

In the context of smart grids, demand response (DR) and energy management systems (EMS) are two technology-categories which, according to scientific evidence (Burger & Luke, 2016; Azzopardi & Gabriel-Buenaventura, 2014; Khoury, et al., 2016), may help surpass the fluctuation problem and promote the aggregation of PV systems.

According to the PATHWAYS project team, smart meters are a form of EMS, and describe them as an emerging technology, part of smart grids, which provides intelligent control over the power system. The emerging generation system which makes use of multiple RES, requires increased flexibility which can be delivered through energy storage, demand side management, etc. Pilot projects deployed to understand the true potential of smart meters showed that changes in billing and tariffs as well as behavioural changes are necessary. In the project's report, it is underlined that smart meters enable dynamic tariffs and better information on loads and generation dynamics, which allows them to keep up with the flexibility requirement. With the increasing penetration of PV, the generation system has become even more fluctuating, making it difficult to balance with the existing methods applied so far. In addition, power flows from lower to higher voltages is a challenge that needs to be addressed by the network regime. Smart meters can answer to part of these challenges by providing feed-in control to generators equipped with smart meters and by changing consumption patterns and making demand more flexible (PATHWAYS, 2015b).

However, social acceptance is still considered to be low, as mentioned in the Pathways project. Indicatively, a non-governmental organization (NGO), "Stop Smart Meters! (UK)" has been established in the UK, expressing concerns about health risks, unwarranted privacy violations, and much higher bills. At the same time, positive social visions exist, agreeing with the arguments referenced in the previous paragraph, stating that smart meters with in-home displays have great potential in bringing significant benefits to the electricity system. The UK government aims at substituting all existing meters with smart meters by 2020, while Germany has decided against a nation-wide deployment of smart

meters, with the argument that all that is needed is real-time metering, since the added value of the other properties of smart meters is not yet proven (PATHWAYS, 2015a).

Specific research needs & priority areas

- ▲ Research on cost declines and technological innovations that will enable DR business models to be less dependent on policy and regulatory conditions;
- ▲ Research on the optimal mix of load shifting (DR) and energy storage capacities that can enable and facilitate the diffusion of aggregated small-scale PV systems;
- ▲ The consumer benefits that smart meters can offer are still unclear to the public; hence social acceptance is still conservative. Further monitoring efforts and ex-post evaluations should take place to provide more empirical evidence on the benefits of smart-meter deployment. In addition, demonstration projects and information provision regarding those benefits is required to act persuasively for the public.

5.4.4. New market and business models promoting flexibility, synergies with storage technologies/demand response, e-mobility etc.

To enhance the EU Renewable Energy Industry's (REI) competitive strengths, investments in the development of novel technologies across all energy sectors should continue, with key area of innovation being the storage of energy (EC, 2014b). Along with Research and Development (R&D) efforts, new mechanisms for deploying innovations into the market, such as business incubators and demonstration projects, have been the focus of policy makers and marketers worldwide. Continuing this rationale, IEA points out that with the increasing penetration of new generation technologies, concerns have been raised by utilities about the viability of the current market operation (IEA, 2014a). Discussion focuses on alternative business models and cost recovery structures that will help maintain the benefits provided by utilities until now.

Two business models regarding PV installation and ownership structures are examined in a recent report from the International Energy Agency (IEA, 2014b); the retail model and the energy service model (see **Table 5**). The retail model (focused on pico PV or solar home systems) gives the end-user full ownership of the system, after purchasing it from a private company. Entities responsible for rural electrification can be supported by public funds, multi/bi-lateral aid or the private banking sector. In the energy service model, the supplying company keeps ownership of the system and the end-user pays for the service provided. The capital needed by the private operating company to buy the necessary equipment is raised from public/private sector loans or equity investors. The initial investment of the supplying company can be decreased if concessional soft loans or

grants from donor funds are available. In this case, the end-user's financial burden is also decreased. Another archetype business model, applied in the USA, is proposed by Burger & Luke, regarding areas where PV establishment is not facilitated, called Community Solar business model. In this situation, the customers can purchase either part of a solar system's output, or an equity stake or revenues from the plant. The company that owns the PV system gets return for the initial investment by charging the customers who want access to the PV's output (Burger & Luke, 2016).

From the viewpoint of self-consumption, (Parag & Sovacool, 2016) identify three innovative self-consumption business models that prosuming, based on solar photovoltaic panels, smart meters, vehicle-to-grid electric automobiles, home batteries and other 'smart' devices, could rely on; namely "Peer-to-Peer", "Prosumer-to-grid" and "Organized prosumer groups". In the "Peer-to-Peer" business model, a platform enables producers and consumers to bid and directly sell or buy electricity respectively from each other. A more complex alternative incorporates an energy storage system owner, to whom the producer stores his electricity, and from whom the consumer buys the electricity he needs. This case is beneficial in cases of generation surplus and low demand. The grid operator in this model is paid for the distribution services offered. In the Netherlands, the Vandebroek platform which is based on this concept and enables individuals to buy directly electricity from local farmers and in the UK the Piclo program, an online platform for local commercial consumers, are in the pilot phase. The "Prosumer-to-grid" model considers local producers connected to a mini-grid, which in turn can either be connected to the main grid or operate autonomously in an "island mode". If the mini-grid is connected to the main grid, producers have the incentive to produce as much electricity as possible, since any surplus can be sold back to the main grid. On the other side, if an "island mode" is in effect, excess generation is only beneficial to the limit of storage and load shifting services available. Finally, the "Organized prosumer groups" model is a combination of the previous two business models. The communities or local authorities can sum-up their "presumption" to generate a revenue stream for community benefit.

Focusing on the simpler "stand-alone prosumer-to-grid" model, the LINEAR project assesses different variants of how such a model can be applied in Belgium. In particular, the influence of PV panel penetration and increasing load on different types of feeders have been simulated to evaluate the business case of using flexibility instead of grid upgrade. Furthermore, the effects of different small-scale storage technologies (i.e. electric storage and thermal storage) have been studied and their effect on the grid voltage has been simulated. Finally, the integration of e-mobility to the grid can insert significant problems, especially at the evening peak, so different coordination schemes have been studied (LINEAR, 2014).

Accordingly, the PROSUITE project team (PROSUITE, 2010) has proposed a scheme which reflects the possible synergy of PV and EVs. Car batteries, can be charged from the grid before leaving a residence, and the remaining energy can be sold back to the network when coming home. This way energy losses due to stationary situations will be minimized and self-regulating effects appear to the grid, since electricity demand peaks decrease. However, this scenario needs further development of new monitoring systems. Continuous developments in the electric-mobility sector have made electric vehicles (EVs) very competitive compared to the existing internal combustion (IC) ones. However, the main drawback of mass EV deployment, is that an increased demand for electricity and storage devices, will lead in higher prices in both electricity and batteries. In combination with the fact that car batteries' prices decrease slowly, IC vehicles' cost of ownership is still lower than that of the EV, making the latter unattractive to consumers.

Finally, PATHWAYS project team (PATHWAYS, 2015b) highlights the case of Germany and the adaptations to the network regime undertaken to accommodate new electricity market agents, products and services. Up to now, the grid fees have been additive to the per-KWh electricity price. With the increasing penetration of PV systems used for self-consumption, network bought electricity will decline, driving the network tariff up. With rising network prices, the self-consumption alternative becomes even more attractive to consumers and the self-consumption sub-regime tends to become more wide-spread.

An overview of the described business models is provided in **Table 5** below. The emergence of new agents, products and services has increased the complexity for the management of the electricity market. The different electricity production/consumption structures need to be further examined so that policy-makers are aided in their effort to reshape the fair market-rules regulating the activities of producers, consumers and grid operators in the energy market.

Table 5: New business models for PV deployment

Implementation Scale	Model name	Description
Consumer Scale (electricity parity)	Retail Model	The end-user has full ownership of the PV system, after purchasing it from a private company.
	Energy Service Model	The supplying company keeps ownership of the PV system and the end-user pays for the service provided.
	Community Solar Model	For areas where PV establishment is not facilitated. A company owns the PV system and the customers can purchase either part of its output, or an equity stake or revenues from the plant. This model is currently applied in the USA.

Consumer Scale (Synergies with self-consumption)	1 st Model (No specific name)	Car batteries, can be charged from the grid before leaving a residence, and the remaining energy can be sold back to the network when coming home.
	2 nd Model (No specific name)	Solar electricity is firstly used to power home appliances, secondly to charge the EV battery, and the remaining energy is sold to the grid
	Peer-to-Peer model	A platform enables producers and consumers to bid and directly sell or buy electricity respectively from each other. A "middle-man", owning a storage system can also be present. Pilot programs Vandebroon and Piclo in the Netherlands and the UK respectively.
	Prosumer-to-grid model	Local producers are connected to a mini-grid, which in turn can either be connected to the main grid or operate autonomously in an "island mode".
	Organized prosumer groups	The communities or local authorities can sum-up their "presumption" to generate a revenue stream for community benefit
Distribution/Transmission Scale (considering storage of energy)	1 st Model (No specific name)	The grid system operator owns the storage asset and captures network value only.
	2 nd Model (No specific name)	The grid operator owns the storage asset and captures both network and market values.
	3 rd Model (No specific name)	The storage asset is owned by a third party. The TSO/DSO gets return through fees charged for using the network.
Both Consumer and Distribution/Transmission Scale making use of DR and EMS	Market-based capacity and reserve DR	Commercial, institutional, municipal or industrial customers are included. Usually, EMS are provided to the customers for optimization of energy consumption/ production leveraging customer loads.
	Utility-based capacity and reserve DR	DR products are sold directly to regulated utilities which in turn contract with DR providers to procure firm capacity, operating reserves, and mitigation of network constraints. Revenues are usually earned either from subscription fees collected from the utilities or from brokerage fees. The participating loads of the utilities get a share of the revenues raised by the DR providers

Sources: (Burger & Luke, 2016; INSIGHT ENERGY, 2014; PROSUIE, 2010; Popiolek & Thais, 2016; IEA, 2014b; Parag & Sovacool, 2016)

Specific research needs & priority areas

- ▲ Design of incentives provision at peak times;
- ▲ Further research on Demand Response (DR) and storage technologies, on the basis that they provide capacity-based services;
- ▲ Research on the potential that car batteries have to act as "peak-demand reducers" when connected to the grid and how Information and Communication Technology (ICT) can support the control of power flows;

- ▲ Research & demonstration efforts should also be oriented towards improving electric vehicles to compare with more efficient internal combustion ones in terms of performance and distance autonomy;
- ▲ Design of measures/incentives that promote electric vehicles with simultaneous counter-measures for internal combustion vehicles.

5.4.5. The impacts of curtailment (PV and other RES)

According to the European directive 2009/28/EC, renewable electricity is prioritized in the network regime, as long as the system's safety limits are not breached. When these limits are surpassed, electricity generated from renewable energy sources (RES) cannot be accommodated in the grid because it would lead in its unsafe operation. When such a case is predicted to happen (usually because of increased generation of RES), some systems are obliged to reduce their output below their maximum rated capacity, to maintain safe grid operation. This action is referred to as active power curtailment (INSIGHT ENERGY, 2014). According to IEA (IEA, 2014b), curtailment can help avoid excessive electricity injection from local systems to the grid, which could possibly lead to a network upgrade need. According to IEA's findings, to prevent such a situation, in Germany domestic small-scale PV (<30KW), should be able to be remotely curtailed. For systems with no such ability, 30% of the system's rated alternating current (AC) capacity is permanently curtailed or self-consumed by the generator.

Another study by IEA on "*High Penetration of PV in Local Distribution Grids*", presents a short economic analysis of active power curtailment, performed in Austria. The scenario that was examined assumed 3kWp capacity per house, which depicts an increased PV penetration scheme, in which some of the systems must curtail their power injection to the grid, so that the voltage levels remain below the network's limit. The results showed that, although the maximal curtailment per system can amount to more than 7% of the annual yield, the overall yield loss for the total number of feeders is only 0.8%. With the current FiT applied in Austria, the maximal curtailment of each system is translated to about 23€/year or 4% of the revenues expected without curtailment. These numbers differ in case that the electricity generated is self-consumed. The next step of the analysis was to quantify the profitability of a PV system after curtailing its operation, taking into account the internal rate of return (IRR). The cost of the initial installation was considered to be 2,250 €/kWp with a subsidy of 400 €/kWp. Depending on the proportion of the energy being self-consumed, the IRR was found to fluctuate between 0.5% and 6% per year, with the most affected installation facing a 0.7% IRR decrease. It is easily understandable that the financial impact is smaller under a self-consumption regime, than under a FiT (IEA, 2014a).

In the same study, findings about the Japanese RES framework, show that the Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry along with the Japanese Renewable Energy Law oblige utilities to accept RES connection to the grid, except for certain situations that technical standards are not met. Such a situation is when the electricity demand is expected to be lower than the electricity generated or renewable electricity levels are expected to exceed the transmission-distribution limits. In these cases, PV generators larger than 500kW must curtail their generation. Utilities at the same time have to make operational efforts, such as the control of the conventional generators (except nuclear, hydro, and geothermal), in order to accept renewable energy and the curtailment duration to remain less than 30 days annually. However, if this is not feasible (technical standards of the electricity quality are still exceeded), generation curtailment can continue for longer than 30 days per year.

Likewise, in Greece, although transmission and distribution of RES electricity is guaranteed by national legislation, in cases of systems connected to congested areas, there is a possibility of predetermined maximal curtailment. For these systems, remuneration is predicted under L3851/2010.

The Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research has proposed that storing energy when RES output is high and the demand is low, and generating when RES output is low and the demand is high can lead to curtailment reduction. In addition, they mention that storage can help decongest the transmission network, and storage technologies with small capacity (batteries, flywheels, etc.) can theoretically be used to instantaneously balance supply and demand for a short period of time (PIC, 2012).

The decision to whether or not to curtail RES generation, as well as the determination of the amount of energy to be curtailed includes costs that burden both the producer because of power losses and the grid operator for grid upgrading requirements. Findings from the INSIGHT ENERGY show that power curtailment can contribute to a reduction in grid and storage extension investments. For this to be done, the output of RES plants has to be limited in some hours of the year, reducing their annual output only by a small percentage. In fact, the German Energy Agency, in a recent study has predicted that grid extension costs can be reduced by 30% until 2030 if RES output is limited to 70% of their maximum capability. Furthermore, curtailment can help avoid operational costs for systems reserve procurement and regulating energy, because of a reduction in forecast errors about RES feed-in that influence the necessary reserve provision (INSIGHT ENERGY, 2014). The PV Grid project team complements stating that active power curtailment in favour of grid expansion expenses reduction makes sense only if the compensation to the system owner for the curtailed power is lower than the costs of grid reinforcement. Otherwise grid reinforcement seems a more logical option (PV GRID,

2014). For an extensive review on the different schemes for curtailment please refer to Kane and Ault (Kane & Ault, 2014).

Regarding the cost of network upgrade, IEA (IEA, 2014a) notes that the prospect of active power curtailment on low voltage feeders in Belgium was aimed in enabling DSOs to increase the networks' capacity by 50% at only 10% of the costs of traditional reinforcement. Currently, European legislation does not support renewable energy curtailment on distribution level and in addition, inverters with integrated communication would be preferred, requiring a complete substitution of classic inverters. Although at this stage communication for local control is not necessary, it would be useful for potential future network requirement changes.

Specific research needs & priority areas

- ▲ Further research is needed with proper data acquisition for statistically relevant results on the benefits of curtailment for PV and other RES. Examine this aspect in a no priority dispatch environment;
- ▲ Efforts should be made in developing policy schemes that balances the socio-economic effects of curtailment with the respective costs;
- ▲ Curtailment should be studied in combination with alternative flexibility options (storage, demand side management, etc.), aiming in optimizing the network operation while increasing RES integration to the grid, driving operational costs down and also considering reserve and security requirements;
- ▲ Open and fair discussion should be performed, to determine the national cost-benefit ratios, the boundary conditions and the compensation rules for the PV owner, in case that curtailment is enforced (compared to grid reinforcement) with a goal to reduce grid expansion expenses.

5.4.6. Synergies with the heating/cooling sector (technical and economical)

Solar PV, apart from generating electricity, have the potential to offer significant services to the cooling and heating sector as well (see also **Figure 6**). The most well-known application is solar water heaters, mainly used for providing hot water for domestic use. Nelson et al. mention the potential synergy of PV with the heating sector, saying that they can be used for heating and cooling spaces as well as for some industrial processes. Solar heating of water and other fluids can be used in food processing, in water desalination, for space cooling using an absorption/refrigeration cycle or a desiccant system, etc. Solar cooling technologies have lower efficiency than electric-mechanical technologies, but can be exploited during the summer, when high cooling demand

coincides with high solar heat production (Nelson, et al., 2014). Indicatively, evidence from countries with increased sunlight throughout the year show that solar assisted A/Cs can help save 30-50% of electricity, while demanding minimum direct sunlight and utilizing ambient heat and heat blown by the condenser (Ministry of Environment and Renewable Energy Sri Lanka, 2011).

The Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research categorizes solar cooling into solar electric refrigeration, solar thermal refrigeration, and solar thermal air-conditioning. The first category uses PV panels to power a conventional refrigeration cycle. The second uses solar-thermal gain to produce the refrigeration effect. For this category, the three common options are solar mechanical compression refrigeration, solar absorption refrigeration, and solar adsorption refrigeration. The third category regards space air-conditioning, which can be provided directly through solar-thermal gain by means of desiccant cooling, using solid or liquid sorbents, such as silica gel or liquid chloride. Since the industrial energy demand for heating and cooling applications accounts for more than 28% of the overall energy demand, it is highlighted that education and knowledge dissemination is mandatory so that the available technologies be widely deployed (PIC, 2012).

Testi et al. investigated the life-cycle, cost-optimal sizing of PV and thermal systems, to cover the heating and cooling needs of a farm hostel in Sicily. This hostel was equipped with a radiant floor, an air-to-water heat pump, a PV generator, a solar-thermal generator and a thermal storage unit. The factors also considered in their study were, the external climate, the surroundings of the building and the electrical loads of the building. The main objective was to evaluate the optimal number of solar thermal collectors and PV modules, corresponding to the best trade-off between thermal storage recharge and solar-thermal installation costs, and PV installation costs and the electricity purchasing/selling ratio. For this case study, their results showed that the optimal design would include 4 solar-thermal collectors, 35 PV panels and a 500-liter thermal storage unit. With this set-up, the life-cycle cost reduction was calculated to about 11% and the primary energy savings to about 67%, compared to a design not including PV. Their full analysis can be found in (Testi, et al., 2016).

Another application, used in Kenya, that demonstrates the possible synergy of PV with the heating sector, is Solar Dryers. They collect solar energy by heating up the air volume in solar collector and then conduct this heat from the collector to an attached enclosure, which is used for drying cereals, legumes, tea leaves, fruits and vegetables (National Environment Management Authority-Kenya, 2013).

Concerning the agricultural sector, Hussain et al., performed a techno-economic analysis of a concentrating¹⁰ photovoltaic-thermal system (CPVT) used for greenhouse heating. Their analysis considered five months of winter, from November 2014 to March 2015, and the parameters used were the cost of the CPVT system, its total power output, the recent energy prices the discount payback period (DPP) and the life cycle savings (LCS). The DPP was found to be 21 years, 16 years and 11 years when replacing network electricity, kerosene oil and diesel respectively with a CPVT system. The energy savings over a five-month period was equivalent to 5400 kWh of electricity, 666 lt of kerosene oil or 576 lt of diesel. Considering those numbers, the LCS was estimated to be 7344\$, 8658\$ and 11405\$ for network electricity, kerosene oil and diesel respectively. Finally, the average heating cost saving for December and January (coldest months of the winter) were 56.08% and 48.64% respectively. During these windy and cold winter months that sunshine is limited and CPVT systems cannot completely replace conventional power methods, the savings considering the current prices for electricity, kerosene oil and diesel were calculated to be 44.2\$, 79.5\$ and 107.6\$ respectively (Hussain, et al., 2016).

One of the most promising and popular technologies combining PV electricity with heating and cooling is concentrated solar power (CSP) (UNEP & EPO, 2015; PROSUITE, 2010). CSP technology concentrates solar energy at a single point, which is used to heat up a fluid, produce steam or activate turbines that produce electricity. This technology uses mirrors and lenses in combination with PV, in order to achieve higher efficiencies, relative to fossil fuelled power generation technologies. The techniques applied to concentrate solar irradiation are parabolic trough, parabolic dish or power tower systems. The major disadvantage of this technology is the high cost of ownership relative to conventional PV systems. The return of investment period is based on the solar radiation of each region. Reportedly further research on CSP is needed to reduce optical errors in components, as well as to reduce damages due to natural phenomena (i.e. storms).

Argouaz et al. present the factors that influence the efficiency of solar assisted heating and cooling applications, and underline the need for further research focused on determining the optimal values. These are the collector's tilt angle, the collectors' configuration and surface area, the existence and the capacity of thermal storage tanks and the evaporator mass flow rate (Argouaz, et al., 2017).

¹⁰Concentrating photovoltaics (CPV) use mirrors or lenses to concentrate solar irradiation in small, high-performance cells, increasing the system's efficiency (see also section 5.4.8).

Figure 6: Synergies with the cooling/heating sector.

Specific research needs & priority areas

- ⤴ R&D efforts to support technological advancements (i.e. improvement of chiller COP, thermal storage tanks integration, evaporator flow control depending on the weather condition), and processes (i.e. determination of the optimal collector configuration and surface) which will make solar cooling technologies more efficient than electric-mechanical technologies;
- ⤴ Ongoing research on CSP technology with main goal to increase efficiency and reduce manufacturing costs, to make the technology more competitive in the energy market;
- ⤴ Life-cycle analysis (LCA) of a solar cooling/heating system considering PV and heating/cooling devices as a single unit is still missing.

5.4.7. Re-use of PV module material in the framework of a circular economy

Many studies, such as the ones conducted by (Varun, et al., 2009; Ling-Chin, et al., 2016; Sumper, et al., 2011; Peng, et al., 2013), focus on life-cycle assessment (LCA) concerning Energy Payback Time and CO₂ payback time. In the classic LCA methodology, the life stages included range from raw material acquisition to final system disposal. More specifically, raw material acquisition, material processing, module manufacturing, system

assembly, operation and final disposal, are the most dominant life stages considered. Depending on the goal of each study, these stages can be further analysed, aiming at a more detailed analysis. The results can be used to compare greenhouse gas emissions savings between different generation technologies. As such, Xingxing et al. have focused on assessing the life-cycle CO₂ emission savings when replacing gas and electric water heaters with a prototypesolar photovoltaic/loop-heat-pipe¹¹ heat pump water heating system, in three different areas; Shanghai - representing poor energy quality, London – representing a high charging tariff area and Hong Kong – representing a hot subtropical climate area. In their study, the gas-to-CO₂ emission factor was estimated to be the same for the three regions, while the electricity CO₂ emission factor was considered different because each country has different national power plant efficiencies. Their results showed that the life-cycle CO₂ savings are about 4.08 ton/m² and 17.87 ton/m² in Shanghai, 1.97 ton/m² and 7.92 ton/m² in London and 3.11 ton/m² & 11.27 ton/m² in Hong Kong by replacing gas and electric water heaters, respectively. The maximum environmental benefits recorded in Shanghai are due to the lowest efficiency of its national power plant (Xingxing, et al., 2014). Regarding other (non CO₂) emissions, the US Environmental Protection Agency evaluates methods for non-CO₂ gases emissions mitigation during the life-cycle of a PV system. Reportedly, it is underlined that during the PV cell manufacturing process, fluorinated greenhouse gases, such as nitrogen trifluoride (NF₃) and the perfluorocompounds (PFCs), carbon tetrafluoride (CF₄) and perfluoroethane (C₂F₆), are released in the atmosphere. Proposed methods for mitigating these emissions are Thermal abatement, Catalytic abatement, Plasma abatement and NF₃ remote chamber clean, which are analyzed in their report (US EPA, 2013).

Very few studies have included the end-of-life phase in the LCA of a PV module. Carnevale et al., are of the few to consider this phase in their LCA analysis and accounted for this phase when conducting the Energy Payback Time and CO₂ payback time calculations (Carnevale, et al., 2014). According to them, material disposal has great environmental impacts, as does final disassembly of a PV system and recycling of materials; processes that cause energy consumption and emissions to the atmosphere. However, recycling of materials produces benefits that greatly overcome these impacts. In the context of LCA evaluation, these benefits stand for reduction of raw material manufacturing, since they are substituted by recycled ones. With the existing technologies, more than 90% of a PV system's materials can be recycled, contributing both to economic and environmental advantages, considering that with the rapid

¹¹A Loop-Heat-Pipe (LHP) is a type of heat pipe that combines thermal conductivity and phase transition. It has a large heat transport capacity enabling heat to be transferred along a relatively long distance by circulating the working fluid in a closed loop.

expansion of PV systems, it is foreseen that waste volume will arise above 40,000Mg by 2020. The currently applied recycling processes are the Deutsche Solar process for the crystalline silicon modules and the First Solar process for the thin-film cells. The Deutsche Solar recycling process recovers glass sheets, aluminium frames and wafers from crystalline modules, using thermal treatment for material separation and chemical process for the wafer recovery. The First Solar process has achieved 95% recovery rate for semiconductor material and 90% recovery rate for glass. The results for the First Solar process are also mentioned in a recent study by the IEA, which also points out that PV manufactures have also set up manufacturer-independent recycling system in June 2010, with more than 300 active members to-date (IEA, 2014b).

The Solar Bankability project consortium, looks into the regulatory framework concerning PV recycling, currently applied in the EU region. The Waste Electronics and Electrical Equipment (WEEE) Directive, defines as “producer” every firm or individual established in the EU region which sells, resells or imports PV modules, and holds them liable for the sound disposal and recycling of the modules after the end-of-life phase. In addition, they mention that apart from module recycling techniques, reasearch on recycling processes for cables, inverters etc., which could further reduce the environmental and energy impact of PV, is still missing. Technical risks related to unclear procedures for recycling and to the content of harmful materials over certain limits, which might lead to higher costs for the safe disposal of the PV modules. Finally, electrical storage systems are predicted to increase in the near future, so recycling procedures should also be well defined. Some recycling procedures, still at an early stage, have been prepared for various battery types, based on different chemical procedures. For example, cobalt oxide lithium based batteries recycling produces an alloy, which in turn can produce cobalt, nickel and other metals with further refinement. Cobalt can then be transformed into high grade lithium cobalt oxide which is used in battery manufacturing. Tesla’s evaluation mentions that recycling of these metals can reduce at least 70% of CO₂ emissions, contributing to the mitigation of the environmental footprint of the Lithium-ion based storage technology. Regarding lead based batteries, the lead is melted and re-cast into ingots or other lead products, battery acid is used in the production of gypsum and the plastic is reprocessed into new plastic (Solar Bankability, 2016b).

Up to now the end-of-life phase has not been extensively studied. This is because PV is a relatively new technology which has a life span of more than 20 years, so studying this phase was considered to be of secondary importance since other phases were more crucial for the time being. However, the increasing number of PV installations will lead to a great ammount of systems that will need to be properly disposed in the years to come. So it is crucial to encourage the end-of-life phase incusion in LCA methodologies.

Specific research needs & priority areas

- ▲ Common methodology for assessing the Product Environmental Footprint of a PV system (LCA-Life Cycle Analysis based on re-use) implementing the Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules (PEFCR);
- ▲ LCA should be expanded to integrate global scale challenges, geographical differentiations, rebound effects, renewability of resources and future scenario modelling;
- ▲ Recycling of module components (cables, inverters etc.) apart from modules themselves, should also be considered in LCA since they can significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions;
- ▲ Recycling and disposal of harmful material procedures ought to be well defined so that recycling costs are reduced, contributing to safe disposal of modules. Development of standards for recycling processes should support future PV deployment.

5.4.8. Improving energy efficiency (PV system) also considering PV and storage

The need for improvement of the efficiency of Solar PV has been identified in scientific literature since many years ago. (Alsema & Nieuwlaar, 2000) have pointed out that in order to promote PV as a major technology for CO₂ mitigation, improvements in the energy balance have to be made. Such improvements can be achieved with (i) the reduction of energy consumed during PV manufacturing, (ii) higher module efficiency and (iii) increased system lifetime. Since then, trends in the crystalline silicon solar cell technology have been towards thinner wafers, because they reduce costs. In addition, the needs for R&D cost reduction of new wafer production techniques, as well as new silicon purification processes which increase materials' specifications have been identified. Finally, it is stated that good system design should be deployed without compromising system lifetimes. A good example of cost reduction technique is the development of frameless PV systems, thus avoiding the use of energy-consuming aluminium profiles. Some manufacturers have raised concerns about this technique, but since it's a proven method, an average solution could be the use of recycled aluminium instead of primary.

Concerning the current trends, recent reports found that currently most PV cells are made either from crystalline silicon (c-Si) or thin film. c-Si technologies use mono crystalline cells, multi crystalline cells and ribbon c-Si cells. Multi crystalline cells are increasing their market share, while ribbon c-Si represents only 5% of the market.

Furthermore, the thin-film CdTe technology has increased its market share from 2% in 2005 to 13% in 2010 (Traverso, et al., 2012; PIC, 2012). Varun et al. measured the efficiency rates of large generation systems ($\geq 100\text{MW}$) which use five types of PV module, installed in the Gobi Desert. Multi-crystalline (type a and type b) had 12.8% and 15.8% efficiency respectively, amorphous silicon 6.9%, cadmium tellurium (CdTe) 9% and copper indium selenium (CIS) 11% efficiency (Varun, et al., 2009). A more recent report of the Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research records an average efficiency reaching 16% for silicon modules, 21% for back-junction and interdigitated back-contact (IBC) modules, 19% for heterojunction (HTJ) technologies and 15% for CdTe thin-film modules (PIC, 2012).

In the PROSUITE project, alternative materials have been explored that can increase efficiency and reduce the production cost of PV. Such materials are iron pyrite (FeS_2), zinc phosphide (Zn_3P_2) and amorphous silicon (a-Si), with the most attractive in both cost and availability being FeS_2 . Cost reduction can also be achieved by replacing silicon with copper indium gallium selenide (CIGS) and cadmium telluride (CdTe). However, large quantities of these materials are not guaranteed, making them an unsafe option in large scale demands. Other proposed materials are nano-composites or organics, which despite their lower efficiency require less material and less-costly processing methods. Finally, according to the project's findings, ongoing studies research the possibility of using nanowires as lithium-ion anodes (these can store 10 times more charge than today's graphite anodes) and direct liquid-coating methods for deposition as a substitution of vacuum deposition (PROSUITE, 2010).

Neij (Neij, 2008) also predicted that module cost will fall by 8% due to reduced requirements of silicon, by 17% due efficiency increase, by 4% due to increased yield (from 85% to 95%) and by 25% due to increased production volume (from 10 to 1000 MWp/year). However, these results may be delayed because of limited access to primary materials such as silicon. He also estimated that thin-film modules' efficiency will rise up to 18% by 2030, further contributing to module cost reduction. New technologies combining the silicon high efficiency advantage with the reduced material requirements of thin-film modules will appear too. Another low-cost module called "Solar electricity glass" (Si-pin) may become commercial available in some applications, such as large skyscrapers facades. More innovative – still expensive – alternatives, such as modules based on dye-sensitized photochemical solar cells, conducting polymer cells, quantum solar cells, hot carrier devices, plasmonic solar cells, modular organic solar cells and thermoelectric devices, are also being developed. Efficiencies of 11% for organic cells and 12% for dye-sensitized cells have recently been achieved by Mitsubishi Chemical and Sharp, respectively (PIC, 2012).

More recently, Nelson et al. (Nelson, et al., 2014) argue that, thin film modules require less semiconductor material because of their increased light absorption capability, and because they can be deposited directly onto glass, plastic or metal foil, minimizing the processing stages needed compared to silicon modules. Thin film modules studies showed 10-14% efficiency and were initially introduced as a low-cost alternative to c-Si modules, on the grounds that a percentage of lower efficiency is acceptable if the cost per unit production is reduced too. In practice, it was noticed that CdTe thin films have increased generation capacity under both high irradiation and cloudy conditions, making them more efficient than classic c-Si modules. Another novel technology is multijunction solar cells, which use multiple layers of different semiconductors (two-junction, three-junction etc.), enabling them to exploit various wavelengths of the solar spectrum more efficiently than single semiconductor systems. These systems have achieved up to 44% efficiency in laboratory conditions and up to 32% efficiency in practice. Their major drawback is that these efficiencies can be achieved only when direct sunlight beams are available, making them non-advantageous when operating with diffused sunlight. A possible increase in efficiency under these conditions is achieved by placing mirrors or lenses that focus the sunlight onto small, high-performance solar cells. These systems are called Concentrator PV (CPV). The European Commission characterizes CPV as an emerging, high-efficiency technology and categorizes them in either high concentration systems (> 300 suns) or low to medium concentration systems (2-300 suns) (EC, 2014a). It is also stated, that these systems can operate viably in high direct normal irradiation conditions, which occurs in a limited geographical range – the Earth’s “sun belt”. According to the (PIC, 2012), low-concentration and high-concentration, tree-junction CPV, have achieved efficiencies up to 38.8% and 44.4% respectively in the Spectrolab, a Boeing subsidiary, while four/five-junction cells with 44.7% efficiency have been manufactured by Soitec and Fraunhofer ISE.

Finally, in the context of the CHEETAH project, ultra-thin wafers and epitaxial wafer cells and modules are being assessed. According to the project team, ultra-thin modules can achieve cost reduction up to 23.4% and epi-foil based modules up to 13.5% compared to standard products. Ultra-thin wafers overcome the current bottlenecks known in wire-sawn wafers, such as wafer breakage or cell processing, while allowing 80µm thick c-Si wafers development. Currently, commercial wafers’ thickness ranges between 160µm and 180µm, so before reaching the 80µm target, an intermediate thickness of 120µm (thin-cut wafers) is studied in industrial predevelopment phase. The epi-wafer modules are 40µm thick, high-quality c-Si products, made by chemical vapor deposition which enables avoiding the wire-sawing process and related kerf losses, while accelerating the manufacturing process since polysilicon formation, ingot formation and wafering are omitted. Both innovations can significantly reduce material usage, kerf loss in wire

sawing, energy consumption and consumables required in crystallization and wafer processing. Regarding the cost reduction, for epi-foil wafers can reach 68.9% and for ultra-thin modules 15.8% compared with the benchmark-cut wafers (180 μ m). The thin-cut, intermediate stage, wafers cost reduction is estimated to be around 16.1% compared with benchmark-cut wafers (CHEETAH, 2016b). The project team concludes that future R&D and research efforts should be oriented towards cost reduction of wafer handling and cell processing.

Specific research needs & priority areas

- ▲ Material development should be focused in increasing the system's lifetime while reducing the costs of operation and maintenance (O&M);
- ▲ Cell manufacturing and wafer handling processes when optimized can contribute to a further cost reduction and increased module efficiency due to defects reduction;
- ▲ Research studies and pilots should focus on the use of less material such as thinner wafers to keep efficiencies high and cost reduced.

5.4.9. Quality criteria and standardization for product development and testing

During the production line of a PV system, some components, such as the PV cell, frame, electronics etc., may get damaged due to mishandling or machinery errors. In order to maintain high quality and extended lifecycle of a PV system, inspection during the production steps, identification and repairing of faulty parts are critical tasks that should be made so that the system meets the quality standards. Furthermore, pre-delivery and receiving inspections are key factors influencing the systems well-functioning and lifetime. Many PV module testing institutes require extensive periodic factory inspections, aimed in maintaining a high-quality level of modules, certified products as well as assuring that no production step has any negative impact on the quality of the final product. The factory inspection usually consists of three parts namely (i) verification of all raw materials used for the certified products, (ii) inspection of the complete production process and (iii) review of general quality related issues.

The first part focuses on the verification of the materials used to produce the final tested and certified product, by checking relevant documents such as invoices or delivery notes. In addition, a random recently manufactured system is chosen and checked for consistent material use. During the second step, inspection of the production line is conducted. While in operation, the manufacturer should be able to demonstrate all the quality control tests performed in-line and off-line and their compliance with the

standards should be verified. Finally, in the third part concerning general quality related issues, ISO certificates, quality manuals and other relevant documents are reviewed. In this part, traceability processes, methods for handling faulty products etc. may be asked to be demonstrated too. A list of possible weaknesses that may be detected during the factory inspection has been prepared by the TÜV Rheinland, which categorizes defects into deviations and recommendations. Deviations require actions to be made in a certain period of time so that the manufacturer can receive or renew his factory's certification, while recommendations do not deprive him the right to receive the certification but their implementation would further improve minor problems detected (Solar Bankability, 2016b; Solar Bankability, 2016c).

Module qualification tests included in the IEC61215 and IEC61646 standards have been developed to check if the produced modules have the required quality, before entering the market. These tests include preconditioning, visual inspection, maximum power determination, insulation testing and wet leakage testing. Usually a sample of 8 modules is chosen. For the test sample, if (a) maximum output power descent does not exceed each individual test limit nor 8% after each test sequence, (b) no open circuits occur during test, (c) no visual evidence of major defects exist, (d) insulation test requirements are met after the tests, (e) current wet leakage test requirements are met and (f) specific test requirements are met, then it is IEC approved (Munoz, et al., 2011; Sharma & Chandel, 2013).

Furthermore, the Solar Bankability consortium states that apart from manufacturing testing, transportation and installation standards have to be kept as well. During the transportation of the system, certified logistics processes should be carried out. Furthermore, the date of manufacturing of a PV system may differ from the date of installation. So, delivery inspection should be conducted, not only for the detection of any damaged modules, but also to check for any possible degradation since the manufacturing of the modules. The installation process should be carried out by qualified/certified installers, who will take responsibility for any damaged may happen during the installation phase. They also have to deliver "as-built" files to the owner so that maintenance can be proper and safe. If the "as-built" documents differ from the original planning documentation, or worse, it does not exist at all, proper maintenance cannot be guaranteed (Solar Bankability, 2016b).

Finally, compared to other power generating technologies, PV plants have reduced maintenance and service requirements. However, periodic inspection and maintenance is considered to be a key factor in preserving the systems high efficiency and extending its lifetime. From the owner's side, periodic visual inspections are expected, to make sure that the surface of the PV is clean from snow or dirt, since existence of those can reduce

their efficiency. Further inspection should be assigned to experts, fully responsible for the plant's Operation & Maintenance (O&M). These experts are usually the Engineering Procurement and Construction (EPC) constructors, during the EPC warranty or Defects Liability Period. Responsibilities of the O&M responsible include inspections for degradation or other defects such as hot-spots, lamination etc., as well as electrical and electronic equipment inspection, using the maintenance protocol and guidelines stated in the installation manual or instructions from the manufacturer (Solar Bankability, 2016b). For an overview of the O&M practices applied in PV systems please refer to Solar Access to Public Capital (SAPC) Working Group (SAPC, 2015).

Overall, O&M has been considered an additional financial burden for the manufacturer, so was usually omitted. Incorporation of O&M strategies in the original design of the PV system, especially in evolutionary technologies, will help identify relations between innovations and defects detected, contributing to their early elimination and simultaneously increasing the system's lifetime and driving O&M costs down.

Specific research needs & priority areas

- ⤴ Accelerating tests and necessary quality improvements to ensure high lifetime performances of components. The standardization discussion should include the whole value chain – also O&M;
- ⤴ Inspection periods, downtime and the interval required to complete the necessary O&M operations should be standardized so that no excessive loss of power is happening;
- ⤴ Research in balancing the interests of PV owners, who want maximum energy production from their system, and the interests of O&M contractors who want minimal costs during the maintenance process is still missing;
- ⤴ Development of data collection mechanisms that track the operation of PV systems will lead in less visual inspection requirements and drive O&M costs down.

5.5. Concluding remarks – Implications for policy and practice

The purpose of this report was to combine knowledge concerning the technological and regulatory state of PV systems in the EU and benchmarking with non-EU countries. Among the literature sources reviewed, several needs have been identified, aiming in making PV more competitive in the energy market. In this section, we try to translate these needs into implications for policy and practice that can prove helpful to policymakers. These implications are summarized as follows:

1. The existing financing policies or the new ones developed should focus not only in inspiring a safe business environment, free of retroactive, continuously changing measures and investment risks, but also leveraging funds from the private sector. Most importantly, new market rules and regulations should clearly define the revenue streams for all parties involved since bidirectional energy flows occur. Furthermore, since industry establishment plays a key role in the determination of the PV electricity cost, EU policymakers need to evaluate industry specific supply-push incentives based on operational cost reliefs, ranging from discounted electricity prices to land use grants. Each of these incentives ought to be well defined and accompanied with a no-change guarantee, so that any uncertainty for future development is eliminated. Benchmarking and lessons learned the hard way from other countries outside Europe could help surpass the difficulty of decision making under deep uncertainty.
2. VAR-RES' capability to provide frequency support, in particular Frequency Containment and Frequency Restoration Reserve (FCR and FRR), to the extent that it is beneficial (reliability vs. cost) to the system should be financially compensated, as well as its readiness and utilization costs. The balancing potential of these technologies can be leveraged only if adequate policy frameworks defining operational issues, such as the time of dispatch and bidding, are in place. This implies that new market development along with R&D focusing on new product portfolios needs to be encouraged. Furthermore, sustainable policymaking must not rest on the identified potential of VAR RES technologies, but should also encourage research for new ones.
3. The aforementioned portfolio consists of energy management systems (EMS) and demand response (DR) technologies. Institutional recruitment and the R&D policy efforts for the algorithmic development of digital systems is strongly recommended. Alongside, public acceptance of newly developed digital systems needs to be strengthened. Public information and demonstration projects underlining the benefits that citizens will appreciate by the deployment of those technologies will help increase public awareness and minimize concerns.
4. The introduction of PV systems and other RES to the generation regime has raised concerns about the viability of the current business model. Some novel business models are currently being studied, defining PV and storage ownership statuses and services. The policies ruling these models must clearly define property rights and charges for the services provided from the grid to the prosumer and vice versa. The policy design process should be based on self-consumption, considering storage of energy and electric mobility and the balancing effects they can have on the distribution system.
5. Power curtailment is necessary in order to maintain network stability and reduce the need for infrastructure upgrading. The policies that define the amount of allowed

curtailment should balance the benefits with the respective costs of the system owner. National cost-benefit ratios and boundary conditions determined jointly with all relevant stakeholders should support them. The balancing procedure and the curtailment level should consider integration of energy storage systems, demand response services, car battery coupling and remuneration schemes for the curtailed power.

6. Solar assisted cooling and heating applications have great potential as a climate change mitigation option, as long as they become more efficient than mechanical-driven systems. For this to happen, financing support should be given to R&D activities that focus on increasing the systems' efficiencies and conducting life-cycle assessments considering PV and cooling/heating devices as one system.
7. Recycling of material after the end-of-life is becoming of great importance in evaluating the environmental footprint of a PV system. Directives like the EU WEEE that hold manufacturers responsible for the safe decommissioning and recycling of modules need to be further studied and standardized. The recycling standardization should not only include modules, but also cables, inverters, storage and any other component that is part of the system. The directives have to consider regional differentiations, future scenario development and recycling costs that do not surpass certain limits, leading companies in abandoning the recycling processes.
8. The amount of raw materials used in a PV system has great environmental and financial impacts. R&D focused on reducing the required materials, as well as, the improvement of handling processes should be encouraged.
9. Operation and maintenance (O&M) is considered to be one of the most significant processes that increase a PV system's lifetime. An improved standardization framework must clearly define the responsibilities of the party responsible for O&M, the actions expected by the system owner, the maintenance periods and the downtime intervals, as well as the consequences for any deviation from predefined routines in case of malfunctions. Quality certificates are a considered a good policy measure that assures the compliance of a PV factory with the quality standards. Finally, the use of tools that gather operational data are considered to be beneficial in minimizing the need for visual inspections and should be further exploited.

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Annex I

Project name	Location	Status	CO ₂ capacity (MtCO ₂ /yr)	CO ₂ source	CO ₂ sink
Operational Projects					
Operational projects IBDP and IL-ICCS project	Decatur, IL, USA	Operating since 2011, IBDP completed	IBDP: 0.3 (1.0 in total) IL-ICCS: 1.0 (3.6 in total until 2015)	Archer Daniels Midland ethanol plant	Mount Simon sandstone
Arkalon	Liberal, KS, to Booker, TX, USA	Operating since 2009/2010	0.29 (0.105 initially)	Conestoga's Arkalon ethanol plant	EOR, Booker North Upper Marrow Field
Bonanza	Garden City to Stuart Field, KS	Operating since 2011	0.15	Conestoga's Bonanza BioEnergy ethanol plant	EOR, Stuart Field
RCI/OCAP/ROAD	Rotterdam, NL	Operating since 2011	0.1 (Abengoa) 0.3 (Shell) (2.5 planned for 2015)	Shell's Pernis refinery, Abengoa's ethanol plant, Maasvlakte power plant, various other	Nearby greenhouses, TAQA's P18-4 gas reservoir after 2015
Husky Energy	Lloydminster, SK, CA	Operating since 2012	0.1	Ethanol plant	EOR, Lashburn and Tangleflags oil fields
Norcem	Brevik, NO	Testing since 2014, CO ₂ capture only	Small-scale	Cement plant, >30% biomass-fuelled	N/A
Planned projects / projects under evaluation White Rose CCS Project	Selby, UK	Planned start in 2019	2.0	Drax power station, biomass(co)-firing	Bunter sandstone
C.GEN North Killingholme Power Project	North Killingholme, UK	Evaluating, planned start in 2019	2.5	Biomass co-fired IGCC power plant	Southern North Sea
Södra	Värö, SE	Identifying and evaluating	0.8	Pulp and paper mill	Skagerrak, North Sea
Domsjö Fabriker	Domsjö, SE	Identifying and evaluating	0.26	Black liquor gasification pulp mill	Saline aquifer, North or Baltic Sea
Lantmännen Agroetanol	Norrköping, SE	Identifying and	0.17	Ethanol plant	Saline aquifer, North Sea

		evaluating			
CPER project	Artenay and Tourey, FR	Identifying and evaluating	0.045-0.2	Tereos ethanol plant	Dogger and Keuper saline aquifers, Paris Basin,
Sao Paulo	Sao Paulo state, BR	Identifying and evaluating	0.02	Ethanol plant	Saline aquifer
Biorecro/EERC	ND, USA	Identifying and evaluating	0.001-0.005	Gasification plant	Saline aquifer
Skåne	Skåne, SE	Identifying and evaluating	0.0005-0.005	Biogas plant	Saline aquifer
Completed projects					
Russel research project	Russel, KS, USA	Completed 2005	0.004 (0.007 in total)	Ethanol plant	EOR, Hall- Gurney-Field
Cancelled projects					
Rufiji cluster	TZ	Cancelled	5.0-7.0	Sekab's ethanol plants	Saline aquifer
Greenville	Greenville, OH, USA	Cancelled in 2009f	1.0	Ethanol plant	Saline aquifer, Mount Simon sandstone
Wallula	Wallula, WA, USA	Cancelled	0.75	Boise Inc's pulp mill	Saline aquifer
CO ₂ Sink	Ketzin, DE	Cancelled	0.08		Saline aquifer

Table A-1: An overview of BECCS projects (sources: Biorecro, 2011; Milne and Field, 2012; Kemper, 2015)

Study/ Source	Main Assumptions	Main Outputs
Rhodes and Keith, 2005	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Burning hydrogen-rich syngas to produce electricity with CCS. - Non-fuel O&M cost: Capacity factor of 0.8. - Electricity cost: Biomass fuel cost and CO₂ sequestration cost of \$50 per dry ton and \$10 per ton, respectively, as well as amortization of capital costs at 10% interest over 20 years. - Cost of carbon mitigation: Computed relative to pulverized coal power generation with fuel, capital, non-fuel O&M cost and net efficiency of 1.0 \$GJ⁻¹, 1.2 \$W⁻¹, 8\$MWh⁻¹, and 40% (HHV*), respectively; coal and biomass carbon intensities of 24 and 25 kgC-1GJ⁻¹, respectively, with the same amortization and utilization assumptions outlined above. These assumptions yield coal electricity cost of 37 \$MWh⁻¹. 	<p>Summary model results</p> <p>Biomass-IGCC</p> <p><i>Process performance</i> Capacity (MWth):444, Net generation (MWe): 149, Net efficiency: 34%, C-capture rate (% input C): 0%, Net emissions (kg C kWh⁻¹): 0.</p> <p><i>Economic performance</i> Capital cost (\$kW⁻¹): \$1,250, Non-fuel O&M cost (\$ kW⁻¹y⁻¹): \$100, Electricity cost (cents kWh⁻¹): 5.9, Cost of carbon mitigation (\$ tC⁻¹): \$102.</p> <p>Biomass-IGCC with CCS</p> <p><i>Process performance</i> Capacity (MWth):444, Net generation (MWe): 123, Net efficiency: 28%, C-capture rate (% input C): 44%, Net emissions (kg C kWh⁻¹): -0.14.</p> <p><i>Economic performance</i> Capital cost (\$kW⁻¹): \$1,730, Non-fuel O&M cost (\$ kW⁻¹y⁻¹): \$131, Electricity cost (cents kWh⁻¹): 8.2, Cost of carbon mitigation (\$ tC⁻¹): \$123.</p>
Keith et al., 2006		70 USD/tCO ₂ captured.
IEAGHG, 2009	Co-firing shares 10%. Lower numbers possible when including revenues from emissions trading or green certificates.	<p>BECCS Cost Estimates</p> <p>94 EUR/MWh SC PC-CCS co-firing. 102 EUR/MWh SC CFB-CCS co-firing. 222 EUR/MWh Sub CFB-CCS dedicated. 301 EUR/MWh Sub BFB-CCS dedicated.</p>
Biorecro, 2011		<p>BECCS Cost Estimates</p> <p>700-900 SEK/tCO₂ combustion (~75-95 EUR/tCO₂). < 500 SEK/tCO₂ ethanol, black liquor/pulp (< 45 EUR/tCO₂).</p>
Carbo et al., 2011	<p>Nth BioSNG plant with 500 MWth input (greenfield plant in The Netherlands, 2010) with the following assumptions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gasification pressure: 7 bar. • Total Capital Investment (TCI): 1,100 €/kW. • O&M cost: 5% of TCI. • Other fixed cost: 2% of TCI. • Return on Investment: 12%. • Depreciation period: 15 years. • Interest rate: 5%. • Biomass price (dry) 4 €/GJ. • Electricity price: 0.05 €/kWh. 	<p>The techno-economic analysis resulted in a BioSNG price of 13.28 €/GJ (LHV) including CCS. The BioSNG price is governed by the use of imported biomass at 4.0 €/GJ, which is as a conservative price estimate (this translates to 5.69 €/GJ of the BioSNG price). The total capital investment and related charges, O&M and fixed cost, complete most of the remaining cost. The CO₂ avoidance cost was calculated using the current natural gas commodity price of 7.50 €/GJ and an emission of 0.055 tonne CO₂/GJ for natural gas combustion. The supply chain and flue gas CO₂ emissions were deducted (0.016 tonne CO₂/GJ), therefore the cost of CO₂ avoided in comparison with fossil natural gas combustion amount approximately 62 €/tonne CO₂. This is under the assumption that negative CO₂ emissions can be accounted for. The CO₂ avoidance cost roughly double to 120 €/tonne CO₂ if negative CO₂</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CO₂ emission natural gas combustion: 55.0 kg/GJ. 	<p>emissions cannot be accounted for.</p> <p>Annual Cost (M€/yr) TCI: 55.15, Biomass: 89.72, Electricity: 10.90, O&M: 28.62, Other fixed cost: 11.45, Total cost: 195.84, Result: 13.54, Revenues: 209.38.</p> <p>Cost (€/GJ_{SNG}) TCI: 3.50, Biomass: 5.69, Electricity: 0.69, O&M: 1.82, Other fixed cost: 0.73, Total cost: 12.42, Result: 0.86, Revenues: 13.28.</p>
Laude et al., 2011	Ethanol plant	<p>BECCS Cost Estimates</p> <p>56-86 EUR/tCO₂ fermentation only. 131-143 EUR/tCO₂ fermentation + cogeneration.</p>
Koornneef et al., 2012	<p>This study shows the global potential for combining biomass with CCS technologies (BECCS) up to 2030 and 2050. The assessment includes six bio-CCS routes for the production of power and biofuels in combination with CCS.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Electricity production PC-CCS co-firing: Co-firing share is 30% in 2030 and 50% in 2050, Post-combustion capture. - CFB-CCS dedicated: 100% biomass share, Post-combustion capture. - IGCC-CCS co-firing: Co-firing share is 30% in 2030 and 50% in 2050, Pre-combustion capture. - BIGCC-CCS dedicated: 100% biomass share, Pre-combustion capture. - Biofuel production - Bio-ethanol-advanced generation: 100% biomass share, nearly pure CO₂; only drying and compression. - FT biodiesel: 100% biomass share, Nearly pure CO₂ from pre-combustion; only compression <p>Overall conversion costs are calculated based on a depreciation period of 30 years, a discount rate of 10% and 8000 full load hours per year.</p> <p>All costs are presented in €2010 unless otherwise stated.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The economic potential for BECCS technologies is up to 20 EJ/yr for bio-electricity routes or up to 26 EJ/yr for the biofuel routes, when assuming a CO₂ price of 50 €/tonne. About one third (up to 3.5 Gt CO₂ eq./yr) of the technical potential can be considered economically attractive when producing bio-electricity; and about half (up to 3.1 Gt CO₂ eq./yr) of the technical potential is attractive in the case of biofuel production. - For the medium to long-term, the route using the BIGCC with CCS has the lowest cost of electricity production when using low cost biomass. - The largest economic potential of about 20 EJ/yr (biomass share) is in the gasification-based routes (IGCC and BIGCC) for the year 2050. The smallest economic potential is in the PC and CFB routes of about 1 EJ/yr for the year 2030. - For the biofuel routes, the economic potential is calculated to be highest for the FT-biodiesel route, at 26 EJ/yr and equivalent to -3.1 Gt CO₂eq./yr. - Estimates for the economic potential are highly sensitive to the CO₂ price, coal price and biomass price.
McGlashan et al., 2012	Dedicated 1GW plant in a 0.1 ppm/yr reduction scenario, costs for CCS components may be underestimated due to lack of commercial experience. < 100 USD/tCO ₂ possible but highly uncertain.	<p>BECCS Cost Estimates</p> <p>59-111 USD/tCO₂e captured.</p>

McLaren, 2012 based on Biorecro, 2011	150 USD/tCO ₂ in 2030 possible.	70-250 USD/tCO ₂ combustion. 45 USD/tCO ₂ ethanol, black liquor/pulp.
IEAGHG(2011, 2013)	Breakdown figures are 2030/2050. Reference technologies are coal PC-CCS at 4.0/2.5 and coal IGCC-CCS at 3.6/2.3.	BECCS Cost Estimates 0.5-8.3 EUR/GJ (capture cost, 2030), 0.4-5.1 EUR/GJ (capture cost, 2050). <i>Breakdown: EUR/GJ</i> 4.3/2.7 PC-CCS co-firing, 8.3/5.1 CFB-CCS dedicated, 3.6/2.3 IGCC-CCS co-firing, 4.0/2.5 BIGCC-CCS dedicated, 0.4/0.4 bioethanol, 1.1/1.0 FT biodiesel, 0.5/0.5 gasification, 0.8/0.7 anaerobic digestion EC&AR, 0.8/0.7 anaerobic digestion MSW, 1.1/1.0 anaerobic digestion S/M ~70-110 USD/tCO ₂ . ~10-90 EUR/tCO ₂
Koornneef et al., 2013	- Assessment of two BECCS routes for the production of biomethane: gasification and anaerobic digestion. - CO ₂ storage costs: 1-13 € per tonne (default value of 5 € per tonne). - Natural gas prices: 6.7-11.4 €/GJ.	The economic potential reaches up to 0.8 Gt of negative GHG emissions when assuming a CO ₂ price of 50 €/tonne.
PROSUITE (D6.4), 2013	- CO ₂ emissions captured on top of the carbon-neutral bioenergy will receive credits that can be sold at the carbon price.	Biomass-fired power plants with CCS Biomass-IGCC without CCS Net plant efficiency (%): 42.10, Net output (MW): 629.00, Capacity factor (%): 80, Biomass price (€/GJ LHV): 2.98, Fuel price (€/MMBtu of biomass): 3.17, Total Plant Cost (TPC), (€/kW): 1991.00, Total Overnight Cost (TOC), (€/kW): 2363.56, Total fixed operating costs (annual unit costs),(€/kW-net): 63.38, Total variable operating costs (€/kW-net): 0.01, CO ₂ Capture: 0%, CO ₂ TS & M Costs (mills €/kWh): 0.00, CO ₂ Emissions (Kg/MWh): 0, Operational Period: 30 years, Discount rate (%): 10%. Biomass-IGCC with CCS Net plant efficiency (%): 31.20, Net output (MW): 497.00, Capacity factor (%): 80, Biomass price (€/GJ LHV): 2.98, Fuel price (€/MMBtu of biomass): 3.17, Total Plant Cost (TPC), (€/kW): 2814.79, Total Overnight Cost (TOC), (€/kW): 3354.26, Total fixed operating costs (annual unit costs),(€/kW-net): 72.42, Total variable operating costs (€/kW-net): 0.01, CO ₂ Capture: 90%, CO ₂ TS & M Costs (mills €/kWh): 4.17, CO ₂ , Emissions (Kg/MWh): -790, Operational Period: 30 years, Discount rate (%): 10%.
Akgul et al., 2014	First figure for a reduction in carbon intensity of > 87%, second for carbon negative electricity.	BECCS Cost Estimates 30-50 GBP/tCO ₂ . 120-175 GBP/tCO ₂ .
Arasto et al., 2014	For industrial BECCS depending on the technology in Finland.	BECCS Cost Estimates 35-300 EUR/tCO ₂ stored.
IPCC, 2014		BECCS Cost Estimates

		60-250 USD/tCO ₂ .
Moreira and Pires, 2016		Storage costs of: - 3 USD/t CO ₂ for onshore depleted oil and gas fields, - 7 USD/t CO ₂ for offshore depleted oil and gas fields; - 5 USD/t CO ₂ for aquifers - 5-10 USD/t CO ₂ for coal seams.
Moreira et al., 2016	<p>- Case study on a BECCS scheme, where CCS is applied to CO₂ vented from a Brazilian ethanol fermentation installation using ethanol by-products (bagasse and other sugar cane residues). The by-products are used for the production of heat and bioelectricity self-consumption, as well as for third party users through the electric grid.</p> <p>- Figures calculated by authors considering: ethanol w/BECCS consumer price = US\$ 0.621/l, financing interest rate = 2%, equity share = 20%, IRR on equity = 6%.</p>	<p>Impacts on the cost and prices of BECCS and in fuel and electricity due different government policies</p> <p>No carbon tax</p> <p>Producer cost increase Overnight BECCS cost (US\$/tCO₂): 27.2, Real BECCS price (US/tCO₂): 30.293, Bioelectricity (US\$/MW h): 1.494, Ethanol (US\$/l): 0.021, Bioelectricity (%):5.91%, Ethanol (%): 3.50%.</p> <p>Consumer price increase Overnight BECCS cost (US\$/tCO₂): -, Real BECCS price (US/tCO₂): 47.908, Bioelectricity (US\$/MW h): 2.716, Ethanol (US\$/l): 0.0334, Bioelectricity (%): 2.00%, Ethanol (%): 3.50%.</p> <p>Shared Consumer price increase Overnight BECCS cost (US\$/tCO₂): -, Real BECCS price (US/tCO₂): 48.908, Bioelectricity (US\$/MW h): 0.412, Ethanol (US\$/l): 0.0066, Bioelectricity (%):0.30%, Ethanol (%): 0.70%.</p> <p>With carbon tax @ US\$ 10/tCO₂</p> <p>Producer cost increase Overnight BECCS cost (US\$/tCO₂): -, Real BECCS price (US/tCO₂): 19.93, Bioelectricity (US\$/MW h): 19.93, Ethanol (US\$/l): 0.0141, Bioelectricity (%): 3.96%, Ethanol (%): 1.48%.</p> <p>Consumer price increase Overnight BECCS cost (US\$/tCO₂): -, Real BECCS price (US/tCO₂): 32.094, Bioelectricity (US\$/MW h): 1.819, Ethanol (US\$/l): 0.0224, Bioelectricity (%):1.07%, Ethanol (%): 2.35%.</p> <p>Shared Consumer price increase Overnight BECCS cost (US\$/tCO₂): -, Real BECCS price (US/tCO₂): 32.094, Bioelectricity (US\$/MW h): 0.276, Ethanol (US\$/l): 0.0044, Bioelectricity (%): 0.02%, Ethanol (%): 0.47%.</p> <p>With tax moratorium</p> <p>Consumer price increase Overnight BECCS cost (US\$/tCO₂): -, Real BECCS price (US/tCO₂): 34.364, Bioelectricity (US\$/MW h): 1.494, Ethanol (US\$/l): 0.0246, Bioelectricity (%): 1.10%, Ethanol (%): 2.58%.</p> <p>Shared Consumer price increase Overnight BECCS cost (US\$/tCO₂): -, Real BECCS price (US/tCO₂): 34.364, Bioelectricity (US\$/MW h): 0.276, Ethanol (US\$/l): 0.0048, Bioelectricity (%): 0.17%, Ethanol</p>

		<p>(%): 0.50%.</p> <p>The overall cost of capturing and storing CO₂ is US\$ 53/tCO₂ and yet the study concludes that applying CCS to sugar fermentation is the less expensive option.</p>
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Table A-2: Key assumptions and findings from cost assessment studies on BECCS

Study/ Source	Main Assumptions	Main Outputs
Kraxner et al., 2003	Average carbon sequestration, BECCS associated with single 'typical' temperate forest. 90% capture rate, scenario based approach to forest management.	Net emissions: 2.5 tC/yr/ha.
Rhodes and Keith, 2005	Biomass IGCC 44% capture rate; net efficiency 28%. Biomass IGCC, with Steam reforming 55% capture rate; net efficiency 25%.	Biomass IGCC: Net emissions: -140 gC/KWh. Biomass IGCC, with Steam reforming: Net emissions: -200 gC/KWh.
Corti and Lombardi, 2004	Technology: BIGCC Biomass type: Poplar Biomass ratio (%): 100 Co-firing ratio (%):100 Capacity (MW): 205 Capture technology: Upstream Chemical Absorption Environmental themes covered: GHG	Life cycle CO ₂ emissions (g/kW h): 70-130. Net life cycle CO ₂ emissions (g/kW h): -410.
Spath and Mann, 2004	Technology: BIGCC and Co-firing Biomass type: Urban Waste-Energy crops Biomass ratio (%):100% and 0-15 Co-firing ratio (%):15 Capacity (MW): 600 Capture technology: Post combustion with MEA Environmental themes covered: GHG	Life cycle CO ₂ emissions (g/kW h): 270. Net life cycle CO ₂ emissions (g/kW h): 43.
Carpentieri et al., 2005	Technology: BIGCC Biomass type: Poplar Biomass ratio (%): 100 Co-firing ratio (%):100 Capacity (MW): 191 Capture technology: Upstream Chemical Absorption Environmental themes covered: ALL	Life cycle CO ₂ emissions (g/kW h): 227. Net life cycle CO ₂ emissions (g/kW h): -594.
IEAGHG, 2009	- CFB boiler, biomass only: Net plant efficiency: 33.8% (LHV*) 90% capture rate. - CFB, 10% biomass co-fired: Net plant efficiency: 25.8% (LHV*)	- CFB boiler, biomass only: Net emissions: -1573 gCO ₂ eq/KWh. - CFB, 10% biomass co-fired: Net emissions: -32 gCO ₂ eq /KWh.

	90% capture rate *LHV – lower heat value (heat gained) from combustion, excluding energy released in water vapor.	
Laude et al., 2011	Investigated potential carbon and energy footprints for BECCS from ethanol production in the CPER Artenay project.	BECCS from fermentation only would reduce the carbon footprint by 60% and BECCS from fermentation and cogeneration could decrease the carbon footprint by 115%, i.e. produce negative emissions.
Cuellar, 2012	Technology: Coal co-firing plant Biomass type: Farmed trees, switch grass, forest residue Biomass ratio (%):0–100 Co-firing ratio (%): 20 Capacity (MW): 75-200 Capture technology: Post combustion with MEA Environmental themes covered: GHG.	Life cycle CO ₂ emissions (g/kW h): Not reported. Net life cycle CO ₂ emissions (g/kW h): -129.5.
Koornneef et al., 2012	This study shows the global potential for combining biomass with CCS technologies (BECCS) up to 2030 and 2050. The assessment includes six bio-CCS routes for the production of power and biofuels in combination with CCS. - Electricity production PC-CCS co-firing: Co-firing share is 30% in 2030 and 50% in 2050, Post-combustion capture. - CFB-CCS dedicated: 100% biomass share, Post-combustion capture - IGCC-CCS co-firing: Co-firing share is 30% in 2030 and 50% in 2050, Pre-combustion capture. - BIGCC-CCS dedicated: 100% biomass share, Pre-combustion capture. - Biofuel production - Bio-ethanol-advanced generation: 100% biomass share, nearly pure CO ₂ ; only drying and compression. - FT biodiesel: 100% biomass share, Nearly pure CO ₂ from pre-combustion; only compression.	- The global technical potential for BECCS technologies is large and, if deployed, can result in negative greenhouse gas emissions. The economic potential for BECCS technologies is up to 20 EJ/yr for bio-electricity routes or up to 26 EJ/yr for the biofuel routes, when assuming a CO ₂ price of 50 €/tonne. About one third (up to 3.5 Gt CO ₂ eq./yr) of the technical potential can be considered economically attractive when producing bio-electricity; and about half (up to 3.1 Gt CO ₂ eq./yr) of the technical potential is attractive in the case of biofuel production. - The amount of sustainable biomass that can be harvested and supplied greatly determines the potential for BECCS technologies. - Up to 59 EJ/yr of bio-electricity, or 47 EJ/yr of biofuels can be produced when deploying the full technical potential. - The amount of CO ₂ stored by conversion routes ranges between 0.7 and 20.9 Gt CO ₂ /yr. - Negative emissions up to 10.4 Gt CO ₂ eq./yr are the highest for the dedicated routes with CCS: BIGCC and CFB. The negative emissions for the biofuel routes with CCS are the lowest, ranging between 0.5 and 5.8 Gt CO ₂ eq./yr.
NETL (vol.1), 2012	Technology: IGCC Biomass type: Switch grass Biomass ratio (%):0–100 Co-firing ratio (%): 30 (weight) Capacity (MW): 451–654 Capture technology: Post combustion with MEA and Oxyfuel	Life cycle CO ₂ emissions (g/kW h): Not reported. Net life cycle CO ₂ emissions (g/kW h): -6 to -105.

	Environmental themes covered: GHG	
NETL (vol.2), 2012	<p>Technology: Super Critical Coal co-firing plant</p> <p>Biomass type: Hybrid Poplar</p> <p>Biomass ratio (%):0-100</p> <p>Co-firing ratio (%): 30</p> <p>Capacity (MW): 550</p> <p>Capture technology: Post combustion with MEA and Oxyfuel</p> <p>Environmental themes covered: GHG</p>	<p>Life cycle CO₂ emissions (g/kW h): Not reported.</p> <p>Net life cycle CO₂ emissions (g/kW h): 38.</p>
Koornneef et al., 2013	<p>- Assessment of two BECCS routes for the production of biomethane: gasification and anaerobic digestion.</p>	<p>Negative greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) up to 3.5 Gt CO₂-eq. on an annual basis in 2050.</p> <p>Including avoided emissions by replacing natural gas, the annual greenhouse gas emission savings could add up to almost 8 Gt of CO₂-eq in 2050.</p>
Volkart et al., 2013	<p>Evaluating three types of wood power plants without/with CO₂ capture to examine if combustion or gasification of wood from sustainable forestry is "CO₂-neutral".</p>	<p>All the three types of wood power plants were found to have very low life-cycle GHG emissions without CO₂ capture and negative life-cycle GHG emissions with CO₂ capture.</p> <p>Conclusions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Combustion or gasification of wood from sustainable forestry is "CO₂-neutral", i.e. using only the natural growth and keeping the carbon stock in the forest at a constant level. - The carbon in the biogenic CO₂ emissions from wood combustion or gasification was taken up by the trees during their growth and is therefore permanently removed from the atmosphere by CCS.
Arasto et al., 2014	<p>The emission reduction potential in different technologies is very much bound to the scale of installations which again is generally limited by the scale of technologies and availability of biomass raw material.</p>	<p>The biggest reduction potential for the studied cases per industrial site:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - iron and steel industry (~3 Mt/a), -pulp and paper industry (~1.3 Mt/a) -combined heat power (CHP) production (~2.5 Mt/a) - straw ethanol production of smaller scale (~0.1 Mt/a). <p>The CO₂ avoidance potential per unit of biomass raw material utilized is highest in co-firing (20tCO₂/toe), iron and steel industry (10tCO₂/toe) and in CHP production (8tCO₂/toe).</p> <p>Straw ethanol has lowest potential (1.5 tCO₂/toe).</p> <p>The cost estimations show a theoretical economic advantage of BECCS over fossil CCS on carbon prices when the carbon sink effect is accounted for. The total costs for BECCS vary from 35€/ton to 300€/ton CO₂ stored depending on the technology.</p>
Schakel et al., 2014	<p>Technology: PC, IGCC.</p> <p>Biomass type: Wood pellets/straw pellets (residues)</p> <p>Biomass ratio (%):0-100</p> <p>Co-firing ratio (%): 30</p> <p>Capacity (MW): 550</p>	<p>Life cycle CO₂ emissions (g/kW h): 281-291, 253-262.</p> <p>Net life cycle CO₂ emissions (g/kW h): -67 to -72, -81 to -85.</p>

	Capture technology: pre-combustion CO ₂ capture Environmental themes covered: ALL	
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Table A-3: Key assumptions and findings from LCA literature studies on BECCS

Annex II

To recognize needs for further assessment regarding the case of BECCS, two relevant associations were identified: namely, the Joint Task Force the European Technology Platform for Zero Emission Fossil Fuel Power Plants (ZEP) and the European Biofuels Technology Platform (EBTP) established by Bellona¹² and composed of the European Technology Platforms for Zero Emission Fossil Fuel Power Plants and the European Biofuels Technology Platform (ZEP and EBTP respectively). To extract the views of ZEP and EBTP, their joint recent report on “Biomass with CO₂ Capture and Storage (BECCS) - The way forward for Europe” (EBTP, 2012) as well as the recent brief by BELLONA “The Carbon-Negative Solution: Incentivizing BIO-CCS in Europe” (Andersen M., 2015), were reviewed to summarize notified challenges and future research efforts to exploit the full potential of BECCS. In addition representatives from both of these organizations were contacted by email to provide their viewpoints on assessment needs, which may help to address the challenges currently preventing further BECCS technology deployment¹³. Table A-4 below summarizes the efforts of the consultation process and relevant position papers identified for the case of BECCS.

Organization	Type of association	Position Papers	Year of publication*	Region	Summary	Contact person
BELLONA- The Bellona Foundation	Environmental non-profit foundation	http://network.bellona.org/content/uploads/sites/3/2015/11/BellonaBrief-The-carbon-negative-solution.pdf	2015	Europe	http://bellona.org/contact	Ellen Viseth
European Biofuels Technology Platform	Coalition of stakeholders from interdisciplinary fields (e.g. Research and Academia, NGOs, companies)	http://www.biofuelstp.eu/downloads/bioccstjtf/EBTP-ZEP-Report-Bio-CCS-The-Way-Forward.pdf	2012	Europe	secretariat@biofuelstp.eu	Judit Sandquist
Zero Emissions Platform (ZEP)					http://www.zeroemissionsplatform.eu/contact.html	N/A

Table A-4: Consultation process-relevant position papers identified for the case of BECCS

¹²The Bellona Foundation is an independent non-profit organization that aims to meet and fight the climate challenges, through identifying and implementing sustainable environmental solutions.

¹³SINTEF, the largest independent research organization in Scandinavia and member of the ZEP has responded during the consultation, providing feedback through semi-structured answers highlighting their positions on the challenges and assessment needs for BECCS technology.

In response to the open-ended question **“What are the main challenges related to Bio-Energy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) that the network you represent is struggling with?”** SINTEF notes:

- ✓ The existence of a wide diversity of BECCS options according to the wide range of biomass feedstock available worldwide for biofuel and bioenergy production (e.g. energy crops, wastes agricultural residues, forestry residues and novel feedstock such as algae).
- ✓ To ensure sufficient, sustainable supply of bio-resources necessary and available to promote large-scale deployment of BECCS.
- ✓ The implementation of accounting methods for negative emissions.
- ✓ The need to improve public awareness and acceptance regarding CCS projects and applications in general.

Finally future assessment needs, in response to the open-ended question **“What are the needs for further research, which may help to address these challenges (from your and/or the network you represent point of view)”**, as recommended by SINTEF entail:

- ✓ Adapted combustion technologies (boilers, furnaces, gasification)
- ✓ Impact of biomass related impurities on CO₂ quality and the whole CCS chain and
- ✓ LCA analysis for the different BECCS options (power, fuels, chemicals, ...)

Finally, in response to the open question **“For which of the following sustainability dimensions do you consider there is a greater need for further assessment (for the case of Bio-Energy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS))? Use the scale 0-5 to weight their urgency for further research (0 indicates limited need for further research and 5 indicates great urgency for further research)”** SINTEF provided us with the following weights:

	Economic-Prosperity dimension (Costs-Benefits)	Social dimension (Social Costs-Benefits)	Environmental/Health/Exhaustible Resources dimension (Climate-Environmental Benefits: mitigation, Costs: Impact on climate, environment and human health)	Market Readiness dimension (Maturity-Diffusion level)	Technological dimension (Uncertainty according to future performance)
0-5 scale	4	4	5	3	4

A justification for this response wasn't provided.

Annex III

No	Research Need	Literature source	Cited in position papers & related stakeholders
1	Focus on developing an LCOE method that better clarifies assumptions such as costs, financing, lifetime and loan terms, in order to acquire more realistic results	(CHEETAH, 2016a; Branker, et al., 2011; Solar Bankability, 2016a)	
2	Analysis of the design of innovative funding mechanisms (e.g. crowd-funding) supporting investments from the private sector and their potential to provide assurance for long-term financial return	(PV Financing, 2016; IEA, 2014b; EC, 2013)	
3	Analysing replication requirements & conditions for success of best-case funding schemes implemented in EU countries	(PV Financing, 2016; IEA, 2014b; EC, 2013)	
4	To enable the transfer of these mechanisms in other country-contexts empirical investigation of such schemes through detailed case-study analysis and ex-post performance evaluations should take place.	(Goodrich, et al., 2013; PV Financing, 2016; IEA, 2014b)	
5	Benchmarking analysis of support mechanisms with other economies are important for further deploying and diversifying the PV industry and deserve special research attention	(Goodrich, et al., 2013)	✓
6	Overhaul of energy market rules and regulations, to better reflect the specificities of variable energy sources, with emphasis given on free, fair, and open global markets and a level playing field between energy generating technologies. More grid studies with high VAR RES scenarios should thus take place	(IEA, 2015a)	✓
7	Research on the optimal mix of RES technologies that has minimum intermittency effects to the grid's operation should take place	(Graabak & Korpås, 2016)	
8	Storage of energy and demand side management should be studied as options for reducing the variability effects of RES technologies, as well as the degree of variability they can handle before incorporating thermal plants as stabilizing factors	(Graabak & Korpås, 2016; EDF R&D, 2015; Huber, et al., 2014; IEA, 2014a; Lingfors, 2015)	

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|----|--|---|---|
| 9 | R&D on developing advanced meteorological forecasting tools that give accurate results of the expected RES electricity generation should be encouraged | (Lingfors, 2015; EDF R&D, 2015) | |
| 10 | Research on operational practices and timing of bidding of services along with advanced forecasting tools is still missing | (REserviceS, 2014) | |
| 11 | New markets and services design, such as frequency restoration reserve and frequency containment reserve, that consider both the characteristics of VAR RES the power system and ancillary services | (IEA, 2014a) | ✓ |
| 12 | Research on cost declines and technological innovations that will enable DR business models to be less dependent on policy and regulatory conditions | (Burger & Luke, 2016) | |
| 13 | Research on the optimal mix of load shifting (DR) and energy storage that will facilitate the aggregation of PV | (Azzopardi & Gabriel-Buenaventura, 2014) | ✓ |
| 14 | The consumer benefits that smart meters can offer are still unclear to the public; hence social acceptance is still conservative. Further monitoring efforts and ex-post evaluations should take place to provide more empirical evidence on the benefits of smart-meter deployment. In addition, demonstration projects and information provision regarding those benefits is required to act persuasively for the public | (PATHWAYS, 2015a) | |
| 15 | Design of incentives provision at peak times | (IEA, 2014a) | ✓ |
| 16 | Further research on Demand Response (DR) and storage technologies, on the basis that they provide capacity-based services | (Parag & Sovacool, 2016; Burger & Luke, 2016; INSIGHT ENERGY, 2015) | |
| 17 | Research on the potential that car batteries have to act as “peak-demand reducers” when connected to the grid and how Information and Communication Technology (ICT) can support the control of power flows | (PROSUITE, 2010) | |
| 18 | Research & demonstration efforts should also be oriented towards improving electric vehicles to compare with more efficient internal combustion ones in terms of performance and distance autonomy | (PROSUITE, 2010; Popiolek & Thais, 2016) | |
| 19 | Design of measures/incentives that promote electric vehicles with simultaneous counter-measures for internal combustion vehicles | (Popiolek & Thais, 2016) | |

- 20 Further research is needed with proper data acquisition for statistically relevant results on the benefits of curtailment for PV and other RES. Examine this aspect in a no priority dispatch environment ✓
- 21 Efforts should be made in developing policy schemes that balances the socio-economic effects of curtailment with the respective costs (INSIGHT ENERGY, 2014; Kane & Ault, 2014; PV GRID, 2014)
- 22 Curtailment should be studied in combination with alternative flexibility options (storage, demand side management etc.), aiming in optimizing the network operation while increasing RES integration to the grid, driving operational costs down and also considering reserve and security requirements (PIC, 2012)
- 23 Open and fair discussion should be performed, to determine the national cost-benefit ratios, the boundary conditions and the compensation rules for the PV owner, in case that curtailment is enforced (compared to grid reinforcement) with a goal to reduce grid expansion expenses (PV GRID, 2014)
- 24 R&D efforts to support technological advancements (i.e. improvement of chiller COP, thermal storage tanks integration, evaporator flow control depending on the weather condition), and processes (i.e. determination of the optimal collector configuration and surface) which will make solar cooling technologies more efficient than electric-mechanical technologies (Nelson, et al., 2014; Testi, et al., 2016; Argouaz, et al., 2017; Hussain, et al., 2016)
- 25 Ongoing research on CSP technology with main goal to increase efficiency and reduce manufacturing costs, to make the technology more competitive in the energy market (UNEP & EPO, 2015)
- 26 Life-cycle analysis (LCA) of a solar cooling/heating system considering PV and heating/cooling devices as a single unit is still missing (Testi, et al., 2016; Hussain, et al., 2016)
- 27 Common methodology for assessing the Product Environmental Footprint of a PV system (LCA-Life Cycle Analysis based on re-use) implementing the Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules (PEFCR) ✓
- 28 LCA should be expanded to integrate global scale challenges, geographical differentiations, rebound effects, renewability of resources and future scenario modelling (Ling-Chin, et al., 2016)

29 Recycling of module components (cables, inverters etc.) apart from modules themselves, should also be considered in LCA since they can significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions	(Solar Bankability, 2016b)	✓
30 Recycling and disposal of harmful material procedures ought to be well defined so that recycling costs are reduced, contributing to safe disposal of modules. Development of standards for recycling processes should support future PV deployment	(Solar Bankability, 2016b)	
31 Material development should be focused in increasing the system's lifetime while reducing the costs of operation and maintenance (O&M)	(Alsema & Nieuwlaar, 2000; Neij, 2008; CHEETAH, 2016b)	
32 Cell manufacturing and wafer handling processes when optimized can contribute to a further cost reduction and increased module efficiency due to defects reduction	(PROSUITE, 2010; Nelson, et al., 2014; EC, 2014a; CHEETAH, 2016b)	
33 Research studies and pilots should focus on the use of less material such as thinner wafers to keep efficiencies high and cost reduced	(Traverso, et al., 2012; PIC, 2012; PROSUITE, 2010; Neij, 2008; CHEETAH, 2016b; Alsema & Nieuwlaar, 2000)	✓
34 Accelerating tests and necessary quality improvements to ensure high lifetime performances of components. The standardization discussion should include the whole value chain – also O&M		✓
35 Inspection periods, downtime and the interval required to complete the necessary O&M operations should be standardized so that no excessive loss of power is happening	(Solar Bankability, 2016c; Solar Bankability, 2016b)	
36 Research in balancing the interests of PV owners, who want maximum energy production from their system, and the interests of O&M contractors who want minimal costs during the maintenance process is still missing	(Solar Bankability, 2016b)	
37 Development of data collection mechanisms that track the operation of PV systems will lead in less visual inspection requirements and drive O&M costs down	(Solar Bankability, 2016b)	

Table A-5: Summary of research needs found in the ensemble of sources reviewed

Annex IV

To recognize needs for further assessment regarding the case of Solar PV, we identified the European Photovoltaic Industry Association¹⁴. To extract the views of EPIA, its recent Position Paper on “Developing a real industrial policy for PV in Europe” (EPIA, 2012) was reviewed to summarize notified challenges and future research efforts to exploit the full potential of Solar PV. To supplement our analysis and enhance our findings, we also reviewed the policy paper “Solar and Storage” jointly authored by Eurobat¹⁵, EHPA¹⁶ and SolarPower Europe (Eurobat, EHPA, SolarPower Europe, 2016). In addition representatives from EPIA were contacted by email to provide their viewpoints on research needs, which may help to address the challenges currently preventing further Solar PV deployment¹⁷. **Table A-6** below summarizes the efforts of the consultation process and relevant position papers identified for the case of Solar PV.

Organization	Type of association	Position Papers	Year of publication*	Region	Summary	Contact person
European Photovoltaic Industry Association-EPIA (old SolarPower Europe)	Member-led Association	http://www.qualenergia.it/sites/default/files/articolo-doc/EPIA_Position_Paper_on_Industrial_Policy.pdf	2012	Europe	http://www.solarpower europe.org	Ioannis-Thomas Theologitis, (Senior Advisor for SolarPower Europe)
Association of European Automotive and Industrial Battery Manufacturers-EUROBAT European Heat Pump Association-EHPA European Photovoltaic Industry	Member-led Associations	https://eurobat.org/sites/default/files/solar_and_storage_position_paper_2016_1.pdf	2016	Europe	http://eurobat.org/ http://www.ehpa.org/ http://www.solarpower europe.org	-

¹⁴SolarPower Europe, the new EPIA (European Photovoltaic Industry Association), is a member-led association representing organizations active along the whole value chain and aiming to shape the regulatory environment and to enhance business opportunities for solar power in Europe.

¹⁵EUROBAT is the association for the European manufacturers of automotive, industrial and energy storage batteries. EUROBAT has 52 members from across the continent comprising more than 90% of the automotive and industrial battery industry in Europe.

¹⁶The European Heat Pump Association (EHPA) represents the majority of the European heat pump industry. Its members comprise of heat pump and component manufacturers, research institutes, universities, testing labs and energy agencies. Its key goal is to promote awareness and proper deployment of heat pump technology in the European market for residential, commercial and industrial applications.

¹⁷Mr Ioannis-Thomas Theologitis, Senior Advisor for SolarPower Europe has been contacted through email and has kindly provided feedback (through a semi-structured questionnaire) on the future challenges for Solar PV, priorities and needs for further research validating and supplementing the ones identified through the review.

Association-EPIA (old SolarPower Europe)						
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Table A-6: Consultation process-relevant position papers identified for the case of Solar PV

In response to the open-ended question **“What are the main challenges related to Solar PV that the network you represent is struggling with?”**Mr. Theologitis notes:

PV has grown and developed beyond anyone’s expectations. It managed to become one of the key technologies of RES for the energy transition. To achieve this, it had to follow a very steep learning curve-reducing the costs and increasing efficiency (conversion and energy). This was the main challenge until a couple of years before-reducing the cost of the technology. Nowadays, this is no longer the first priority. PV is a competitive technology and has proven capable to create value and provide services to many stakeholders. However, to continue the exponential growth and really be at the end center of the energy transition, it has to provide solutions to different challenges that have emerged to the increased shares. Those are indeed mainly regulatory challenges and consequently financial/business challenges. Some main ones that also SolarPower Europe is addressing are included below in bullet points:

- ✓ Market design - The whole electricity market framework in a post support scheme era that will enable valorization of PV technology (within this, issues such as self consumption schemes, flexibility, distribution/aggregation, ancillary services, priority dispatch, curtailment etc, are included).
- ✓ Attached to the above, the energy efficiency and renewable energy directives.
- ✓ Smart Buildings – linked with the energy efficiency discussion and of course the related BIPV technologies. BIPV should be seen as a stand alone component due to multiple functionalities it provides to the building envelope (electricity is only one of them). The discussion is also linked with the automation industry and the EV.
- ✓ Trade Case-Resolving the trade case and create a suitable market and industry environment.
- ✓ Product related matters - Eco-design and Ecolabel. Ensure that PV is assessed properly based on real industry facts and avoiding low quality results that will hamper the market, create more costs and compromise the well earned competitiveness.
- ✓ Industrial Policy - Facilitate EU sustainable growth of the upstream and downstream business with focus on quality infrastructure, employment and value creation. The investment or support of solar should not be seen as sectoral approach – it is aligned with the consumer’s empowerment of the EC.
- ✓ Bankability and Financing issues - Enhancing the confidence of investors, reducing the risk for PV investments, promoting good practices and business models by assessing the current bottlenecks.

Finally future assessment needs, in response to the open-ended question **“What are the needs for further research, which may help to address these challenges (from your and/or the network you represent point of view)”**, as recommended by Mr. Theologitis entail:

- ✓ The technical feasibility has already been proven to a great extent (although grid studies with high VAR RES scenarios should take place). However to implement the technical solutions, the market framework should be in place. The challenge is on building new market and business models that will promote flexibility, synergies with storage technologies/demand response, e-mobility etc. Aggregation of PV systems (especially smaller size systems) and the use of this portfolio for providing services. How digitization can enable this.
- ✓ Evaluating the benefits of curtailment (PV and other RES) – research is needed, as well as proper data acquisition for statistically relevant results. Examine this aspect in a no priority dispatch environment.
- ✓ Assess the impact on DSO/TSO – regarding the grid fees.
- ✓ Assess synergies with the heating/cooling sector (technical and economical).
- ✓ Common methodology for assessing the footprint of a pv system (LCA) – PEFCR implementation. Focus on research around re-use of material in the framework of a circular economy. Additional research on energy efficiency (PV system) and also considering PV with storage. Use of less material – e.g. thinner wafers and keep the efficiencies high and cost reduced.
- ✓ Research on quality criteria and standardization for product development and testing. Accelerating tests and necessary quality improvements to ensure high lifetime performances of components. The standardization discussion touches upon the whole value chain - also O&M.

Finally, in response to the open question **“For which of the following sustainability dimensions do you consider there is a greater need for further assessment (for the case of Solar PV)? Use the scale 0-5 to weight their urgency for further research (0 indicates limited need for further research and 5 indicates great urgency for further research)”** Mr. Theologitis provided us with the following weights:

	Economic-Prosperity dimension (Costs-Benefits)	Social dimension (Social Costs-Benefits)	Environmental/Health/Exhaustible Resources dimension (Climate-Environmental Benefits: mitigation, Costs: Impact on climate, environment and human health)	Market Readiness dimension (Maturity-Diffusion level)	Technological dimension (Uncertainty according to future performance)
0-5 scale	5	3	2	1	5

He justified his response as following:

Economic-Prosperity dimension (Costs-Benefits): This is a key priority because in my mind it includes the political/regulatory dimension too. All the current changes and developments regarding valorising the PV technology in a market framework that tries to adapt in new conditions (RES into the market) are linked with the economic and business dimension for all stakeholders and consumers.

Social dimension (Social Costs-Benefits): By default, the social dimension should not be disregarded, but for PV that is a proven clean renewable option which offers the distributed dimension and directly links with the customer (prosumer) i believe the urgency is less-the social benefits, acceptance by customer (for the residential systems-creating a feeling of ownership and control of power source), value of the technology (e.g. employment) are facts. In most cases, the problems arise from opposing lobbies and of course from the costs that emerge from inflexible market designs or/and bad political and support scheme decisions which damage the "image" of the technology.

Environmental/Health/Exhaustible Resources dimension (Climate-Environmental Benefits: mitigation, Costs: Impact on climate, environment and human health): Many studies have shown great reductions in the energy and material use. PV has developed a lot on that dimension and still does. It is definitely important, but classifying it more than 2 will imply that we are behind on this which is not true-especially in contrast to conventional technologies. I would focus more on the recycling and reuse discussion.

Market Readiness dimension (Maturity-Diffusion level): I am not sure I get this correctly, but I believe PV has already proven to be a mature technology-many claim the word commodity, although I don't personally like this wording for a sophisticated energy technology.

Technological dimension (Uncertainty according to future performance): Always of importance. We have so many things and technologies to work on and improve further. For market exploitation, current technologies are fully bankable, but we would greatly limit ourselves if we say we reached our goals. Technology and processes change and PV should follow this learning curve – especially when it comes with synergies with other sectors (storage, IT etc.)